

DISAC

Document Number: HORIZON-JU-SNS-2023/6G-DISAC/D3.1

Project Name:

6G for **D**istributed **I**ntelligent **S**ensing and **C**ommunication (6G-DISAC)

Deliverable D3.1

Initial solutions towards waveforms, sensing,
communication, and DISAC

The 6G-DISAC project has received funding from the Smart Networks and Services Joint Undertaking (SNS JU) under the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation program under Grant Agreement No 101139130

Deliverable D3.1

Initial solutions towards waveforms, sensing, communication, and DISAC

Project Number:	HORIZON-JU-SNS-2023 - 101139130
Project Name:	<i>6G for Distributed Intelligent Sensing and Communication (6G-DISAC)</i>

Document Number:	HORIZON-JU-SNS-2023/6G-DISAC/D3.1
Document Title:	Initial solutions towards waveforms, sensing, communication, and DISAC
Editor(s):	Benoît Denis (CEA)
Authors:	Raffaele D'Errico, Tan-Tho Luc, Benoît Denis, Tom Malherbe, Francesca Costanzo, Emilio Calvanese Strinati (CEA), Henk Wymeersch, Furkan Keskin, Hui Chen, Yu Ge, Sauradeep Dey, Mengting Li (CHAL), Sami Mekki (NOKIA), Francois Rivet (IMS), Giyyarpuram Madhusudan, Guillaume Larue (ORA), Ioannis Gavras, Kyriakos Stylianopoulos, George Alexandropoulos (NKUA), Placido Mursia, Marco Rossanese (NEC)
Dissemination Level:	PU
Contractual Date of Delivery:	30/06/2025 (M18)
Security:	Public
Status:	Final
Version:	1.0
File Name:	6G-DISAC_D3.1_v1.0.docx

Abstract

This document presents preliminary algorithmic studies and simulation-based evaluation results regarding the radio physical layer, which have been put forward in the context of the 6G-DISAC project to support Distributed Integrated Sensing and Communication (DISAC) functionalities in future wireless networks. First, a reminder of the DISAC foundations and key concepts is provided, followed by a review of suitable state-of-the-art physical models and simulations tools that can be used for validations. Then, focusing on wireless transmissions, various proposals are made in terms of waveform shaping, physical layer parameters optimisation, and physical network deployment, to enable spatially distributed sensing and localisation operations, as well as efficient transmissions of the acquired sensing data to tiers for further processing. Subsequently, putting emphasis on processing operations on the receiver side, detection and estimation methods are proposed for the distributed localisation and tracking of both passive objects and connected users in a plurality of deployment scenarios, as well as for simultaneous localisation and mapping purposes, while addressing relevant trade-offs between complexity and accuracy. Finally, it is shown how the communication network can benefit from sensing information, typically for improved handover, beamforming and beam tracking, or full-duplex operations.

Keywords

6G; Integrated Sensing and Communications (ISAC); Distributed ISAC (DISAC); Physical (PHY) layer optimisation; Waveform design; Detection and estimation algorithms; Simultaneous localisation and mapping (SLAM); Sensing-aided communications; Simulation Tools; Propagation channel, antenna, and radar cross section models, European Smart Networks and Services Joint Undertaking (SNS JU).

Disclaimer

This work has been performed in the framework of the Horizon Europe project 6G-DISAC co-funded by the EU. This information reflects the consortium's view, but the consortium is not liable for any use that may be made of any of the information contained therein. This deliverable has been submitted to the EU commission, but it has not been reviewed, and it has not been accepted by the EU commission yet.

Contents

1	Introduction	15
2	Reminder of DISAC Principles and Architecture	16
2.1	Main Principles.....	16
2.1.1	Foundation of Network-based Localisation and Sensing	16
2.1.2	Foundation of Location-aided Wireless Communications	19
2.1.3	Foundation of Integrated Sensing and Communication	20
2.1.4	Expected Benefits and Challenges from Distributed Settings and Solutions.....	21
2.2	Foreseen Architecture and Related Aspects	22
2.2.1	Implications of Processing Segmentation and Data Representation.....	22
2.2.2	Support to Passive Objects Tracking and Handover	24
2.2.3	Support to Heterogeneous Devices.....	24
2.3	Interplay with Semantic Reasoning and Control	25
3	Relevant Physical Models, Channel Features, and Simulation Tools for DISAC.....	26
3.1	Main Channel Features	28
3.1.1	Large Antenna Array and Near Field	28
3.1.2	Blockages	29
3.1.3	Doppler and Mobility	30
3.1.4	Spatial Consistency and Distributed Aspects	30
3.1.5	RIS-enabled Channel Models.....	30
3.1.6	Radar Cross Section and Object Backscattering.....	31
3.2	Overview on DISAC-Oriented Channel Measurements and Models	33
4	Physical Layer Optimisation and Adaptive Waveform Shaping.....	35
4.1	Physical Layer Solutions and Waveforms Shaping for the Transmission, Collection, and Fusion of Distributed Sensing Data.....	37
	Contribution #A-1: Semantic Waveforms for AI-native 6G Networks	37
4.2	Physical Layer Solutions and Waveforms Shaping for Distributed Sensing and Localisation Operations	41
4.2.1	Contribution #A-2: Waveform Design for Cooperative RIS-aided Localisation.....	41
4.2.2	Contribution #A-3: Onsite Anchor Beam Pattern Calibration.....	43
4.3	Physical Layer Solutions and Waveforms Shaping for Simultaneous Communication and Sensing Operations	45
4.3.1	Contribution #A-4: Monostatic Integrated Sensing and Communication: Receiver Design and Trade-off Analysis	45
4.3.2	Contribution #A-5: Secure MIMO Systems Exploiting Interference with Bayesian Cramer-Rao Bound Optimisation for Eavesdroppers Detection under Guaranteed Communication QoS.....	48
5	Sensing, Localisation, and Tracking of Active and Passive Objects	49
5.1	Localisation of Connected Users.....	54
5.1.1	Contribution #B-1: Joint RIS Channel Estimation and Localisation via Dictionary Learning and Compressed Sensing.....	54
5.1.2	Contribution #B-2: Frugal Localisation and Synchronisation with Multiple Reconfigurable Intelligent Surfaces	55
5.1.3	Contribution #B-3: Phase-coherent Downlink Localisation and Synchronisation with Distributed Access Points	57
5.1.4	Contribution #B-4: Joint Localisation, Synchronisation and Mapping via Phase-Coherent Distributed Arrays.....	59
5.1.5	Contribution #B-5: Near-Field Localisation with Dynamic Metasurface Antennas at THz	61
5.1.6	Contribution #B-6: Mobile User Localisation and Tracking Exploiting Mobile RISs and Fixed Beacons.....	62

5.1.7	Contribution #B-7: Opportunistic User Localisation based on Available RIS Configurations and Environment Knowledge	64
5.2	Sensing of Passive Objects.....	66
5.2.1	Contribution #B-8: Sensing based on 5G Standard Signals within Distributed Architectures.....	66
5.2.2	Contribution #B-9: Cooperative Sensing of Side Lobes Interference for Blockage Detection and Localisation in Dense mmWave Networks	68
5.2.3	Contribution #B-10: Detection and Cooperative Localisation of Moving Passive Objects through RIS Beam Scanning of Non-coherent Power Sources	71
5.2.4	Contribution #B-11: Large-scale/Long-term Targets Tracking based on Cooperative Sensing Nodes	75
5.2.5	Contribution #B-12: Joint Detection and Localisation of Multiple Moving Targets in a Distributed Radar System	76
5.2.6	Contribution #B-13: mmWave Cellular Passive Drone Detection with Reconfigurable Intelligent Surfaces	78
5.2.7	Contribution #B-14: RF Imaging based on Physics-Informed Neural Networks and New Physical Models.....	80
5.2.8	Contribution #B-15: Digital Twin Aided Sensing	83
6	Sensing-Aided Communications.....	86
6.1	Sensing-/Location-aided Dynamic Handover Management	88
	Contribution #C-1: Sensing-aided Handover Triggering Policy in Dense mmWave Networks.....	88
6.2	Sensing-/Location-aided Full-Duplex Communications.....	91
	Contribution #C-2: Simultaneous Near-Field Communications and Guaranteed Sensing with Full Duplex Radios.....	91
6.3	Sensing-/Location-aided Beamforming and Beam Tracking	93
	Contribution #C-3: Near Field Beam Tracking and Sensing Aided Beamforming using Dynamic Metasurface Antennas.....	93
7	Conclusion	96
8	References.....	99
9	Appendices	109

List of Figures

Figure 2-1: Example of ToA-based localisation (left) and DL-AoD-based localisation (right)..	18
Figure 2-2: Various sensing modalities. In all cases, roles of the BS and UE can be interchanged, such as monostatic sensing by a UE or bistatic sensing between two UEs.	19
Figure 2-3: Preliminary DISAC architecture, as specified in D2.2 [6GDISAC-D22], incl. Sensed Targets (STs), Sensing Transmitters (STxs), Sensing Receivers (SRxs), Local Sensing Processing Functions (LSePFs), a central Sensing Processing Function (SePF) and a Sensing Management Function (SeMF).....	23
Figure 3-1: Paraxial (a) and non-Paraxial (b) settings.....	29
Figure 3-2: Deep Neural Network output trained on empirical measurements. A Deep Neural Network (DNN) can be used to replicate a realistic RIS model.	31
Figure 3-3: RCS of a metallic plate in far-field (a) vs. near-field (b).....	32
Figure 3-4: Representation of the near-field of the target (a) and related expression of the target near-field distance condition (b).....	32
Figure 3-5: Multipath components and clusters measured in an indoor environment (a) and relation with the perimeter of the room (b) [GGD+17].	34
Figure 4-1: Example of Deployment scenario for Semantic Waveforms	38
Figure 4-2: System model and key components of the semantic-aware waveform communication chain.....	39
Figure 4-3: F1 score Comparison: OSSDM vs. OFDM (Semantic and Non-Semantic) waveforms vs. SNR.....	40
Figure 4-4: Power Gain and SSE Gain for both OSSDM and OFDM transmissions.	41
Figure 4-5: Illustration of the localisation scenario, where multiple RISs cooperate to locate the UE with optimised beam.....	42
Figure 4-6: Visualisation of optimised beams for 2 different cases (2 RISs and 3 UEs). The figures indicate the probability map of UEs (left), optimised beams for RIS 1 (middle) and optimised beams for RIS 2 (right).	43
Figure 4-7: Illustration of beam calibration (for both array and RIS-aided localisation).....	44
Figure 4-8: Visualisation of beam patterns using different models.	44
Figure 4-9: Comparison of cumulated density function for the absolute lower bound within a $10 \times 10 m^2$ area using different beam models.	45
Figure 4-10: Monostatic ISAC system featuring a monostatic ISAC transceiver, which integrates an ISAC transmitter and a sensing receiver on the same hardware platform, and a communication receiver on a separate device.....	46
Figure 4-11: ISAC trade-off curves under concurrent transmission for QPSK and 1024-QAM modulations. (a) Low-SNR sensing scenario. (b) High-SNR sensing scenario.	47
Figure 4-12: The considered system model comprising multiple communication users and multiple targets in the vicinity of an ISAC access point.	48
Figure 4-13: Average symbol error rates at both UEs and targets/eavesdroppers versus the SNR threshold, for UEs with different power budgets.	49
Figure 5-1: Visual representation of the considered RIS-aided joint localisation and communication system.....	54

Figure 5-2: CDF of the TDoA estimation error for the path with the lowest TDoA of either the BS-MS or the RIS-MS channel 55

Figure 5-3: Frugal localisation scenario involving one single-antenna BS, 3 RISs and one single-antenna user with NB (single-carrier) communication. 56

Figure 5-4: Position estimation performance vs. transmit power for the scenario with 2 RISs under LoS blockage. 57

Figure 5-5: System model of a downlink D-MIMO system for UE localisation. The APs are phase-synchronised, leading to two options for downlink beamforming (P1 and P2). 58

Figure 5-6: PEB values versus the x-coordinate of the UE position for transmission protocols P1 and P2 with coherent and non-coherent processing..... 59

Figure 5-7: Representative scenario of uplink UE localisation supported by a network of 4 distributed radio stripes. There are 2 dominant scatterers, 4 walls, and a single UE..... 60

Figure 5-8: PEB in the low-bandwidth regime (3MHz, left figure), the mid-bandwidth regime (30MHz, middle figure), and the high-bandwidth regime (300MHz). 60

Figure 5-9: The considered DMA-equipped RX, including its geometry and the adopted coordinate system, used for near-field localisation. 61

Figure 5-10: Mean RMSE of the positions of the $U = 3$ UEs versus the transmit power in dBm. 62

Figure 5-11: Deployment scenario for indoor user localisation with mobile RIS-AGV and fixed beacons, where the dependency of the relative angles on time (under AGV mobility) has been deliberately omitted here for the sake of representation simplicity. 63

Figure 5-12: IoT device localisation exploiting AGV-mounted mobile RIS and with an L-shaped beacon deployment. 64

Figure 5-13: Schematic representation of COLoRIS..... 65

Figure 5-14: COLoRIS performance; a) results for simulation stage and b) for implementation stage. 65

Figure 5-15: Adopted scenario for the simultaneous sensing and communication receiver. ... 67

Figure 5-16: Ghost target elimination with the presence of two target with $Comb = 12$, $F_c = 25$ GHz and $s_{cs} = 120$ kHz..... 68

Figure 5-17: Network model from the perspective of sensing UE u_0 , consisting of 3 BSs interfering on a communication link ($b_0 \rightarrow u_0$), with a mobile blocker (robot) moving around; Example of cooperative scenario to localize a mobile blocker (robot) based on 3 sensing EUs (b). 69

Figure 5-18: Accuracy (in m) and coverage of detected blocker's 2D position estimation with the proposed distributed method in a dense mmWave network, as a function of the number of cooperative sensing nodes N 70

Figure 5-19: Deployment scenario for the RIS-aided detection of moving passive obstacles in a mmWave network context, while relying on reflected signals from non-coherent sources (a); Example of extension to a distributed multi-RIS scenario (b). 72

Figure 5-20: Canonical network deployment considered for the evaluation of the proposed selectively cooperative RIS-based sensing approach (big circles: BSs, small circles: UEs, rectangles: RISs, small red circle and red straight line: blocker and its trajectory). 73

Figure 5-21: Empirical CDF of blocker's estimated position error when cooperating at least 5 (a) or 7 RISs (b) with different SSIM-based pre-processing strategies (i.e., outliers rejection and/or measurements weighting). 74

Figure 5-22: Example of the considered scenario. Targets move over time, and each BS can only observe those within its own FoV. Each BS independently processes its local observations to track the targets, then shares the tracked trajectories with neighbouring BSs (i.e., with overlapping or adjacent FoV). 75

Figure 5-23: Tracking results from the TPMBM filter that integrates the target handover method at BS2. 76

Figure 5-24: Illustration of a distributed radar system with N local stations and P moving targets. There exists a communication system without distortion, enabling the FC to flawlessly gather the complete raw data from each local station..... 77

Figure 5-25: Probability of detection and RMSE results of all targets versus SNR. (a) Probability of detection. (b) RMSE in the location estimate. (c) RMSE in the velocity estimate. (d) RMSE in the velocity direction estimate. 78

Figure 5-26: Drone detection system with one MIMO BS, one RIS, and one UE, all located on the roof of a building..... 79

Figure 5-27: Probability of detection performance with and without using an RIS..... 81

Figure 5-28: Probability of detection performance with different kinds of RIS training beam designs..... 81

Figure 5-29: Example of the electric field intensity over the area of investigation when three solid metallic objects are randomly positioned. The transmitting node is positioned far away to the right side of the area while receivers are assumed to be located onto the edge of the area. . 82

Figure 5-30: Proposed “GAT-Res-UNet” network architecture for RF imaging consisting of a Graph-Attention module for incorporation of system geometry, a ResNet for feature extraction, and a U-Net for the construction of images. 82

Figure 5-31: Visual comparison of the proposed GAT-Res-UNet architecture for RF imaging on a data set of circular and square objects. 83

Figure 5-32: Visual comparison of the proposed GAT-Res-UNet architecture for RF imaging on a data set of handwritten digits seen as solid objects. 84

Figure 5-33: Example of position heatmap predictions within the proposed machine learning pipeline..... 86

Figure 6-1: Deployment scenario considered for the evaluation of sensing-aided HO decisions based on the definition of a risky angular sector (a) or 2D region (b), with one reference DL to protect from a mobile blocker between a sensing BS and its served UE, and another spare BS in range from the UE (for possible HO triggering). 89

Figure 6-2: Evaluation of sensing-based HO decisions making (expressed in terms of probability, along the y-axis) in a dense mmWave network as a function of the blocker size, without (a) or with (b) cooperation, according to sensing algorithms from [SDD23] and [DSD24] respectively. 90

Figure 6-3: The considered FD massive MIMO system for simultaneous data transmission and mono-static sensing. The FD massive MIMO node jointly optimises its hybrid analog and digital Tx BF, analog Rx combining, and digital SI cancellation for the intended ISAC operation. 91

Figure 6-4: Sensing (a) and communication (b) performance for K=3 targets, U=2 of which being UEs, versus the transmit power with the proposed FD-enabled XL-MIMO ISAC scheme for the case where $N_{RF}=4$ TX/RX microstrips, each with $N_E=4$ metamaterials..... 92

Figure 6-5: The considered system model comprising a static BS equipped with a DMA of an extremely large number of metamaterials, lying in the xz-plane and a mobile single-antenna UE moving inside the xy-plane. 94

Figure 6-6: Dynamic non-uniform grid for UE localisation. The proposed non-uniform sampling process for a circular area of interest with central point at the polar coordinates $r = 70$ m and $\Phi = \pi / 4$, resolution $\delta\% = 80$ % and radius $c = 30$ m. It is also observed that Δr increases with increasing r 95

Figure 6-7: Left vertical axis: average percentage of optimum gain achieved and 95th percentile error bar, over time with 500 μ s time step. Right vertical axis: average estimation time interval. Both are plotted versus the different QoS constraints. 95

List of Tables

Table 3-1: Physical tool and channel model requirements for DISAC.	27
Table 3-2: Sensing-oriented channel measurements.....	33
Table 3-3: List of evaluation means and tools exploitable in the context of 6G-DISAC WP3..	34
Table 4-1: Overview of 6G-DISAC contributions on radio physical layer optimisation and waveforms shaping.	36
Table 5-1: Overview of 6G-DISAC contributions on sensing, localisation, and tracking.	50
Table 6-1: Overview of 6G-DISAC contributions on sensing-aided communication.	87
Table 9-1: Mapping table between main D3.1 and D4.1 technical contributions.	109

List of Acronyms

3GPP	3 rd Generation Partnership Project
5G(-A)	5 th Generation (- Advanced)
6G	6 th Generation
(A-)GPS	(Assisted) Global Positioning System
AGV	Autonomous Guided Vehicle
AI	Artificial Intelligence
ALB	Absolute Lower Bound
AMRFC	Advanced Multifunction Radio Frequency Concept
AoA	Angle-of-Arrival
AoD	Angle-of-Departure
Aoi	Area of Investigation
AP	Access Point
BS	Base Station
CFO	Carrier Frequency Offset
CI	Combined Impacts
CIR	Channel Impulse Response
COST	Cooperation in Science and Technology
CR(L)B	Cramér-Rao (Lower) Bound
CRS	Cell-specific Reference Signal
DAC	Digital to Analog Converter
DFT	Discrete Fourier Transform
(D)ISAC	Distributed Integrated Sensing and Communication
DL	Downlink
DMA	Dynamic Metasurface Antenna
DMC	Dense Multipath Component
DMRS	DeModulation Reference Signal
DNN	Deep Neural Network
DSSS	Direct Sequence Spread Spectrum
(E)CDF	(Empirical) Cumulative Distribution Function
ELAA	Extra Large Aperture Array
EM	Electromagnetic
ETSI	European Telecommunications Standards Institute
FC	Fusion Centre
FD	Full Duplex
FDTD	Finite Difference Time Domain

FFN	Feed Forward Neural Network
FoV	Fields of View
FR	Frequency Range
GBSM	Geometry-Based Statistical Modelling
GFDM	Generalised Frequency Division Multiplexing
GIC	Generalised Information Criterion
GLRT	Generalised Likelihood Ratio Test
gNB	gNodeB
GNN	Graph Neural Network
GPU	Graphics Processing Unit
HO	Handover
IFFT	Inverse Fast Fourier Transform
IoT	Internet of Things
ITU-R	International Telecommunication Union – Radiocommunication
IWT	Inverse Walsh Transform
JDL	Joint Detection and Localisation
KED	Knife-Edge Diffraction
KG	Knowledge Graph
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
LLM	Large Language Model
LLR	Log-Likelihood Ratio
LoS	Line-of-Sight
LMMSE	Linear Minimum Mean-Squared-Error
LS	Least Squares
LSePF	Local Sensing Processing Function
(D-)MIMO	(Distributed-)Multiple Inputs Multiple Outputs
MCM	Mutual Coupling Matrix
MISO	Multiple Input Single Output
ML	Maximum Likelihood
mmWave	Millimetre Wave
MOMP	Multidimensional Orthogonal Matching Pursuit
MPC	Multipath Component
NASA	US National Aeronautics and Space Administration
NC	Non-Ideal Codebook
NR	New Radio
OFDM	Orthogonal Frequency Division Multiplexing

OTFS	Orthogonal Time Frequency Space
ORAN	Open Radio Access Network
OSSDM	Orthogonal Semantic Sequency Division Multiplexing
PADP	Power And Delay Profile
PDSCH	Physical Data Shared Channel
PEB	Position Error Bound
PHY	Physical layer
PO	Physical Optics
PoC	Proof of Concept
PPP	Poisson Point Process
PRS	Positioning Reference Signal
QAM	Quadrature Amplitude Modulation
QoS	Quality of Service
QPSK	Quadrature Phase Shift Keying
RAD	Radar-Angle-Doppler
RCS	Radar Cross Section
RE	Resource Element
RF	Radio Frequency
RIS	Reconfigurable Intelligent Surface
RMSE	Root Mean Square Error
RP	Reflected Path
RRIS	Reflecting RIS
RRM	Radio Resource Management
RS	Radio Stripes
RT	Ray Tracing
RTT	Round-Trip-Time
Rx	Receiver
SAW	Semantic-aware Adaptive Waveform
SemCom	Semantic Communications
SeMF	Sensing Management Function
SePF	Sensing Processing Function
SI	Self-Interference
SIC	Successive-Interference-Cancellation
S(I)NR	Signal-to- (Interference plus) Noise Ratio
SISO	Single Input Single Output
SLAM	Simultaneous Localization And Mapping

SN	Sensing Node
S-OFDM	Semantic – Orthogonal Frequency Division Multiplexing
SP	Scattering Point
SRx	Sensing Receiver
SSE	Semantic Spectral Efficiency
SSIM	Structural Similarity Index Measure
SSP	Single-Scattering Property
STx	Sensing Transmitter
SVD	Singular Value Decomposition
TDoA	Time-Difference-of-Arrival
TPMBM	Trajectory Poisson Multi-Bernoulli Mixture
ToA	Time-of-Arrival
TRIS	Transmitting RIS
Tx	Transmitter
UE	User Equipment
UL	Uplink
UTD	Uniform Theory of Diffraction
V2V	Vehicle-to-Vehicle
VNA	Vector Network Analyzer
VR	Visible Region
WP	Work Package
WSSUS	Wide-Sense Stationary Uncorrelated Scattering
WT	Walsh Transform
XL-MIMO	eXtremely Large (XL) – MIMO

1 Introduction

In the context of next-generation wireless networks, the demand for systems capable of delivering not only reliable, efficient, and high-speed communications, but also context awareness and localisation capabilities, is steadily increasing. This evolution is driven by the recent convergence of communication, sensing, and edge computing, which appear as fundamental building blocks and functionalities for future wireless environments and applications, including autonomous vehicles, Industry 5.0, extended reality, and digital twinning [LBB+21], [AVM+23]. To meet these growing expectations, the concept of Integrated Sensing and Communication (ISAC) has emerged for the last past years as a very promising paradigm, offering mutual benefits for the two communication and sensing services, as well as a multiplicity of possibilities in terms of implementation variants (e.g., considering multiplexed services in time/frequency/space or the use of unified waveforms for better efficiency) [LCM+22]. Beyond, even more recently, distributed forms of ISAC (DISAC) have also been promoted to overcome the identified limitations of standard ISAC schemes, while aiming at improved scalability, coverage, and sensing accuracy, reduced latency, better flexibility and responsiveness across complex and dynamic environments, as well as better resilience against local nodes failures [SAG+24], [CAA+25], [SMJ+25].

In the frame of the 6G-DISAC project, the Work Package 3 (WP3) is specifically in charge of exploring “Physical (PHY) layer implications and enablers of ISAC”, addressing PHY optimisation and adaptive waveform shaping (Task T3.1), the sensing, localisation, and tracking of both active and passive objects (Task T3.2), as well as sensing-aided communications (T3.2). In WP3, this first deliverable D3.1, which is entitled “Initial solutions towards waveforms, sensing, communication, and DISAC”, gives a comprehensive overview of the initial algorithmic developments realised at PHY layer level during the first half of the project’s lifetime along these three main parallel lines of research. According to the task-wise work package architecture and objectives, the document is structured as follows.

Section 2 provides a brief reminder of the core principles and motivations underpinning both ISAC and DISAC concepts. This includes an overview of conventional network-based localisation and sensing techniques, but also more marginally, of existing location-aided communication schemes. In addition, the section outlines the anticipated benefits from relying on distributed deployments in the specific context of DISAC. The reference 6G-DISAC architecture introduced in D2.2 [6GDISAC-D22] is also recalled, which shall support the fusion of sensing information from spatially distributed nodes, real-time targets tracking and handover, as well as a semantic control and orchestration of heterogeneous communicating and sensing devices.

Then, Section 3 recalls relevant physical models and channel characteristics for DISAC. More concretely, key propagation aspects are discussed and a literature survey is provided regarding e.g., the impact of mobility and multipath, far-field and nearfield propagation regimes, the use of Extra-Large Aperture Arrays (ELAAs) or Reconfigurable Intelligent Surfaces (RIS), temporary shadowing effects caused by moving obstacles, or the characterisation of the Radar Cross Section (RCS) in complex multistatic scenarios and/or in presence of very large passive targets. All these insights on channel modelling in the broadest sense are essential for both the design and the evaluation of effective strategies at PHY level. Finally, suitable simulation tools exploitable in the context of 6G-DISAC WP3 studies, which implement in part the previous models, are also summarised.

In Section 4, focusing on the transmitter side first, novel PHY optimisation schemes and waveform shaping techniques adapted to DISAC are introduced, enabling improved sensing operations, but also more efficient transmissions of the acquired sensing data, as well as the optimal fusion of spatially distributed information from multiple sensing nodes. Typically, these contributions include frugal semantic-aware communication schemes, low-complexity cooperative lo-

calisation mechanisms with the right level of exchanged sensing data, network deployment optimisation, as well as integrated monostatic sensing-communication solutions that jointly address the design challenges of communication reliability and sensing accuracy.

Subsequently, Section 5 introduces new estimation algorithms that address the problems of detection, localisation, tracking, and/or mapping, in both active and passive forms, within a variety of scenarios and network settings. For instance, these contributions span from the high-resolution localisation of both connected users and Scattering Points (SPs) using distributed receivers or RIS-aided techniques, to approaches enabling the detection of passive mobile obstacles, such as cooperative beam scanning and Radio Frequency (RF) imaging enabled by neural networks. These various contributions cover a wide spectrum of performance tradeoffs, in terms of sensing accuracy (e.g., spatial resolution, location accuracy, probability of missed detection and false alarm...) and system complexity (i.e., computational load, a priori information, deployment constraints, synchronisation requirements, etc.).

In Section 6, several methods are proposed so as to leverage the acquired sensing and localisation data for optimising the communication network itself. These solutions include sensing-aided beamforming and beam tracking, proactive network handover management policies, and full-duplex communication systems that can efficiently adapt in real time to environmental and mobility dynamics.

Finally, Section 7 provides a synthesis of the major WP3 achievements accounted for in this deliverable and outlines a few prospective research directions, while putting the emphasis on both intra-/inter-WP interactions as well as on future experimental validations. Beyond the provided theoretical and simulation-based results, this deliverable is indeed intended to serve also as a basis to down-select and adapt possible candidate algorithms for future Proof-of-Concept (PoC) demonstrations at system level under real-life hardware requirements in the context of WP5.

For all the provided technical contributions (i.e., from Sec. 4 to 6), the Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) considered to assess performance from both sensing and communication standpoints are aligned with those introduced in D2.2 [6GDISAC-D22]. The various explored physical deployments also globally comply with the main scenarios identified in D2.2.

Moreover, this document comes along with D4.1 deliverable [6GDISACD41], which more specifically addresses related protocol, resource allocation, and network orchestration aspects, as a support to the PHY layer techniques introduced herein. An explicit mapping between the main technical features contributed in D3.1 and their corresponding protocol/orchestration enablers in D4.1 is provided in the Appendices, for clarity. Note that, likewise, links between WP3-WP4 contributions are discussed in [6GDISACD41] too. From WP3's perspective, the contributions presented in the next sections thus constitute concrete DISAC algorithms that may borrow functionalities and mechanisms designed under WP4, when deployed to the architecture and use cases presented in WP2.

2 Reminder of DISAC Principles and Architecture

2.1 Main Principles

2.1.1 Foundation of Network-based Localisation and Sensing

In radio systems, localisation (synonym: positioning) refers to the process of determining the 2D or 3D location of a connected device, typically a User Equipment (UE), based on Uplink (UL) or Downlink (DL) measurements taken from one or several Base Station(s) (BS(s)) [PRL+18]. In some cases, localisation may extend to estimating the UE's orientation or velocity. These measurements are performed through the reception of dedicated pilot signals, generally of the following types:

- **Time-of-Arrival (ToA)** of the Line-of-Sight (LoS) path. ToA forms the foundation of common positioning methods such as Time-Difference-of-Arrival (TDoA), utilizing multiple time-synchronised BSs, or Round-Trip-Time (RTT), leveraging several unsynchronised BSs.
- **Angle-of-Arrival (AoA) at the BS** for the LoS path. In the uplink (UL), AoA provides directional information towards the UE.
- **Angle-of-Departure (AoD) from the BS** for the LoS path. In the downlink (DL), AoD provides the direction from which the BS transmits toward the UE.
- **AoA and AoD at/from the UE** side becomes feasible if the latter is equipped with multiple antennas (e.g., AoA in DL and AoD in UL). In this case, UE's orientation estimation becomes possible.
- **Channel State Information (CSI)**, which captures a rich set of multipath characteristics, is usually used for fingerprinting-based positioning. This method is particularly effective in complex indoor or Non-Line-of-Sight (NLoS) environments where geometric methods (e.g., ToA/AoA) may fail.
- **Carrier phase**, whose differential measurements between a transmitter and a receiver enable accurate range estimation. However, this method usually suffers from ambiguity due to phase wrapping and requires careful synchronization and calibration, which can increase system complexity. Alternatively, one can perform differential phase measurements of the received signal over different frequency tones, which also typically relate to the ToA of the transmitted signals (e.g., in case of direct path propagation).
- **Doppler shift**, which measures changes in frequency of the received signal caused by the relative motion between the transmitter and receiver. This shift provides information about the velocity and direction of movement, which, when combined with other data, can help estimate the mobile's trajectory or location. While effective for tracking moving targets or UEs, it is useless in static scenarios and can be affected by multipath.
- **Signal polarisation**, which indicates how the orientation of the electromagnetic wave changes as it propagates through the physical environment. Since different materials and angles affect polarisation differently, these changes can provide insights into the followed signal's path and help infer location or even orientation of a mobile UE or a target. While this method can enhance localisation in complex environments, it also requires specialised antenna systems (i.e., sensitive to various polarisations) and suffers from both multipath and polarisation mismatch.
- **Cell ID**, which consists in associating the position of a connected UE to that of the BS it is connected to (i.e, assuming the UE is located within the coverage area of its serving BS). This method is relatively basic and requires no additional hardware. Its accuracy is usually limited and largely depends on the spatial density of the deployed BSs.

Positioning typically relies on geographically distributed reference nodes, such as BSs, and naturally fits within the DISAC framework. Figure 2-1 illustrates examples of ToA-based localisation in 2D, which constrains the UE's location to the intersection of circles, and DL-AoD-based localisation, which confines the UE within a sector or along a ray from each BS (typically, endowed with one single sectorised antenna or with multiple antennas enabling beamforming, respectively).

The position estimation process occurs within the network core and involves calculating the most probable location, or a probability density function, that aligns with the observed measurements.

The pilot signals used for localisation are designed to be orthogonal across BSs in either time and/or frequency domains. In the time-frequency domain, DL pilots employ comb signals that occupy the full signal bandwidth, while in the spatial domain, these signals are transmitted across multiple directional beams at the BS, enabling angle measurements (AoA in UL or AoD in DL). Several factors influence the quality of ToA, AoA, and AoD measurements [WLW+18]:

Figure 2-1: Example of ToA-based localisation (left) and DL-AoD-based localisation (right).

- **Bandwidth:** The available bandwidth directly influences delay resolution (but also to some extent, accuracy), while improving multipath suppression. For example, two distinct paths can be separated if their delay difference exceeds $1/\text{bandwidth}$. In environments with a strong secondary path (e.g., 10 meters difference in travelled distance compared with the direct path), a bandwidth of approximately 30 MHz is necessary to resolve this secondary path. Large bandwidths are therefore crucial for accurate localisation in multipath-rich environments.
- **Transmission Power:** The accuracy of delay and angle measurements is proportional to the received Signal-to-Noise Ratio (SNR), which in turn depends on transmission power. Higher transmission power enhances localisation accuracy, assuming the resolution of multipath interference. Additionally, longer transmission durations can boost SNR, improving localisation performance.
- **Number of Antennas:** The angular resolution (but also to some extent, accuracy) is proportional to the number of antennas. In a linear array, two paths with angular differences in radians beyond $2/(\text{number of antennas})$ can be resolved. Therefore, larger antenna arrays, spaced at half-wavelength intervals, yield superior angular resolution.
- **Signal Processing and Hardware Constraints:** Advanced signal processing and knowledge of the utilised beams can significantly enhance delay and angle estimation. However, hardware limitations, including synchronisation and calibration errors, introduce practical constraints, often causing a performance gap between theoretical and real-world localisation results.

Sensing extends beyond localisation and includes the detection and estimation of changes or events in the environment. In radio systems, this primarily involves radar-like sensing for detecting and tracking passive objects. Unlike localisation with Positioning Reference Signal (PRS), there are currently no dedicated signals for sensing in the communication systems. Sensing can be categorized as follows (see Figure 2-2):

- **Monostatic Sensing:** The Transmitter (Tx) and Receiver (Rx) are co-located, sharing a common clock and typically operating in full-duplex mode. The Tx emits a known

waveform, which is backscattered from objects in the environment and processed by the Rx to detect target presence. Monostatic sensing allows for the detection of both static and dynamic objects, as well as the estimation of their position, velocity, and potentially shape or size. Since Tx and Rx are co-located, the processing benefits from precise time synchronisation, minimising clock-induced errors and simplifying signal processing.

- Bistatic Sensing:** In bistatic configurations, the Tx and Rx are not co-located and may operate on independent clocks. This setup introduces additional complexities in terms of synchronisation, as the relative clock offset between Tx and Rx needs to be accounted for during signal processing. The Tx transmits a signal, and the Rx processes the signal after it has been reflected or scattered by objects in the environment. Bistatic sensing can offer improved spatial diversity, as the separation between Tx and Rx provides different perspectives on the environment, enabling more robust detection of objects obscured by obstacles or non-line-of-sight conditions. However, achieving accurate bistatic sensing typically requires the compensation of phase and clock discrepancies between the Tx and Rx.
- Multistatic Sensing:** Multistatic sensing is a generalisation of bistatic sensing, involving multiple Tx or multiple Rx. The distributed Tx and Rx create an increased aperture for sensing, enabling the fusion of signals from several vantage points to provide a more detailed and comprehensive picture of the environment. This method significantly enhances spatial resolution and target detection capabilities. However, to realize the full potential of multistatic sensing, phase synchronisation among the Tx and Rx is crucial. Advanced signal processing techniques are required to fuse the data from multiple receivers, combining the scattered signals into a coherent image of the environment. Multistatic sensing is particularly useful in cluttered environments where objects may be partially obscured, as the different angles of observation provide additional information that would not be available in monostatic or bistatic setups.

Figure 2-2: Various sensing modalities. In all cases, roles of the BS and UE can be interchanged, such as monostatic sensing by a UE or bistatic sensing between two UEs.

The principles that apply to radio localisation, such as delay and angle resolution, signal processing techniques, and hardware limitations, are also relevant to sensing. In fact, many of the same metrics, such as ToA and AoA, are used in both localisation and sensing, albeit with different objectives. However, there are several key distinctions in the challenges that sensing faces, especially in terms of signal propagation and power: in localisation the information resides mainly in the high-power LoS propagation paths, while in sensing the information about targets is subject to scattering, which severely reduces the received power.

2.1.2 Foundation of Location-aided Wireless Communications

By leveraging geographical information, location-aided communications enhance the performance, efficiency, and accuracy of wireless systems. This approach addresses challenges such as signal interference, network congestion, and resource management.

Location-aided wireless communications have emerged as a key enabler for next-generation networks like 5G and the upcoming 6G. By incorporating real-time user positioning into the communication process, these systems significantly enhance fundamental tasks such as beam training, alignment, synchronisation, and handover [LBB+21]. Traditional beamforming approaches often rely on exhaustive search methods to establish directional links, which can be time-consuming and inefficient. With accurate location information, networks can dramatically narrow the search space, rapidly aligning beams toward the intended users, reducing initial access delays, and improving overall energy efficiency.

Synchronisation between base stations and user equipment is another challenge that location awareness helps address. Precise timing and frequency adjustments can be made based on predicted user trajectories, minimising errors during communication. Moreover, location-based predictions facilitate seamless handovers, allowing the network to proactively allocate resources and configure new beams even before a user moves out of the current cell's coverage area.

Sensing-aided communications play an increasingly important role alongside traditional methods. By utilising environmental sensing and positioning technologies (e.g., radar, lidar, or radio-based sensing), the network can not only track user locations with high accuracy but also map obstacles and reflectors in the environment. This information enables the system to optimise beamforming, dynamically illuminating specific areas with enhanced signal power while minimising interference to unintended regions [KCK+23]. As a result, networks can achieve highly directional, energy-efficient communication links even in complex urban or indoor environments.

Channel estimation and optimisation also benefit substantially from location and sensing data. Rather than relying purely on reactive measurements, predictive models can estimate the channel characteristics in advance based on the user's position, motion patterns, and environmental context [SGD+18]. This proactive strategy reduces signalling overhead, boosts reliability, and increases throughput, while aligning closely with the core objectives of 5G and beyond, including support for ultra-reliable low-latency communications and machine-type communications.

2.1.3 Foundation of Integrated Sensing and Communication

The 5th Generation advanced (5G-A) and 6th Generation (6G) mobile networks are expected to enable advanced applications such as machine-type communication, smart city infrastructure, autonomous driving, manufacturing and supply chain Internet of Things (IoT), all of which require both high-speed data transmission and precise sensing. Current systems that handle communication and sensing separately struggle to meet these combined demands, while the scarcity of available spectrum further complicates matters as both functions compete for the same frequency bands. To overcome these challenges, ISAC systems have been developed. ISAC merges wireless communication and radar sensing into a unified system, improving spectrum efficiency and minimising conflicts between these functions. It also offers the advantages of smaller hardware size and reduced energy consumption, making ISAC a key technology for 5G-A and 6G networks.

ISAC's origins date back to the 1960s with active phased array radar, but it gained momentum in the 1980s when National Aeronautics and Space Administration (NASA) explored its use for space shuttles. Since the 1990s, countries like the US, Germany, and the UK have advanced ISAC research, with the US launching the Advanced Multifunction Radio Frequency Concept (AMRFC) in 1996 to demonstrate the integration of many sorts of shipboard RF functions. Major breakthroughs in ISAC signals include the introduction of Direct Sequence Spread Spectrum (DSSS) in 2006 to reduce interference and Orthogonal Frequency Division Multiplexing (OFDM) in 2011, which improved radar imaging and target detection. Recent innovations, such as Orthogonal Time Frequency Space (OTFS) in 2017 and Generalised Frequency Division Multiplexing (GFDM) in 2019, have further enhanced spectrum efficiency and mobility detection. By 2030, ISAC is expected to be a crucial enabler of 6G networks.

Despite these advancements, ISAC signal design remains a major challenge. Communication systems require efficient data transmission with high spectrum efficiency and robust interference handling, while radar sensing demands high-resolution detection and wide bandwidth. Achieving a balance between these requirements is difficult, as improvements in one area can negatively impact the other. Signal processing must also be optimised to ensure accurate sensing while minimising computational complexity, especially for real-time applications. Flexible algorithms are needed to adapt to various scenarios and balance communication and sensing demands dynamically.

2.1.4 Expected Benefits and Challenges from Distributed Settings and Solutions

In the context of radio-based sensing, distributed network deployments and operations (involving multiple BSs, multiple mobile UEs, and other assisting devices such as RISs), as well as distributed signal and data processing methods, offer several benefits that all together contribute to improved localisation accuracy (i.e., for both connected users and passives objects/obstacles), reliable environment monitoring and mapping, and seamless targets handover.

- **Spatial diversity:** One first advantage lies in spatial diversity, which allows for wide-area coverage that could not be achieved otherwise (e.g., with standalone monostatic radars), while expanding the field of physical perception of the overall system and combining data from multiple viewpoints through multi-site cooperation and generalised multistatic approaches. Such diversity also ensures more robust data collection, reducing the probability of local missed detection, and/or mitigating the impact of erroneous measurements caused by signal radio obstructions, dense multipath, or cluttered environments, thanks to a plurality of propagation channel conditions (hopefully sufficiently uncorrelated), incident angles, or types of Electromagnetic (EM) interactions, etc. Finally, spatial diversity also contributes to solve out geometric ambiguities that could result from limited physical resources or deployments (e.g., too few sensing nodes, too limited signal bandwidth or number of antenna elements, leading to low resolutions in delay or angular domains, resp.).
- **Information redundancy:** Additionally, using multiple sources of information distributed in space enables both redundancy and better system resilience, hence contributing to improve also the accuracy and reliability of sensing data. This is particularly valuable as sensing device may be endowed with very heterogeneous capabilities (e.g., in terms of hardware, measurements quality, embedded pre-processing...).
- **Distributed processing and cooperative data sharing:** The necessity to collect and coherently process measurements from multiple sensing nodes disseminated over large areas tends to plead in favour of distributed data fusion schemes, or at least hierarchical ones (i.e., including intermediary levels of centralisation/distribution). These schemes benefit from wireless cooperation between sensing peers and/or with respect to local fusion centres, not only for sharing raw measurements or aggregating locally pre-processed sensing data, but also occasionally, for the execution of estimation or data association algorithms themselves (e.g., when performing over-the-air message-passing or consensus-based algorithms).
- **Resource consumption:** Another by-product benefit of spatial distribution lies in the possibility to save resources, as only the “best-placed” nodes (and likely, the lightweight ones) have to participate to the sensing tasks, hence offering advantages over utilising a single but much more powerful node. However, at the overall system level and depending on the considered scenario, these benefits could be limited in practice by the extra traffic and overhead (See the challenges below).

These distributed configurations and settings also come along with specific challenges, including:

- Synchronisation of multiple sensing nodes (e.g., in time and/or frequency/phase), for the acquisition of radio measurements or parameters, depending on the kind of processing required on the receiver side (e.g., coherent, non-coherent, etc.), which can require much higher complexity in terms of protocol and/or hardware capabilities;
- Management of sensing data at large scales, with the necessity to guarantee its space-time consistency (typically, when asynchronous sensing data from spatially distributed sensing sites must be fused), as well as its continuous tracking (typically, necessitating dedicated data association procedures);
- Need for a complex coordination overlay between all sensing nodes (incl. specific signalling and control protocols), as well as sophisticated orchestration mechanisms at network level, not only to optimally configure the sensing devices in a timely manner, but also possibly to trigger the sensing actions themselves (e.g., in case of targets handover);
- Potential suboptimality of some estimation schemes in comparison with more centralised solutions, which could benefit from a more exhaustive knowledge and/or synchronicity of the collected measurements;
- Possibly, extra latency and overhead induced by control signalling, data sharing (e.g., in case of local data fusion at the sensing devices themselves, or at a local fusion centre), and/or the convergence of specific cooperative algorithms (e.g., through message passing).

2.2 Foreseen Architecture and Related Aspects

In this section, the main architectural elements of the DISAC architecture are reviewed, according to its initial definition in D2.2 [6GDISAC-D22]. In particular, in the 6G-DISAC project, four key enablers of the architecture are identified, namely, i) novel data processing and representation methods addressing the challenge of finding an efficient representation of the potentially large-volume data produced by distributed processing to reduce the overall amount of control signalling, ii) sensing and tracking of passive targets, as well as their associated handover support in order to ensure seamless service continuity, iii) support for heterogeneous devices, ranging from low-power low-complexity, to RIS, and high-performance UEs, addressing the challenge of optimised resource allocation for such heterogeneous requirements, and iv) semantic reasoning and control, which jointly addresses all the challenges listed above.

The envisioned DISAC architecture transitions from the current 3rd Generation Partnership Project (3GPP) centralised architecture to distributed sensing, thereby improving resolution and reliability for a large number of sensing applications, ranging from smart cities, environmental monitoring, active and passive user localisation and tracking, etc.

The DISAC architecture proposal is depicted in Figure 2-3. In the following sub-sections, a more detailed description of the key architectural enablers is provided.

2.2.1 Implications of Processing Segmentation and Data Representation

In the envisioned DISAC architecture, the sensing data is retrieved by multiple nodes in the network, each one having different computing power, energy resource, and storage capabilities. Therefore, it is crucial to find intelligent and adaptive data processing and representation methods.

Sensing data processing options range from localised to centralised fusion techniques. Information-level fusion involves preliminary detection and estimation at each node, transmitting

summary information like angles or times of arrival to a Fusion Centre (FC), which then performs global detection and localisation. While computationally lightweight, this approach risks degraded performance due to information loss from the raw data. On the other hand, signal-level fusion processes raw data from multiple nodes at the FC, leveraging full signal information for enhanced detection accuracy but at the cost of increased data volume and communication requirements. A trade-off exists between sensing performance and data exchange needs, which depends on the application.

Figure 2-3: Preliminary DISAC architecture, as specified in D2.2 [6GDISAC-D22], incl. Sensed Targets (STs), Sensing Transmitters (STxs), Sensing Receivers (SRxs), Local Sensing Processing Functions (LSePFs), a central Sensing Processing Function (SePF) and a Sensing Management Function (SeMF).

After data processing comes the choice of data representation models, progressing from low-level quantized data to high-level semantic representations. Examples include quantized raw data, Range-Angle-Doppler (RAD) tensors, point clouds, voxel grids, and deep learning-based representations. Low-level representations, such as quantized raw data, reduce communication overhead but sacrifice detail. Conversely, high-level representations like point clouds and deep learning embeddings offer richer information for tasks like detection and tracking but demand advanced processing capabilities. Realising such architectures involves tackling challenges such as managing data volume, minimising noise, and ensuring computational efficiency. Additionally, architectural adaptability is crucial to negotiate data representation formats among distributed, edge, and central nodes, ensuring seamless integration across heterogeneous devices and varied service requirements. The framework emphasizes a collaborative and flexible approach, particularly for use cases like smart intersections where diverse device capabilities and Quality-of-Service (QoS) objectives must be addressed.

2.2.2 Support to Passive Objects Tracking and Handover

The 6G-DISAC framework aims to provide a robust and seamless solution for tracking passive targets across time and space, addressing key challenges in DISAC systems. As illustrated in Figure 2.3, central to the architecture is the Sensing Management Function (SeMF), which in collaboration with the Sensing Processing Function (SePF) facilitates coordination among sensing nodes by assigning unique target identifiers, maintaining consistent data association, and overseeing handover processes. These features ensure continuous and accurate tracking as targets move between the Fields of View (FoV) of different sensing nodes. Based on the target information, a dynamic global map can be created to predict target trajectories in real time, minimising latency during handovers and enabling sensing nodes to anticipate incoming targets proactively.

The architecture also supports dynamic resource allocation and sensing configuration adaptation, enabling nodes to adjust parameters such as beam alignment, resolution, and resource distribution to sustain high detection accuracy. All these capabilities rely on adaptive waveform shaping, optimised sensing signal, effective sensing, localisation, and tracking of passive objects. By leveraging real-time target and map information, sensing nodes can also adapt their communication strategies to optimise resource utilization and reduce interference, particularly during handovers. Practical applications, such as Autonomous Guided Vehicle (AGV)-human interaction in smart factories and vulnerable road user protection in urban intersections, highlight the framework's benefits, including extended coverage, enhanced scalability, and real-time decision-making capabilities.

2.2.3 Support to Heterogeneous Devices

As mentioned above, the different Sensing Nodes (SNs) involved in the DISAC architecture possess a wide range of heterogeneous capabilities, in terms of energy budget, communication and sensing capabilities, computation and storage, etc. Therefore, it is of paramount importance to design a network architecture capable of supporting such broad range of nodes via robust synchronisation and coordination methods, while preserving tight requirements in terms of communication and sensing QoS. Alongside the architecture design, another major challenge is represented by the associated protocol and distributed resource orchestration algorithms design, which is tackled by WP4 [6GDISACD41].

In particular, the envisioned DISAC architecture provides support for:

- **Multiple Inputs Multiple Outputs (MIMO) and multi-antenna transceivers, incl. Distributed-MIMO (D-MIMO):** Devices such as massive MIMO, and hybrid/analog beamformers provide substantial gains in terms of communication rate and sensing accuracy thanks to increased spatial resolution, allowing for precise 3D beamforming. Therefore, they are regarded as key components of the DISAC ecosystem. However, the envisioned architecture is designed to support both single- and multi-antenna devices. Among the various MIMO system, D-MIMO is particularly relevant for DISAC, as it inherently embodies distributed design, sensing, and processing, via its widely distributed radio units, connected to a central unit for signal design, processing, and clock/phase synchronisation. Moreover, the algorithms devised in WP4 take into account each device capability when efficiently orchestrating network resources.
- **In-band and out-of-band controlled nodes:** Advanced control, coordination, and synchronisation methods are required to support, on the one-hand, both out-of-band controlled devices, including nodes that only require few, sporadic control signals, as well as autonomous nodes, and, on the other hand, in-band controlled devices. In both cases, the envisioned control plane aims at minimising the amount of control signalling without compromising sensing and communication performance. Such a challenge is

tightly coupled with the design of network protocols within WP4, for both types of control channels.

- **Heterogeneous storage, computational hardware, and offloading capabilities:** In distributed settings, such as the ones considered in this project, the involved nodes possess different storage, computation and offloading capabilities. In this regard, the architecture design allows for all such devices to coexist, while the envisioned distributed orchestration algorithms within WP4 efficiently allocate resources depending on the device capability. Special consideration is given to computational hardware capabilities, ranging from low-capacity to powerful processing units (e.g., hardware accelerators) capable of supporting Artificial Intelligence (AI) / machine learning-based computations. In this regard, the control plane takes care of offloading operations from local sensing processing units to a central block for low-capacity nodes, whereas it allows for the post-processed data to flow from high-capacity nodes to the core network.
- **Multi-modal sensors:** The DISAC architecture moves beyond conventional support for RF-based sensors (e.g., radar) to encompass next-generation sensors such as LiDAR-equipped mobile terminals, infrared and thermal sensors, cameras equipped with local processing capabilities, acoustic sensors, etc. although such non-radio sensors are not represented on the preliminary architecture of Figure 2-3, which puts emphasis mostly on elements of the network architecture.
- **RISs:** Special attention is given to the case of RISs, since such ground-breaking devices are well regarded as key technological enablers for ISAC. Indeed, while their use in boosting communication performance is well known, recently such devices have been exploited for unlocking novel sensing applications. In this project several heterogeneous kinds of RISs, such as nearly passive reflecting RISs, simultaneous reflection and sensing RISs, i.e., reflecting devices equipped with sensing capabilities, transmissive RISs, and amplifying, or active, RISs are included. Moreover, static, i.e., non-reconfigurable, reconfigurable with the network control, and autonomous RISs, i.e., devices that decide their own optimised configuration based on local channel state information, are considered, thereby providing significant challenges in the architecture design. To this end, the envisioned 3GPP- and Open Radio Access Network (ORAN)-compliant architecture includes support for the *RIS controller*, which is devoted to the optimisation of the RIS functions, both for communication and sensing. Such network node can be located at the network-side, in the case of reconfigurable RISs, while it may be physically co-located with the surface itself in the case of autonomous RISs, thereby acting as a local processing function unit. Moreover, a *RIS orchestrator* is deployed in the central network, taking care of orchestrating multiple RIS nodes in the network.
- **ELAAs:** MIMO systems with large numbers of antenna elements, often in the order of thousands or more, are often referred to as ELAAs [SMM24]. The array elements may be distributed (as in D-MIMO) or co-located (as in massive MIMO). ELAAs are characterised by wavefront curvature effects (as opposed to plane waves in classical MIMO) and channel non-stationarity (variation of the channel amplitude across the array for each propagation path). These two effects are geometric, allowing them to be harnessed for ISAC, in particular at higher frequency bands.

2.3 Interplay with Semantic Reasoning and Control

Beyond purely architectural aspects, the emerging semantic approaches to both wireless data communication and contextual sensing may also have a significant impact on the way the new DISAC functionalities and algorithms are designed at the PHY layer level, while aiming at exploiting the fine synergies and interplay between radio and semantic domains:

- **Semantic waveforms:** The semantic transceiver includes revisiting waveform optimisation, channel parameter estimation, location estimation and tracking, to adapt to instantaneous application requirements. A Semantic-aware Adaptive Waveform (SAW) for communication is currently being studied (See Sec. 4 hereafter). From the architectural perspective, the control and configuration of SAW need to be addressed. Further issues such as the coexistence with traditional OFDM waveforms, the provisioning of the knowledge base(s), the configuration of the parameters and the models updating, will be investigated in the course of the 6G-DISAC project.
- **Semantic RAN:** The connection between the semantic and the radio domains is envisioned as the exchange of semantic information between different network functionalities, which implies the introduction of new protocols and network functions, including semantic extraction, semantic composition, and semantic instruction. The DISAC network architecture enables support of AI modules at both semantic and radio layers, while specific interfaces will be designed to enable interactions of these new functionalities.
- **Semantic alignment in the ISAC context:** Semantic alignment refers to the process of ensuring that both the transmitter and the receiver share a common understanding of the transmitted information. Incorporating semantic alignment into the ISAC framework represents a significant advancement for 6G, IoT, and autonomous systems [ZGZ+24]. In the context of ISAC, semantic alignment involves aligning the meaning of sensed data and communicated information to enable more efficient use of resources and reduce misunderstandings between these systems. In terms of architecture, the semantic alignment of ISAC requires to introduce several changes to the design and operation of traditional communication and sensing systems:
 - Joint semantic encoder for communication and sensing, to optimise the trade-off between communication and sensing competing for shared resources;
 - Semantic-aware resource allocation module, to dynamically adapt network resources to the current semantic context;
 - Semantic decoder, to interpret the received semantic information and generate outputs aligned with the original goals of both communication and sensing tasks;
 - Shared knowledge base and contextual model between communication and sensing subsystems, to enable meaning alignment and adaptation to an evolving context.

Akin to the deep learning-based representations, semantic-based representations for sensing will be investigated during the project.

3 Relevant Physical Models, Channel Features, and Simulation Tools for DISAC

The wireless propagation channel, which serves as the medium between the Tx and the Rx, sets the performance limits of wireless communication and sensing. Channel characteristics are studied through measurements or specific simulation tools, which are then analysed to create models that support system design and performance assessment.

Current measurement, characterisation, and modelling approaches, however, do not fully capture the ISAC channel, introducing unique features. For instance, the RCS measures a target's ability to scatter back signal power. ISAC channel modelling must account for various sensing targets, extract target information from the environment, and model these elements separately, which are areas often overlooked in traditional channel modelling.

Existing models struggle to capture the newly introduced features accurately, despite thorough developments. For instance, geometry-based statistical modelling (GBSM), such as the International Telecommunication Union - Radiocommunication (ITU-R) *M.2412* model [ITUR17] and the *3GPP TR 38.901* model [3GPP20], are widely used for generating realistic channel responses in various scenarios. The latter can simulate statistically consistent wideband propagation channels, capturing parameters like polarimetric path gain, azimuth and zenith angles for arrival and departure, and path delay. This ensures that the probability density functions of the generated channel parameters closely match those of measured channels for a specific scenario. To apply this model, input parameters from measurements are needed. Deterministic methods, though capable of precisely describing propagation parameters in a calculable, deterministic way, involve complex computations. Other approaches, including hybrid and map-models, also exist.

As an alternative direction, channel models can be derived from EM theory, leveraging approximations of first principals. Such approaches have the benefit of accurate modelling, especially when advanced antenna designs are considered (e.g., metamaterials surfaces or Dynamic Metasurface Antennas (DMAs) – see also Sec. 3.1.5 that follows), or when the underlying application needs to capture peculiarities related to the physical shape and EM properties of the environmental objects – as in RF imaging, for example. The work of [FSA+23], capitalised on the coupled dipole formalism to model all of the wireless environment, including TXs, RXs, RISs, and other resonant material, as a combination of Hertzian dipoles. This treatment presents a high-fidelity model especially in high-reverberation and rich scattering scenes. However, the representation of rigid bodies and advanced antenna elements remains an open point. Addressing different antenna designs, authors in [GDR21], [MPS+23] exploited circuit theory and following the discrete dipole approximation, they model all objects in the environment as thin wire materials, which enable a closed-form channel expression with mutual impedance parameters. Nevertheless, controlling the mutual impedance values to obtain desirable system behaviour (e.g., pre-defined beams) is far from trivial. In addition, authors in [SCM22] and [ATR23] modelled the end-to-end channel including metamaterial elements following the scattering parameter theory. Although it makes no particular assumptions, the latter typically requires a vector analyser to obtain the respective coefficients, hence limiting its overall applicability. Finally, stemming from the Helmholtz equations of EM theory, physics-compliant channel models can be derived by expressing the received signal through the electric field integral equations [BAL11]. Such approaches have been exploited to RF imaging scenarios [WC18], [SGA25], since they can capture the effect of the exact shape and EM properties of appearing objects, however they have not been widely adopted in ISAC literature due to their large computational requirements and need for exhaustive scene description.

In the context of DISAC, the main requirements for channel simulation and modelling are listed in Table 3-1 below.

The remainder of this section provides a more detailed and documented description of available models regarding key channel features, as well as of simulation tools and measurements, which can be useful and relevant in the context of (D)ISAC. Even if these models and tools have not been all in use in the frame of 6G-DISAC studies and evaluations yet, this overview represents an outcome of WP3 on its own, while highlighting also possible gaps to address fully distributed scenarios in next WP3 and/or WP5 studies ahead (typically, by means of new channel characterizations).

Table 3-1: Physical tool and channel model requirements for DISAC.

Requirement/need	Details	Importance
Propagation phenomena	Different types of channels: reflection, diffraction, transmission, diffusion, multiple bounces etc. Backscattering from objects (RCS) Obstruction model: blockage or partial blockage	High/Critical

	Combination of deterministic + statistic aspects (e.g., Dense Multipath Components (DMC))	
Nearfield effect	Large antenna arrays and/or RIS Sensed objects (e.g., extended target instead of point target)	High
Doppler/mobility (Tx/Rx and objects)	Types of mobility: single mobility (Rx or Tx), double mobility (both Tx and Rx), mobility of the target/object to be sensed Spatial consistency of the channel to be considered	High
Distributed aspect	Multiple TXs and RXs to perform localisation and sensing simultaneously Multi-static sensing for multiple passive objects Spatial consistency	Critical
Antenna/RIS inclusion	Phased array, co-located multiple antennas RIS (unit cell level, pattern), Radiation pattern to be considered, e.g., Isotropic, half dipole Antenna / RIS to be added in postprocessing	Medium
Scene/Environment generation	Generation of the environment Import different types of data (e.g., Open Street Map, 3D model, STL format) Dataset availability of material characteristics	Medium
Integration Compatibility	Compatible with other systems, coding languages, and models Computation requirements Frequency limitation of EM modelling? Limited or preferred to some scenarios.	Medium

3.1 Main Channel Features

3.1.1 Large Antenna Array and Near Field

The classical 3GPP model assumes limited array sizes, relatively narrow bandwidths, and link distances that satisfy far-field conditions. Typically, the maximum permissible phase discrepancy across antennas is $\pi/8$, aligning with the Fraunhofer condition $2D^2/\lambda$, where D and λ represent the array size and carrier wavelength, respectively. This model presumes plane wavefronts; however, spherical wavefronts should be considered for accuracy in near-field scenarios [ZOY14]. To address this, second-order approximate models using parabolic wavefronts for massive MIMO channels have been developed to simulate near-field effects in both spatial and temporal domains [LW18]. In [ZWY+23], a general 3D non-stationary GBSM for large array communication systems was introduced, and studies in the near-field region reveal that large arrays exhibit non-stationary characteristics [YZJ23]. For instance, in large arrays, the multipath components (MPCs) vary across sub-arrays, with some common to multiple sub-arrays [MdEO20, MdEO22]. The Cooperation in Science and Technology (COST) 2100 model, a cluster-level GBSM for MIMO, was the first to use the concept of a visible region (VR) to simulate non-stationarity along the antenna array, where clusters are only visible to antenna elements within the corresponding VR [COST2100]. However, its reliance on the plane wave assumption restricts its applicability. The VR concept was later adapted to near-field effects for large-scale arrays [LAH19]. In [HEXAXXIID43], phase variations due to path length differences are calculated by adjusting the Tx and Rx array orientations and then measuring Euclidean distances for each Rx-virtual Tx element pair. This path-specific information is used to determine phase terms that describe the geometry of MIMO arrays, processed individually for each MPC.

In summary, while near-field effects and non-stationarity across large arrays have been addressed in several studies, they are not yet fully incorporated into the 3GPP and standard model. Current methods primarily apply to "one-way" communication channels, and using them for sensing, especially when targets are within the antenna's near-field, remains an open area of research.

Moreover, the use of large antenna arrays operating in the sub-terahertz frequency range often results in limited transmission distances dominated by LoS channels. In such scenarios, the Tx

and Rx pairs are typically positioned within each other's radiating near field. These characteristics render traditional far-field-based designs for MIMO systems less effective in achieving optimal spatial multiplexing gains. To address this limitation, in [RDM+24], an innovative optimisation approach has been introduced for configuring MIMO array layouts, aimed at maximising degrees of freedom in the near-field regime. This method explicitly considers the spherical wavefront behavior of electromagnetic waves in the near field.

Specifically, the study examines both paraxial and non-paraxial configurations, as shown in Figure 3-1. For the paraxial case, a simplified analytical framework is developed, offering clear insights into the influence of critical design parameters, and hence bringing significant improvements over the existing literature. For the non-paraxial case, a novel analytical framework is proposed, establishing a set of sufficient conditions required to achieve the highest possible spatial multiplexing gain.

Figure 3-1: Paraxial (a) and non-Paraxial (b) settings.

3.1.2 Blockages

Blockage effects, particularly in the Millimeter Wave (mmWave) range and especially due to the human body, have been extensively studied in the literature [MH13], [CTT+16], [ATL+20]. Additionally, in [FMV+20], the blockage effects of multiple users have been examined. Notably, these models have been explored in the METIS [METIS15] and mmMAGIC [mmMAGIC16] projects.

Typically, shadowing caused by human blockage between a transmitter and receiver is modelled using the knife-edge diffraction (KED) approach. KED theory offers a relatively straightforward and robust method for calculating diffracted fields at the edges of surfaces. However, when applying single KED to model human blockage, the semi-infinite plane assumes a finite width and infinite height. As a result, the total diffracted field is the sum of the diffracted fields around each side of the plane. To address KED theory limitations, the uniform geometrical theory of diffraction (UTD) provides solutions for diffraction problems and can be applied to canonical objects like edges or cylinders. UTD theory is well-documented and is often used to model human blockage with high accuracy, representing it as a conducting cylinder [SZM+09].

A relatively simple blockage model has now been integrated into the 3GPP channel model. However, simultaneous modelling from different angles, which could be significant for distributed approaches, has not been fully characterised yet. Still, this could be readily modelled by considering the reciprocal positions of the transmitter, receiver, and blocker.

3.1.3 Doppler and Mobility

Most channel models primarily adopt the wide-sense stationary uncorrelated scattering (WSSUS) assumption. GBSM channel models, including 3GPP, incorporate the evolution of clusters over time to emulate the dynamic nature of channels on very short intervals, accounting for time variations typical in real communication scenarios. 3GPP channel model also allows for the inclusion of Doppler effects due to device mobility.

However, in scenarios where both the transmitter and receiver are in motion, as in vehicle-to-vehicle (V2V) channels, non-stationary characteristics across the space, time, and frequency domains are verified. In a dual-mode perspective, this could be seen as a case where the transmitter and receiver remain stationary while the surrounding environment changes due to scatterers movement. In the DISAC context, this corresponds to the movement of objects in the sensing environment, even if the transmitter and receiver remain fixed. This channel feature is poorly addressed in the existent literature.

3.1.4 Spatial Consistency and Distributed Aspects

COST 2100 is a channel model that takes into account the spatial consistency of multiple link channels thanks to the concept of visibility region of clusters.

The QuaDRiGa [JRB+14] implementation of the 3GPP channel model extends it and embodies novel modelling approaches that make the multilink tracking of users accurate and qualitative in changing environments. QuaDRiGa combines each segment of the user's trajectory into a continuous channel. A smooth transition between segments is made through the birth-death procedure of clusters. Similarly, the NYUSIM model proposes using multiple reflection surfaces to update the channel single-scattering properties (SSPs) in the mobile scenarios. A cluster birth-death procedure is used to smoothly connect the consecutive channel segments [NYUSIM].

Nowadays few measurements of multi-link [SLF+23] [ZCC+24], mainly for sub-6GHz cell-free massive MIMO, have been conducted to experimentally characterise the channel distributed aspects.

3.1.5 RIS-enabled Channel Models

The performance and characteristics of a representative RIS prototype can be found in [RMG+24b]. Additionally, the corresponding characterisation data has also been made publicly available as datasets in [RMG+24]. Within the 6G-DISAC project, building on this empirical dataset, a deep learning model was proposed to represent the behaviour of a real RIS, whose output is shown in Figure 3-2. Such data can therefore be exploited to enable an efficient validation of theoretical ISAC RIS-based algorithms outlined in the project, the results of which are foreseen to be included in future deliverables.

In [OBL19], path losses of the transmitter-RIS link and RIS-receiver link have been considered as a sum of the different sub-links. In [Eil21], the scattering by the RIS is computed as the discrete sum of fields scattered from each RIS element.

In [GDR21], a theoretical impedance-based RIS model has been initially proposed, which has been further validated on different practical RIS designs. Also, an extension to a scattering environment has been validated and calibrated through indoor measurements [MMM+24]. Finally, the Tx-RIS-Rx link model has been extended to a multi-RIS model generalised to both Transmitting RISs (TRISs) and Reflecting RISs (RRISs) [MMS+24].

Figure 3-2: Deep Neural Network output trained on empirical measurements. A Deep Neural Network (DNN) can be used to replicate a realistic RIS model.

3.1.6 Radar Cross Section and Object Backscattering

When modelling the sensing channel of a target, it is important to consider the impact of the target's characteristics on the channel, as the target's radar cross-section (RCS) contributes to the echo signal.

Often used in defence applications, RCS originates from radar sensing, where targets are typically in far-field conditions. In such cases, the target features are largely determined by its overall structure, allowing RCS to be approximated as a constant.

However, in ISAC scenarios, the sensing target is often in the near-field. This closer relative distance between the target and the Tx and/or Rx results in an enlarged RCS, which becomes dependent on range and is closely related to the target's geometry and electromagnetic properties. The near-field RCS has been defined in [CR85] [TT97] as:

$$\sigma_{NF} = 4\pi R^2 \frac{|E_s \wedge H_s^*|}{|E_i \wedge H_i^*|}$$

where R is the range, E_s and H_s represent the backscattering electric and magnetic fields, E_i and H_i represent the incident electric and magnetic fields. Hence, the RCS can vary by tens of dBms across different angles, necessitating a multi-angle RCS model for accurate representation. As an example, in Figure 3-3, we show the RCS of a metallic plate in both far-field and near-field regimes.

(a)

Figure 3-3: RCS of a metallic plate in far-field (a) vs. near-field (b).

In most V2V scenarios, the size of the vehicle implies that the radar is in the near-field zone of the target. Also, several applications consider that the human body is often the target being sensed. In the past, human body scattering has been experimentally characterised [SKM+13], [AMZ20] under very specific conditions, without considering the actual distance between the target and the antenna (See Figure 3-4). Given the short wavelength at mmWave, the antenna is in the near zone of the backscattered field. This raises the challenge of accurately modelling the backscattering of a lossy dielectric target, while considering both near-field and far-field conditions based on the intended application.

There are currently different viable methods to address this point. The first involves approximating Maxwell's equations for precise RCS calculation, through full-wave simulations. This approach is computationally intensive. An alternative method, which consists in exploiting physical optics (PO) approximations, considers wave effects but with a lower computational cost [MDD+23].

$$R < d_f^T = 2 \frac{2D_T^2}{\lambda}$$

Figure 3-4: Representation of the near-field of the target (a) and related expression of the target near-field distance condition (b).

3.2 Overview on DISAC-Oriented Channel Measurements and Models

In the literature, only few measurements have been carried out while aiming at ISAC specifically. Most measurements use separate sensing and communication channels to extract target information, with limited focus on the correlation between the two. While communication channels measure received power, path loss, and delay spread, sensing channels concentrate on the target’s reflection path power and body attenuation. Integrated channel measurements aim to capture the correlation between these features. In Table 3-2 below, a list of channel measurement campaigns carried out for sensing applications is provided. Besides [WZZ+22], most of the works do not consider the correlation between the sensing and communication channels.

Table 3-2: Sensing-oriented channel measurements.

Author	Sounder	Environment	Frequency	Antenna Type	Results
[KMH21]	Real-time	Laboratory, parking lot	73 GHz	SIMO, Horn	Received power, path loss, APS
[LZZ23]	Real-time	Indoor hall	28 GHz	Horn and omni	Received power, delay spread, angle spread, Power and Delay Profile (PADP)
[WZZ+22]	Real-time	Outdoor street	28 GHz	Horn	Power, delay spread, environment effect. Sensing and communication
[GGD+17]	Vector Network Analyzer (VNA)	Corridor and office room	57.5-63.5 GHz	Transmit-array	Delay spread, angle spread, intra-cluster AoA/ToA, PADP
[SM11]	VNA	Anechoic chamber	2-8 GHz	Horn and virtual array	PADP, power, delay, path length, angle

Prior to ISAC considerations, for more specific sensing-oriented applications such as radio Simultaneous Localization And Mapping (SLAM), former works in [GGD+17] illustrated the time and spatial correlation of clusters with respect to the room geometry (See e.g., Figure 3-5). This approach, which has been considered for monostatic sensing so far, would need to be extended to the multistatic case to better cover DISAC applications.

Figure 3-5: Multipath components and clusters measured in an indoor environment (a) and relation with the perimeter of the room (b) [GGD+17].

More recently, first attempts on ISAC-oriented channel models have been proposed. In [ZHA+23] a statistical ISAC channel model including sensing characteristics as extension of the 3GPP framework was proposed. In this model however, the RCS is considered as a random value and near-field is not supported. This model has not been validated by measurements. In [LZZ23] a shared cluster-based ISAC GBSM channel model was proposed. This model does not support an RCS representation and has been parametrised in just one set of measurements in indoor at 28 GHz.

Several deterministic tools based on ray-tracing (RT) exist in literature and are available as products. In [ABM+22], a RT tool was proposed, but the support of RCS targets is not included, as well as the inclusion of antennas and RIS. Sionna [HCA+23] is also a widely used tool that allows including deterministic objects with dielectric properties. Among the other deterministic tools, REMCOM uses RT and Finite Difference Time Domain (FDTD). However, like all the RT tools, an accurate calibration is needed. For instance, the importance of calibrating dense components in industrial environments, which are of interest for 6G-DISAC, was shown for the Volcano tool in [GMC+24]. The main counterpart of these deterministic tools is that near-field is not supported, and Doppler can be emulated by sequence of different static simulations with a displacement step lower than half-wavelength.

The correspondence of all these available tools and measurements with respect to DISAC requirements are summarized in Table 3-3 below.

In the framework of 6G-DISAC, specific measurements in WP5 are foreseen to address some of the main features not covered yet in literature.

Table 3-3: List of evaluation means and tools exploitable in the context of 6G-DISAC WP3.

Requirement/ Tool	Ray-Tracing (e.g., SIONNA, REMCOM, Volcano)	Full wave simulation (e.g., FDTD)	Statistical Channels	EM-compliant models	Measurements
RCS / Backscattering evaluation	Not supported.	Yes, but computational heavy. RCS under plane wave available in most cases.	Not supported for objects. Yes for map oriented works for environment	Partially	Yes (6G-DISAC)

<i>Scene/Environment generation (or import)</i>	Yes. (partially in simplified RT tools)	Limited to the computation. Not feasible for practical scenario	Yes if hybrid map-based	No	N/A
<i>Antenna/RIS inclusion</i>	Yes (with limited functionalities)	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes (6G-DISAC)
<i>Near-field effect</i>	No Physical Optics to be applied for nearfield RCS (6G-DISAC)	Yes, but computational heavy	Not supported by any. Proposal in Hexa-XII	Yes	Yes (6G-DISAC)
<i>Doppler/mobility of TX and /RX and objects</i>	Yes if high number of simulations emulating movement	No	Yes (for communication)	No	Yes if measurements done in real-time
<i>Doppler/mobility of objects</i>	Yes if high number of simulations emulating movement. Micro-Doppler	No	Bo	No	Yes if measurements done in real-time
<i>Distributed aspect</i>	Yes, but several simulations needed	Yes, but computational heavy	Not for sensing	Yes	Yes (6G-DISAC)
<i>Space/time consistency</i>	Yes	N/A	Yes for COST 2100, Quadriga, NYUSIM	N/A	Yes
<i>Communication and sensing compatibility and correlation</i>	Yes	N/A	No. Preliminary works only	Yes (yet to be done)	Yes if the setup is foreseen (6G-DISAC)

4 Physical Layer Optimisation and Adaptive Waveform Shaping

DISAC requires optimised operations at both the sensing transmitter(s) and sensing receiver(s), as well as at front- and backhaul to communicate the acquired sensing data to tiers for further remote processing (typically, fellow sensing nodes in case of decentralized processing, or fusion centres hosted in the edge/cloud/core network in case of hierarchical or centralised processing). In this section, the focus is on the transmission side, covering deployments, transmitter selection, wireless transmission of sensing signals, and the (possibly wired) transmission of sensing data. This section is organized into 3 parts, covering the following aspects:

- Transmission schemes at PHY level for the energy-/spectrum-efficient collection of the data acquired by distributed sensing nodes (in the context of sensing data fusion), typically through innovative semantic-oriented approaches (Sec. 4.1);

- Waveform shaping, PHY optimisation and/or specific deployments for distributed sensing and localisation operations (i.e., independently of communication operations), including beam optimisation and calibration (at RISs and BSs resp.) (Sec. 4.2);
- PHY optimisation for simultaneous communication and sensing operations, including Rx design aspects in monostatic settings and secure MIMO schemes with guaranteed QoS (Sec. 4.3);

Table 4-1 provides a synthetic overview of the related technical contributions.

Table 4-1: Overview of 6G-DISAC contributions on radio physical layer optimisation and waveforms shaping.

	Cont. #A-1: Semantic-aware Communication of Sensing Data through Orthogonal Sequences - Division Multiplexing based on the Walsh Transform	Cont. #A-2: Waveform Design for Cooperative RIS-aided Localisation	Cont. #A-3: Onsite Anchor Beam Pattern Calibration	Cont. #A-4: Monostatic Integrated Sensing and Communication: Receiver Design and Trade-off Analysis	Cont. #A-5: Secure MIMO Systems Exploiting Interference with Bayesian Cramer-Rao Bound Optimisation for Eavesdroppers Detection under Guaranteed Communication QoS
Physical Deployment					
Nb, types and mobility regimes of TX nodes	Single antenna, stationary	Single or multi- antenna, stationary	Multi-antenna, stationary	Multi-antenna, stationary	Multi-antenna, stationary
Nb, types and mobility regimes of RX nodes	Single antenna, stationary	Single antenna, stationary, mobile	Single antenna, stationary and mobile	Multi-antenna, stationary	Multi-antenna, stationary
Nb, type and mobility regime of Passive Objects	n/a ¹	Stationary	Stationary	Mobile	Stationary
Nb, types and mobility regimes of RISs	n/a	Multi-antenna, stationary	n/a	n/a	n/a
Environment					
Indoor/outdoor	No specific	Both	Outdoor	Outdoor	Outdoor
LoS/NLoS conditions	LoS	LoS	Both	Both	LoS
Radio Set-up					
Uplink/Downlink/Full-Duplex	Uplink	Downlink	Uplink/Downlink	Downlink	Downlink
Tested frequency (mostly for evaluations when specified)	2.4Ghz	28GHz	28GHz	28 GHz	n/a
Bandwidth	10MHz	Up to 400MHz	Up to 400MHz	Up to 400MHz	n/a
Near-field/Far-field regime	n/a	Far-field	Far-field	Far-field	Far Field
Time synchronisation requirements	None	Yes, treated as unknown (variable to be estimated)	Yes, treated as unknown	None, as it is a monostatic system with a shared clock between TX and RX	None
Phase coherence requirements	None	None	None	None	None
Localisation and/or Sensing Operations (If any)					
Type of radio measurements at distributed sensing points	n/a	Angle, delay	Angle, delay	Angle, delay, Doppler	Angle

¹ An entry with « n/a » means that the proposed solution is agnostic with respect to the value of the parameter.

Entity collecting the radio measurements (for fusion)	n/a	Central unit	Receiver	Co-located receiver	n/a
Data Communications (if any)					
Type and traffic of conveyed information (ex. data format, refresh. rate...)	Semantic symbols generating by a knowledge graph, mapped into Walsh coefficient to be transmitted	RIS profile, UE status	UE status, beamforming vector	n/a	Modulated data
Spectral efficiency requirements	None	None	None	Data rate is evaluated under different modulation orders	None

4.1 Physical Layer Solutions and Waveforms Shaping for the Transmission, Collection, and Fusion of Distributed Sensing Data

Contribution #A-1: Semantic Waveforms for AI-native 6G Networks

Motivations and Challenges

5G development has emphasized symbol-level accuracy over data meaning, leading to advanced physical layer technologies, adaptive antennas, and flexible resource allocation for reconfigurable systems with multiple waveform configurations [YA20]. In ISAC scenarios, 6G leverages AI and semantic communication to manage waveform complexity and enable intelligent, context-aware networks across distributed edge infrastructure [CAA+25]. SemCom, proposed for 6G, leverages AI to transmit only task-relevant information, enabling efficient, robust, and semantically driven communication co-designed with hardware and AI systems [CSD+24].

Designing a SemCom-aware physical layer, integrating meaning-aware communication with technologies like MIMO [W+24], beamforming [MLL+24], RIS [HMC+24], and ISAC, is a key challenge for future 6G networks. However, despite their central role, waveforms remain underutilised in current SemCom frameworks, while they should enable meaning-driven communication, not just carry bits. While combining semantic processing with OFDM shows promise, joint waveform-SemCom design remains unexplored. A new approach focuses on transmitting only the sufficient amount of symbols needed to convey the intended meaning to achieve the goal (an instruction, an update of the state or of the environment, a new observation), while adapting the waveform consequently.

In this section, we propose a novel semantic-aware waveform design Orthogonal Semantic Sequence Division Multiplexing (OSSDM) that leverages Sem-Com to reduce physical layer resource usage (power, spectrum, time). Our approach, OSSDM, uses orthogonal Walsh-based waveforms to enable energy-efficient, multi-objective semantic encoding, trading controlled degradation for optimized resource use and improved semantic spectral efficiency. The achieved results show substantial gains in semantic reconstruction, adding value beyond traditional source and channel coding [HHC+25].

Deployment Scenario

The deployment scenario for this contribution, can be a generalisation of the one in Figure 4-1. We can suppose an entity, endowed with computation and communication capabilities, transmitting sensing information, once the received sensing data has been locally semantically processed and encoded. For example, a SRx entity transmits to a LSePF semantic symbols instead of raw sensed data, or the STx, if enabled with the computation and communication capabilities, can process and compress sensing data locally, before sending to the receiver. Leveraging semantic waveforms, as the one proposed in this section, can improve sensing by conveying the most relevant and goal-achieving information. Sensing data are processed to obtain context and meaning-aware adapted waveforms, improving ISAC techniques. In this contribution, the

sensing process is not covered but planned for next deliverables. In relation with the distributed intelligent ISAC envisioned by this project, the deployment of semantic-aware waveforms to transmit sensed data can be imagined implemented at different network levels. A distributed multi-modal sensor network can communicate with multiple fusion centres to compress, transmit and decode data to achieve the specific goal (localisation, mapping, positioning, cooperative solutions, etc.), while saving network resources and delivering reliable contents.

Figure 4-1: Example of Deployment scenario for Semantic Waveforms

Proposed Approach and Followed Methodology

The proposed methodology is illustrated in Figure 4-2, build upon the approach introduced in [HDC24]. It leverages SemCom through knowledge graphs (KGs) to enhance the efficiency of knowledge representation compression. We extend the semantic communication model by incorporating waveform generation based on OSSDM, which leverages orthogonal basis representations for direct RF signal conversion. OSSDM exploits the properties of the Walsh matrix, a binary-valued orthogonal matrix with entries in $\{-1, +1\}$.

In our approach, we utilise the Walsh Transform (WT) as a core operation to convert signals between the time domain and the Walsh domain, through the Walsh matrix. In the following, a detailed description of each component of the proposed system model is provided:

- *Semantic Encoder*: maps an input KG into a latent space representation. It consists of a cascaded architecture composed of a Large Language Model (LLM) encoder followed by a Graph Neural Network (GNN). The LLM associates feature vectors with the textual attributes of each concept node and relational edge in the KG. These features are then processed by the GNN, to produce compact node-level embeddings that capture both concept and relational context. Then, a Feed Forward Neural Network (FFN) maps each node embedding from the latent space to a sequence of semantic complex symbols. These complex symbols are the semantic units representing the encoded information, outcoming from the KG combined with the FNN processing on the original data.
- *Semantic Symbol to Walsh Coefficients Mapper*: predicts the corresponding Walsh coefficients to a given semantic symbol. The mapping process is performed by a parameterized FFN which associates a vector of Walsh coefficients with each semantic symbol. This FFN adapts this mapping to generate physical signal representations that are inherently more resilient to noisy transmission environments.

Figure 4-2: System model and key components of the semantic-aware waveform communication chain.

- *Waveform Generator:* After the Walsh coefficient mapping, an Inverse Walsh Transform (IWT) layer reconstructs the discrete-time signal by summing the associations of Walsh coefficients and their respective Walsh functions. To simulate channel effects, Gaussian noise is added to the reconstructed signal.
- *Waveform to Walsh Coefficients:* At the receiver, the WT layer converts the received noisy discrete-time signal into its Walsh domain representation to get its Walsh coefficients.
- *Walsh Coefficients to Semantic Symbol Mapper:* reconstructs the original complex symbol from the noisy Walsh coefficients of the received time signal. The reconstruction process is performed by an FFN, which takes the noisy Walsh coefficients as input and outputs the estimated semantic symbol.
- *Semantic Decoder:* An FFN reconstructs latent vectors from the semantic symbols, which are then decoded with a branched architecture comprising a Node Decoder, and a Relation Decoder, working in parallel to reconstruct the transmitted knowledge graph at the receiver.

The end-to-end system is trained using a composite loss function that jointly optimises concept and relation classification accuracy, while preserving semantic information, and, in addition, a penalty term that enforces conformity to the spectral emission mask.

Results and Discussion

Impact of Waveform Design on Semantic Preservation in Noisy Environments: To evaluate the preservation of semantic information under low-SNR conditions, the performance of the proposed OSSDM waveform is compared against two OFDM-based transmission schemes. For the Semantic OFDM (S-OFDM) baseline, the semantic encoding is performed as previously described (KG generation followed by the FNN processing) to generate the semantic complex

symbols. Then, the proposed OSSDM modulation and mapping are replaced with a conventional OFDM-based scheme. Semantic symbols are modulated and demodulated using OFDM parameters specified in the 5G New Radio (NR) standard for Frequency Range 1 (FR1). Additionally, the traditional (non-Semantic) OFDM baseline is evaluated, in which the KG outcome is compressed using Huffman encoding, followed by 16-quadrature amplitude modulation (QAM) and OFDM transmission. In our experiments, the F1 score provides a comprehensive measure of how well the information and structure of the source KG are preserved in the inferred KG, serving as a key indicator of the semantic fidelity of the proposed system. For simulation results, different orders n of the Walsh function are considered, meaning that the effective number of coefficients used to transmit information will be 2^n . In Figure 4-3, one can see how the OSSDM with $N = 64$ (order $n = 6$), achieves the maximum F1 score with an SNR that is 6dB lower than that required by the S-OFDM baseline. A similar performance gain is observed for OSSDM with $N = 32$. For OSSDM with $N = 16$ and $N = 8$, the SNR gains with respect to S-OFDM are 4 dBs and 2 dBs, respectively, while OSSDM with $N = 4$ reaches its maximum F1 score at the same SNR as the S-OFDM scheme.

These improvements are attributed to the learnable nature of the OSSDM waveform generation process. While both OSSDM and S-OFDM enable the transmission of semantic symbols, OFDM relies on a fixed modulation and does not adapt the waveform to the underlying semantic content. In contrast, OSSDM integrates a trainable mapping from semantic symbols to Walsh domain representations, allowing the model to optimise waveform characteristics to improve robustness under noisy channel conditions. Furthermore, OSSDM with $N = 64$ requires up to 16 dB less SNR than traditional (i.e., non-semantic) OFDM, demonstrating the benefits of semantic-aware waveform design.

Energy and Semantic Spectral Efficiency Analysis: To quantify the transmission efficiency of the proposed OSSDM system compared to classical OFDM, the power and Semantic Spectral Efficiency (SSE) gains across different Walsh orders are also analysed. SSE is a measure of

Figure 4-3: F1 score Comparison: OSSDM vs. OFDM (Semantic and Non-Semantic) waveforms vs. SNR.

the rate at which semantic symbols are transmitted over a given bandwidth and is defined as the ratio of semantic throughput to radio frequency bandwidth. The SSE has been introduced in [YQZ+22] to measure meaningful semantic unit (symbols)/sec/Hz, favouring robust, meaning-preserving communication over bit-level precision. Figure 4-4 illustrates the comparative results

for Walsh orders from 1 to 6, where the primary y-axis shows the power gain (defined as P_{Walsh}/P_{OFDM}) and the secondary y-axis shows the SSE gain, computed as the ratio SSE_{Walsh}/SSE_{OFDM} . The reference OFDM power P_{OFDM} includes contributions from a state-of-the-art low-power Digital to Analog Converter (DAC) and Inverse Fast Fourier Transform (IFFT) engine evaluated using a complexity-energy model known in literature. Across all Walsh orders, the OSSDM architecture achieves a power gain below 1, confirming its lower transmission energy cost per semantic symbol. Simultaneously, the semantic spectral efficiency gain is significantly higher for lower Walsh orders. This gain monotonically decreases with increasing Walsh order, due to the longer block durations required to preserve orthogonality in higher-order WTs.

These results validate that OSSDM provides a robust trade-off between energy consumption and spectral efficiency, offering programmable control via Walsh order selection. The ability to tune this trade-off at inference time offers a key advantage over fixed-grid OFDM schemes. A central advantage of the Walsh domain lies its representation diversity through all Walsh coefficients combination possibilities. For a given order $N = 64$, one obtains 64 orthogonal basis vectors, allowing for fine-grained control over waveform construction and message diversity within a fixed spectral emission mask constraint. This flexibility supports semantic symbol mapping with high diversity and deterministic orthogonality.

Related Dissemination

The results of this contribution are under preparation for a paper submission.

Figure 4-4: Power Gain and SSE Gain for both OSSDM and OFDM transmissions.

4.2 Physical Layer Solutions and Waveforms Shaping for Distributed Sensing and Localisation Operations

4.2.1 Contribution #A-2: Waveform Design for Cooperative RIS-aided Localisation

Motivations and Challenges

RISs represent a transformative technology that can significantly extend communication coverage and address challenges such as LoS blockage. In addition to their communication benefits,

RIS can also serve as extra anchors for sensing, offering valuable information to enhance localisation and tracking [CKA+24]. In distributed systems, where multiple RIS and UEs coexist, effective coordination and resource allocation among the RIS is critical [CZK+24]. Unlike BSs, where time and frequency resources can be allocated for optimisation, RIS relies primarily on beam design to improve system performance. This unique aspect of RIS requires a different approach to the optimisation of surface profile, particularly in dynamic environments with multiple UEs and RISs.

Existing model-based beam optimisation methods often rely on directional or derivative beam strategies [KJM22]. While effective in specific scenarios, these methods face limitations when addressing UE state uncertainty, particularly when sample-based approaches fail to capture the full uncertainty distribution due to a limited number of transmissions. Additionally, solving optimisation problems in real time is computationally demanding, making such methods impractical for large-scale, dynamic systems.

Deployment Scenario

The system under consideration focuses on a single-antenna BS to emphasize the design challenges and opportunities at the RIS. One or more UEs are assumed to be located within the sensing area, equipped with prior information from previous measurements or additional sensors. Localisation is performed based on received DL signals and the predefined RIS profiles, leveraging both LoS and RIS-reflected paths. By optimising the RIS configuration, the UEs can accurately locate themselves even in complex scenarios with limited LoS availability. An illustration of the considered deployment scenario can be found in Figure 4-5.

Figure 4-5: Illustration of the localisation scenario, where multiple RISs cooperate to locate the UE with optimised beam.

Proposed Approach and Followed Methodology

To overcome these challenges, a machine learning-based approach is proposed to optimise RIS profiles. By extending the concept of active sensing [ZJY23], this work moves beyond latent space representations to use mixed Gaussian distributions to model the UE state uncertainty. The network is trained to output both the optimal RIS profile and an updated state representation for each UE. This methodology is expected to bring a robust solution for RIS optimisation in scenarios with dynamic UE states and limited LoS availability.

Results and Discussion

Initial results for the learning-based beam design can be found in Figure 4-6. This work starts from the optimisation of 2 RISs and 3 UEs. The Gaussian mixture model contour map of the targets, which serves as the input of the network, is shown in the left figures. In the middle and right figure, several beams (4 out of 20) and the average gain of all the beams (scaled by 2.5

for better visualisation) are visualised. It can be observed that more energy is allocated to the area where UEs have a high probability of appearing.

Related Dissemination

The results of this contribution are under preparation for a paper submission.

4.2.2 Contribution #A-3: Onsite Anchor Beam Pattern Calibration

Motivations and Challenges

High-accuracy localisation is recognised as essential for ISAC systems [TSM+21]. Arrays and RISs are adopted to enhance localisation performance, benefiting from their high angular resolution and cost-effectiveness [BWM+22]. However, practical RIS beam patterns are often observed to significantly deviate from the idealised theoretical models, mainly due to mutual coupling effects, RF hardware imperfections, measurement uncertainties, and fabrication errors [CKA+23]. Such mismatches inevitably degrade localisation accuracy, underscoring the necessity of beam calibration for accurate modelling and robust localisation performance in real-world deployments [GZC+24].

Deployment Scenario

A single-input-single-output (SISO) RIS-aided localisation system is considered. The BS is located at the coordinate origin, transmitting signals received directly (LoS path) and reflected by an RIS positioned within the area of interest. The RIS employs predefined beamforming patterns

Figure 4-6: Visualisation of optimised beams for 2 different cases (2 RISs and 3 UEs). The figures indicate the probability map of UEs (left), optimised beams for RIS 1 (middle) and optimised beams for RIS 2 (right).

to sequentially scan multiple directions toward UE (See Figure 4-7). An OFDM framework is utilised, with multiple codewords across numerous subcarriers. The experimental validation of RIS beam patterns was conducted in an anechoic chamber using a prototype consisting of 256 RIS elements, demonstrating realistic beam imperfections caused by practical deployment conditions.

Figure 4-7: Illustration of beam calibration (for both array and RIS-aided localisation).

Proposed Approach and Followed Methodology

Three distinct RIS beam models addressing practical imperfections are proposed: (i) Mutual Coupling Matrix (MCM) model, explicitly considering mutual coupling effects among RIS elements; (ii) Non-Ideal Codebook (NC) model, accounting for imperfections in phase-shifting hardware; and (iii) Combined Impacts (CI) model, integrating element patterns, RF impairments, and measurement uncertainties. Corresponding calibration algorithms were developed to estimate unknown parameters based on experimentally measured RIS beam patterns. Least-square optimisation techniques were employed for parameter estimation. The effectiveness of these beam models was evaluated using theoretical mismatch analyses and validated against experimental measurements to reconstruct realistic RIS beam patterns accurately.

Results and Discussion

Simulation results demonstrated that the combined impacts model significantly outperformed the MCM and NC models by accurately reconstructing experimentally measured RIS beam patterns. The comparison of the measured beam pattern and the calibrated pattern can be found in Figure 4-8.

Figure 4-8: Visualisation of beam patterns using different models.

To quantify the impact of beam calibration error on localisation, the Absolute Lower Bound (ALB) through mismatch analysis is adopted (See Figure 4-9). Using the calibrated beam from the CI model, positioning errors were observed to be below approximately 10 cm for more than 90% of tested scenarios, showing substantial improvements compared to other models. This result emphasizes the importance of comprehensive beam modelling and calibration, which effectively incorporates realistic hardware imperfections and measurement uncertainties, for achieving robust, high-accuracy RIS-aided localisation.

Related Dissemination

M. Li, et al. “Beam Calibration for ISAC System: Modelling and Performance Analysis”, submitted to IEEE GLOBECOM 2025.

Figure 4-9: Comparison of cumulated density function for the absolute lower bound within a $10 \times 10 \text{ m}^2$ area using different beam models.

4.3 Physical Layer Solutions and Waveforms Shaping for Simultaneous Communication and Sensing Operations

4.3.1 Contribution #A-4: Monostatic Integrated Sensing and Communication: Receiver Design and Trade-off Analysis

Motivations and Challenges

Several critical trade-offs arise in monostatic OFDM-based ISAC systems due to the dual demands of efficient communication and accurate sensing. As a prevalent modulation scheme in wireless systems, OFDM naturally lends itself to ISAC due to its large design flexibility and low-complexity radar operation [LML+18]. However, integrating sensing and communication functions within the context of OFDM introduces significant challenges. For instance, the time-frequency trade-off arises because high-order modulation schemes like QAM enhance communication rates but degrade sensing performance due to increased side-lobe levels [DLX+24]. On the other hand, using constant-modulus Quadrature Phase Shift Keying (QPSK) reduces side-lobe levels, improving sensing performance but sacrificing communication rates [LLL+24]. Another trade-off arising in monostatic OFDM ISAC systems is the spatial trade-off, which results from the choice of ISAC beamformers. Optimising this trade-off involves balancing resource

allocation between sensing and communication beams, i.e., how much to illuminate communication users and sensing targets. These challenges necessitate novel approaches to manage the inherent conflicts in ISAC system design [LHL+22]. These trade-offs become even more challenging in distributed ISAC scenarios, where coordinated transmission across multiple nodes introduces additional constraints, such as synchronisation and joint beam design. Insights from monostatic OFDM trade-offs can guide distributed implementations, especially when aiming to reuse existing communication waveforms for joint sensing without centralised control.

Previous approaches to OFDM sensing receiver design suffer from limitations. First, they have primarily used QPSK signalling, which limits communication performance, or employed QAM data with reciprocal filtering, which increases side-lobe levels at low SNRs due to amplified noise power. Alternatively, using matched filtering with QAM signalling instead of reciprocal filtering leads to higher side-lobe levels at high SNRs, resulting from varying amplitude data.

Deployment Scenario

The deployment scenario comprises a monostatic OFDM ISAC transceiver equipped with multiple antennas, serving both as a transmitter and a sensing receiver, and a separate single-antenna communications receiver, as shown in Figure 4-10.

Figure 4-10: Monostatic ISAC system featuring a monostatic ISAC transceiver, which integrates an ISAC transmitter and a sensing receiver on the same hardware platform, and a communication receiver on a separate device.

The ISAC transceiver transmits OFDM signals containing both communication data and pilot symbols to the communications receiver, while simultaneously performing radar sensing by processing the backscattered signals from targets. This monostatic configuration allows the sensing receiver to access the entire transmitted OFDM signal, facilitating effective sensing operations. To ensure that the sensing receiver operates without self-interference during full-duplex operation, it is assumed that the transmit and receive antennas at the ISAC transceiver are sufficiently isolated.

Proposed Approach and Followed Methodology

A novel MIMO-OFDM radar sensing algorithm based on a Linear Minimum Mean-Squared-Error (LMMSE) estimator is proposed, which has been specifically designed to handle varying-amplitude random communication data. This approach effectively suppresses high side-lobes induced by high-order QAM signalling, thereby enhancing detection capabilities, particularly for weak targets. In addition, two ISAC transmission strategies have been investigated: *concurrent transmissions*, which employ joint beams for simultaneous sensing and communication, and *time-sharing transmissions*, which utilise separate, non-overlapping beams. To evaluate these strategies, a mutual information approximation method using Monte Carlo sampling techniques has been developed, enabling the assessment of data rates and resulting ISAC trade-offs under various modulation schemes. Simulations and real-world experiments have been conducted to provide guidelines for 6G system design, demonstrating that the proposed LMMSE estimator offers substantial improvements over existing methods across a wide range of conditions.

Results and Discussion

In Figure 4-11, ISAC trade-off curves under concurrent transmissions are presented for QPSK and 1024-QAM modulations, as the relative weight varies between sensing and communication.

In the low-SNR scenario, significant improvements in the ISAC trade-off were demonstrated by employing 1024-QAM modulation with LMMSE estimation compared to reciprocal filtering, highlighting its robustness in preserving detection probability despite using higher-order modulations. Conversely, in the high-SNR scenario, matched filtering was shown to fail, and reciprocal filtering exhibited inferior performance compared to LMMSE. Overall, it was illustrated that the LMMSE estimator consistently outperformed traditional estimators (RF and MF) across various SNR conditions and modulation types, ensuring superior balance between sensing accuracy and communication data rate in OFDM-based ISAC systems.

Figure 4-11: ISAC trade-off curves under concurrent transmission for QPSK and 1024-QAM modulations. (a) Low-SNR sensing scenario. (b) High-SNR sensing scenario.

Related Dissemination

M. F. Keskin, et al. "Fundamental Trade-offs in Monostatic ISAC: A Holistic Investigation towards 6G," accepted for publication into IEEE Transactions on Wireless Communications.

4.3.2 Contribution #A-5: Secure MIMO Systems Exploiting Interference with Bayesian Cramer-Rao Bound Optimisation for Eavesdroppers Detection under Guaranteed Communication QoS

Motivation and Challenges

The paradigm of ISAC has garnered significant research attention, particularly in the context of future high-frequency, high-bandwidth operations. As these systems operate over common frequency bands and leverage similar hardware architectures, they present unique opportunities for a co-design that can enhance the performance of both sensing and communication tasks. However, this integration introduces significant security vulnerabilities due to the broadcasting nature of wireless transmission, which can make confidential information susceptible to interception by unintended eavesdroppers. Specifically, adversaries can exploit the integrated nature of ISAC signals to infer sensitive location information or manipulate environmental perception, while simultaneously compromising communication confidentiality. Additionally, the shared hardware architecture enables cross-domain attacks where vulnerabilities in sensing operations can compromise communication security, and vice versa. Thus, there is a need for developing a signalling design that not only improves sensing performance but also ensures the physical layer security of communication data against potential eavesdroppers.

Deployment Scenario

The system model presented in Figure 4-12, involves a downlink multi-user multiple inputs single output (MISO) wireless system, where a dual-functional multi-input multi-output BS simultaneously communicates with multiple single-antenna UEs, while also detecting multiple targets considered as potential eavesdroppers. The BS is equipped with transmit and receive antennas, enabling both data transmission and target detection. In this context, the targets' responses are modelled using a target response matrix that accounts for factors such as the RCS and path loss.

The deployment scenario envisions a shared frequency band for both communication and sensing, necessitating the optimisation of communication QoS, while ensuring physical-layer security against eavesdropping by strategically controlling the signal constellation received by the users and targets.

Figure 4-12: The considered system model comprising multiple communication users and multiple targets in the vicinity of an ISAC access point.

Proposed Approach and Followed Methodology

A novel signalling design is developed for secure ISAC systems utilizing a dual-functional BS. The approach minimises the Bayesian Cramér-Rao Bound (CRB) through a successive convex approximation method to effectively handle the non-convex nature of the addressed problem.

The proposed design leverages constructive interference to direct signals towards intended users while simultaneously reducing their decodability for potential eavesdroppers by ensuring the eavesdroppers' signals remain within a destructive region of the signal constellation.

Results and Discussion

The results of the proposed framework demonstrate the effectiveness of the considered techniques in enhancing physical-layer security. Through extensive numerical simulations, it was indeed shown that the algorithm outperforms conventional block-level precoding techniques, achieving lower symbol error rates at UEs, while ensuring that signals received by potential eavesdroppers fall into a destructive constellation region, thereby protecting the communication data. Additionally, the beam patterns indicate improved sensing performance with narrower main beams and higher gains when prior statistical information about the targets is accurately known. Most notably, Figure 4-13 depicts the average symbol error rate at UEs and the average symbol error rate at targets/eavesdroppers versus the SNR threshold for UEs with different power budgets. The results show that by imposing destructive interference constraints, the symbol error rate at the targets/eavesdroppers is close to one, indicating effective protection of communication data from being decoded these targets.

Figure 4-13: Average symbol error rates at both UEs and targets/eavesdroppers versus the SNR threshold, for UEs with different power budgets.

Related Dissemination

N. Su, et al. "Secure ISAC MIMO systems: exploiting interference with Bayesian Cramér–Rao bound optimisation." submitted to EURASIP Journal on Wireless Communications and Networking

5 Sensing, Localisation, and Tracking of Active and Passive Objects

Complementing the transmitter-side optimisation from Section 4, DISAC also relies on optimised operations at the receivers to enable sensing, localisation and tracking, with trade-offs between complexity and performance. Receiver-side processing generally involves channel parameters estimation, as well as the detection and tracking of targets, and positioning and tracking of connected users (either based on estimated channel parameters or directly out of received signals). These operations also differ depending on the level of synchronisation among distributed nodes (e.g., phase synchronised, or time synchronised), the channel or propagation characteristics (e.g., near-field or far-field, line of sight or non-line of sight), and the involved devices (e.g., massive MIMO, distributed MIMO, RIS). This makes for a rich set of research questions to be addressed, as follows:

- Algorithms for localising connected UEs, which address channel estimation, synchronisation, and positioning problems, while leveraging spatially distributed RISs (incl. both static or mobile surfaces, DMAs in near-field, etc.), D-MIMO BSs in DL, or synthetic ELAAs in UL (Sec. 5.1).
- Algorithms for detecting, localising and tracking passive objects, including multi-static positioning based on standard 5G reference signals, shadowing-based cooperative positioning from dense ambient RF sources' power monitoring at multiple sensing nodes, multi-cell positioning and tracking through information exchange between monostatic sensing nodes, RIS-aided passive radar through beam sweeping, physics-driven RF imaging or detection through deterministic multipath Ray-Tracing simulations based on DNN (Sec. 5.2).

In this section, the waveforms are assumed to have been optimised (in accordance with some of the solutions from Section 4) and generally, the distributed receivers are aware of these optimised waveforms.

Table 5-1 summarizes the main parameters of the proposed technical proposals.

Table 5-1: Overview of 6G-DISAC contributions on sensing, localisation, and tracking.

	Cont. #B-1: Joint RIS Channel Estimation and Localisation via Dictionary Learning and Compressed Sensing	Cont. #B-2: Frugal Localisation and Synchronisation with Multiple Reconfigurable Intelligent Surfaces	Cont. #B-3: Phase-coherent Downlink Localisation and Synchronisation with Distributed Access Points	Cont. #B-4: Joint Localisation, Synchronisation and Mapping via Phase-Coherent Distributed Arrays	Cont. #B-5: Near-Field Localisation with Dynamic Metasurface Antennas at THz
Physical Deployment					
Nb, types and mobility regimes of TX nodes	Multi-antenna, stationary	Single-antenna, stationary	Multi antenna immobile TX node	Single-antenna, stationary	Single-antenna, stationary
Nb, types and mobility regimes of RX nodes	Multi-antenna, stationary	Single-antenna, stationary	Single antenna immobile RX node	Multiple-antenna, stationary	Multiple-antenna, stationary
Nb, type and mobility regime of Passive Objects	n/a	n/a	n/a	Stationary (reflecting walls and scattering objects)	n/a
Nb, types and mobility regimes of RISs	Passive RIS, stationary	Passive RIS, stationary	n/a	n/a	n/a
Environment					
Indoor/outdoor	Outdoor	Outdoor	Outdoor	Indoor	Outdoor
LoS/NLoS conditions	Both	Both	LoS	Both	LoS
Radio Set-up					
Uplink/Downlink/Full-Duplex	Downlink	Downlink	Downlink	Uplink	Uplink
Tested frequency (mostly for evaluations when specified)	60 GHz	30 GHz	3.5GHz	3.5 GHz	120 GHz
Bandwidth	1 GHz	100 kHz	100 kHz	10 MHz	150 KHz
Near-field/Far-field regime	Far-field	Far-field	Near-field	Near-field	Near-Field
Time synchronisation requirements	None	None	APs are time synchronised, UE is not synchronised with the network	Time sync. among APs	None
Phase coherence requirements	None	None	Phase coherent	Phase sync. among APs	None
Localisation and/or Sensing Operations (If any)					
Type of radio measurements at distributed sensing points	Channel Impulse Response (CIR), position	CFO, angle	Carrier phase, angle	Angle, delay, carrier phase	Elevation, azimuth angles, distance

Entity collecting the radio measurements (for fusion)	UE	UE	UE	Central unit	n/a
Data Communications (if any)					
Type and traffic of conveyed information (ex. data format, refresh. rate...)	n/a	n/a	n/a	APs send IQ data to the central unit	Modulated data
QoS requirements	None	None	None	None	None
Transmission range/coverage requirement	None	None	10-100m	None	None
Throughput requirements	None	None	None	None	None
Spectral efficiency requirements	None	None	None	None	None

Cnt'd	Cont. #B-6: Mobile User Localisation and Tracking Exploiting Mobile RISs and Fixed Beacons	Cont. #B-7: Opportunistic User Localisation based on Available RIS Configurations and Environment Knowledge	Cont. #B-8: Sensing based on 5G Standard Signals within Distributed Architectures	Cont. #B-9: Cooperative Sensing of Side Lobes Interference for Blockages Detection and Localisation in Dense mmWave Networks	Cont. #B-10: Detection and Cooperative Localisation of Moving Passive Objects through RIS Scanning of Non-coherent Sources Power
Physical Deployment					
Nb, types and mobility regimes of TX nodes	Single antenna, stationary	Multiple-antenna, stationary	Multiple-antenna, stationary	1 BS (if DL to be protected from obstructions) or 1 UE (if UL to be protected from obstructions) Multiple non-coherent sources in Tx (BSs and UEs, besides the link to be protected)	1 BS (if DL to be protected from obstructions) or 1 UE (if UL to be protected from obstructions) Multiple non-coherent sources in Tx (BSs and UEs, besides the link to be protected)
Nb, types and mobility regimes of RX nodes	Single antenna, mobile	Single antenna, mobile	Multiple-antenna, stationary	1 UE (if DL) or 1 BS (if UL) with sectorized sensing capabilities (Sector-wise Rx power measurements), depicted as sensing node	At least 1 so-called sensing-node in Rx associated with the RISs, which can be co-located with a BS (if UL to be protected) or a UE (if DL to be protected)
Nb, type and mobility regime of Passive Objects	No passive objects	No passive objects	Multiple moving passive object	Multiple, Mobile	Multiple, Mobile
Nb, types and mobility regimes of RISs	One reflective nearly-passive RIS, mobile	One reflective nearly-passive RIS, stationary	No RIS assumed	None	Multiple static dual-beam reflect. RISs
Environment					
Indoor/outdoor	Indoor	Outdoor	Outdoor	n/a	n/a
LoS/NLoS conditions	Both	Both	Both	Both (Transient shadowing created by mobile obstacles)	Both (Transient shadowing created by moving obstacles)
Radio Set-up					
Uplink/Downlink/Full-Duplex	Uplink/Downlink	Uplink/Downlink	n/a	Uplink/Downlink	Uplink/Downlink
Tested frequency (mostly for evaluations when specified)	n/a	n/a	n/a	mmWave (typically 5G-NR FR2 or FR3)	mmWave (typically 5G-NR FR2 or FR3)
Bandwidth	Agnostic, narrow-band	Agnostic, narrow-band	n/a	n/a	n/a

Near-field/Far-field regime	Far-field	Near-field and Far-field	n/a	n/a	n/a
Time synchronisation requirements	Yes	Yes	None	Standard requirements for 5G-NR type communications	Synchronisation btw. sensing nodes and their associated RIS Standard requirements for 5G-NR type communications (besides)
Phase coherence requirements	None	None	None	None	None
Localisation and/or Sensing Operations (if any)					
Type of radio measurements at distributed sensing points	Angle, delay	Angle, delay	n/a	Received power (for each RIS beam steering angle/sector) Sensing node-centric detected/occupied angular sector (out of Rx power analysis)	Received power (for each RIS beam steering angle/sector) RIS-centric detected/occupied angular sector (out of Rx power analysis)
Entity collecting the radio measurements (for fusion)	Central unit	External AI module	n/a	Any sensing node (BS or UE), after collecting info from its neighbours, in case of distributed positioning Local fusion centre (can be collocated with one specific sensing node)	Any sensing node (BS or UE), after receiving reflected signals from multiple RISs or collecting info from other sensing nodes, in case of distributed positioning Local fusion centre (can be collocated with one specific sensing node)
Data Communications (if any)					
Type and traffic of conveyed information (ex. data format, refresh. rate...)	Reference signals sent by APs	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a
QoS requirements	None	None	None	None	None
Transmission range/coverage requirement	10s of meters	10s of meters	None	A few 10s of meters at most	A few 10s of meters at most
Throughput requirements	None	None	None	None	None
Spectral efficiency requirements	None	None	None	None	None

Cnt'd	Cont. #B-11: Large-scale/Long-term Targets Tracking based on Cooperative Sensing Nodes	Cont. #B-12: Joint Detection and Localisation of Multiple Moving Targets in a Distributed Radar System	Cont. #B-13: mmWave Cellular Passive Drone Detection with Reconfigurable Intelligent Surfaces	Cont. #B-14: RF Imaging based on Physics-Informed Neural Networks and New Physical Models	Cont. #B-15: Digital Twin Aided Sensing
Physical Deployment					
Nb, types and mobility regimes of TX nodes	Multiple single-antenna UE, constant velocity Multiple multi-antenna BSs, if sensing passive targets	Multiple single-antenna stationary TXs	Multiple antenna, stationary TX	Single Tx, single antenna, non mobile	Single antenna, stationary
Nb, types and mobility regimes of RX nodes	Multiple multi-antenna BSs, stationary	Multiple single-antenna stationary RXs co-located with TXs	Multiple antenna, stationary RX	Multiple static single-antenna RXs	Single antenna stationary

Nb, type and mobility regime of Passive Objects	Scattering points, reflectors, stationary	Multiple, mobile	Drone, mobile	Multiple static solid conducting objects	Up to 3 objects, static or moving
Nb, types and mobility regimes of RISs	n/a	n/a	Passive RIS, stationary	n/a	No RIS envisioned
Environment					
Indoor/outdoor	Outdoor	Outdoor	Outdoor	Indoor (free space)	Both
LoS/NLoS conditions	NLoS	Both	Both	LoS	Both
Radio Set-up					
Uplink/Downlink/Full-Duplex	Uplink	Full-duplex	Downlink	Downlink	Uplink/Downlink
Tested frequency (mostly for evaluations when specified)	28GHz	10 GHz	28 GHz	n/a	Sub-6 GHz
Bandwidth	400MHz	5 MHz	10 MHz	n/a	Flexible
Near-field/Far-field regime	Far-field	Far-field	Far-field	Near-field	n/a
Time synchronisation requirements	Among BSs	Different monostatic radars are time-synchronised	None	Among RXs	None
Phase coherence requirements	None	None	None	Synchronisation among the RXs but not with e TX.	None
Localisation and/or Sensing Operations (If any)					
Type of radio measurements at distributed sensing points	ToA and AoA	Delay, Doppler	Channel Impulse Response	Received pilots	Channel Impulse Response
Entity collecting the radio measurements (for fusion)	BS	Fusion centre collecting measurements from individual monostatic radars	UE	SRx	n/a
Data Communications (if any)					
Type and traffic of conveyed information (ex. data format, refresh. rate...)	n/a	Received radar IQ data sent to fusion centre	n/a	n/a	n/a.
QoS requirements	None	None	None	None	None
Transmission range/coverage requirement	None	None	None	Full-area coverage	None
Throughput requirements	None	Communication bandwidth should support the high-data-rate between radars and FC	None	None	None
Spectral efficiency requirements	None	None	None	None	None

5.1 Localisation of Connected Users

5.1.1 Contribution #B-1: Joint RIS Channel Estimation and Localisation via Dictionary Learning and Compressed Sensing

Motivation and Challenges

As already mentioned in Sec. 2, RISs are set to become a cornerstone technology in next-generation wireless networks, enabling efficient programmability of the propagation environment. With the growing demand for higher data rates and precise localisation, and the transition to higher operational frequencies such as mmWave bands, they hold immense potential to enhance performance by improving channel estimation and localisation accuracy. However, this technology also introduces new challenges, including hardware impairments, which can adversely affect system performance.

Deployment Scenario

The system model demonstrated in Figure 5-1 involves a RIS-aided mmWave communication setup, where a BS communicates with a UE through a RIS. The model considers a frequency-selective environment, incorporating both the BS-UE and BS-RIS-UE channels, which are essential for accurate channel estimation and localisation. The deployment scenario is designed to reflect realistic conditions, accounting for hardware impairments such as mutual coupling and gain/phase errors at the BS, RIS, and UE. Additionally, the model addresses the challenge of clock offsets between the transmitter and receiver, which can significantly impact localisation accuracy.

Figure 5-1: Visual representation of the considered RIS-aided joint localisation and communication system.

Although this setup focuses primarily on a single-RIS scenario, the approach is also highly relevant to DISAC contexts. The same estimation framework can indeed be extended to distributed systems involving multiple RISs or base stations, where each node performs local estimation and contributes to a cooperative localisation task.

Proposed Approach and Followed Methodology

The proposed approach involves a novel algorithmic solution that integrates a multidimensional orthogonal matching pursuit algorithm (MOMP) for joint channel estimation and localisation in RIS-aided systems. The algorithm employs a dictionary learning stage to calibrate hardware impairments at the user array, enhancing the accuracy of channel estimation. By formulating the problem as a sparse recovery task with independent dictionaries for angle and delay domains, the approach effectively addresses the challenges posed by large antenna arrays and hardware imperfections. This results in a low-complexity solution that significantly improves localisation accuracy in realistic indoor scenarios simulated through ray tracing. This structure also supports distributed extensions, as the dictionary learning and sparse recovery steps can

be performed independently at different nodes and later fused, enabling scalable deployment in DISAC systems.

Results and Discussion

Figure 5-2 demonstrates significant improvements in channel estimation and localisation accuracy when utilizing the proposed RIS-aided approach. The findings indicate that, even at low transmit power levels, the integration of both the BS-UE and RIS-UE channels leads to centimeter-level localisation accuracy, highlighting the effectiveness of the proposed methodology. The analysis shows that while the localisation errors are relatively constant with only the BS-UE channel, they increase when relying solely on the RIS-UE channel due to double path loss. However, the use of larger RISs further reduces localisation errors, underscoring the potential of RIS technology in enhancing positioning performance. Overall, the results validate the effectiveness of the MOMP-based algorithm and the dictionary learning strategy in achieving high localisation accuracy in complex indoor environments.

Related Dissemination

M. Bayraktar, et al. "RIS-Aided Joint Channel Estimation and Localisation at mmWave Under Hardware Impairments: A Dictionary Learning-Based Approach." submitted to IEEE Transactions on Wireless Communications.

Figure 5-2: CDF of the TDoA estimation error for the path with the lowest TDoA of either the BS-MS or the RIS-MS channel

5.1.2 Contribution #B-2: Frugal Localisation and Synchronisation with Multiple Reconfigurable Intelligent Surfaces

Motivations and Challenges

A significant limitation of existing research on RIS-aided localisation is that carrier frequency offset (CFO) between the BS and user equipment UE is often neglected [KKS+21]. CFO, alongside the use of distinct RIS phase profiles, such as those employed for beam sweeping in AoD estimation [BT21], induces phase variations over time, leading to the angle-Doppler/CFO coupling phenomenon, which complicates accurate localisation and synchronisation [FKC+22]. Experimental studies have shown that it is possible to achieve SISO localisation for a stationary UE with a single BS and two RISs [KDA+23]. However, these setups often rely on unrealistic assumptions, such as the BS and UE sharing a common oscillator to mitigate CFO effects. Furthermore, these methods typically depend on directional RIS beams to perform beam sweeping and estimate AoDs, an approach that is unsuitable when employing random RIS phase profiles, which is a standard practice in RIS-aided communications for unknown UE locations [EGG+21].

These challenges highlight two fundamental questions unanswered so far: first, is it feasible to jointly achieve 3D downlink localisation and frequency synchronisation in a SISO narrowband setting with multiple RISs operating under random phase configurations? Second, can efficient, low-complexity algorithms be developed to detect the presence of LoS between the BS and the UE, estimate channel parameters and CFO, and enable localisation in both the presence and absence of the direct LoS path between the BS and the UE?

Deployment Scenario

In alignment with the 6G goals of sustainability and efficiency, we focus on a frugal communication scenario with minimal spatial and spectral resources (i.e., narrowband SISO system). Hence, the deployment scenario consists of a single-antenna BS, multiple RISs, and a single-antenna UE, as shown in Figure 5-3. The BS transmits narrowband signals to the UE, with the RISs assisting by reflecting these signals to enhance coverage and localisation accuracy. Each RIS is composed of multiple passive elements that can adjust the phase of the incident signals, thereby controlling the reflection direction. The positions and orientations of the RISs are assumed to be known. The goal of the UE is to estimate its 3D location and CFO using complex scalar downlink measurements collected over multiple transmission instances.

Figure 5-3: Frugal localisation scenario involving one single-antenna BS, 3 RISs and one single-antenna user with NB (single-carrier) communication.

Proposed Approach and Followed Methodology

Low-complexity estimators for CFO and AoD have been proposed to enable accurate localisation. Separate estimation algorithms are developed for different scenarios: one for the cases where a direct LoS exists between the BS and the UE, and two for situations where the LoS is blocked. In addition, a generalised likelihood ratio test (GLRT)-based detector is designed to identify the presence of a LoS path, completing the framework for comprehensive localisation and synchronisation. The proposed approach is evaluated for its sensitivity to MPCs, demonstrating rapid convergence to theoretical bounds even with a low Rician factor of 10. The impact of CFO estimation is also analysed by considering a CFO-agnostic estimator, revealing significant performance degradation at even small CFO values.

Results and Discussion

As shown in Figure 5-4, comprehensive simulations have confirmed that the proposed approach (RMSE-ML and its low-complexity variant RMSE-LC) meets theoretical performance thresholds in scenarios with medium to high transmit power, illustrating its efficacy in localizing single-antenna UEs using minimal spectral and BS antenna resources. Additionally, our analysis underlines the vital role of CFO estimation in achieving precise localisation, as evidenced by comparisons with a previous CFO-agnostic method. The omission of CFO estimation substantially diminishes performance, underscoring its criticality in our model. Furthermore, our method's effectiveness was proven in simulated multipath conditions, where it achieved performance close to theoretical predictions even with a Rician factor of just 10.

Figure 5-4: Position estimation performance vs. transmit power for the scenario with 2 RISs under LoS blockage.

Related Dissemination

Y. Etefagh, et. al., “Frugal RIS-aided 3D Localisation with CFO under LoS and NLoS Conditions”, submitted to IEEE Transactions on Vehicular Technology.

5.1.3 Contribution #B-3: Phase-coherent Downlink Localisation and Synchronisation with Distributed Access Points

Motivations and Challenges

Accurate UE localisation is a key enabler for emerging 6G applications such as extended reality, autonomous systems, and digital twins [RDM+24], [MPM+21]. Among the candidate technologies, D-MIMO systems are particularly promising due to their spatial diversity and ability to form large virtual antenna apertures [AVM+23]. While prior works have primarily focused on uplink-based localisation [NMP21], [NMM+19], [FDK+25], downlink-based positioning is especially attractive because it allows for network-side beam focusing, which can significantly enhance localisation accuracy. Downlink also scales efficiently for multiple UEs without additional network overhead.

However, downlink-based localisation introduces new challenges. The UE, being unsynchronised with the network, must estimate both its position and phase offset from the received downlink signals. This joint estimation becomes difficult when multiple APs transmit simultaneously, leading to superposed signals at the UE, which necessitates new estimation frameworks.

Deployment Scenario

A downlink D-MIMO system is considered, comprising multiple APs, each equipped with multiple antennas and jointly coordinated through a central processing unit. These APs are synchronised in phase, enabling them to act as a virtual large-scale antenna array. A single-antenna UE is located somewhere within this area, and the network aims to localize and synchronize the UE using only downlink pilot signals (See Figure 5-5). Each AP transmits single-carrier pilot signals over a designated subcarrier. Two transmission protocols are explored. In the sequential transmission protocol, referred to as P1, APs transmit beams, one at a time. In contrast, the simultaneous transmission protocol, referred to as P2, involves all APs transmitting concurrently in a phase-coordinated manner. The UE, which is not synchronised with the network, uses the received downlink signals to estimate its position and phase offset.

Proposed Approach and Followed Methodology

The localisation and synchronisation problem is framed as a maximum likelihood (ML) estimation problem, aiming to jointly estimate the UE’s 2D position and its phase offset. The ML esti-

mation problem is solved by an iterative process, wherein the amplitude coefficients of the received signals are first estimated, followed by a phase offset estimation. The resulting objective function is minimised using a 2D exhaustive search to determine the optimal UE position. To further enhance the accuracy and reduce the computational complexity, the non-coherent solution is used as an initialization point for the coherent solution. The performance of both solutions is evaluated in terms of localisation and synchronisation accuracy.

Figure 5-5: System model of a downlink D-MIMO system for UE localisation. The APs are phase-synchronised, leading to two options for downlink beamforming (P1 and P2).

Results and Discussion

In the following simulation-based performance evaluations, a network of 20 4-antenna APs is considered. These APs are placed uniformly along the edges of a 40 m × 40 m square centered at the origin with their antennas oriented towards the centre. The APs precode unity pilots to illuminate 36 illumination points. These illumination points are uniformly distributed over a 5 m × 5 m square region around the origin. The total transmit energy of the AP network remains fixed across both transmission protocols. The UE is positioned at $u = [1, 1]$ m and has a phase offset of 10 deg relative to the AP network. The system operates at a carrier frequency of 3.5 GHz.

Figure 5-6 shows the 1D Position Error Bound (PEB) as a function of the x-coordinate of the UE position, for $y = 1$ m, considering both coherent and non-coherent processing for protocols P1 and P2. The illumination region, which is indicated by the red region, represents the portion of space where APs focus their beams. We observe that for coherent processing, the PEB values for both P1 and P2 reach their minima at the centre of the illumination region. In contrast, for non-coherent processing, the PEB at the centre is higher than at the edges. This occurs because the beams formed by APs in non-coherent operation are much wider than those in coherent operation, resulting in limited spatial diversity at the centre (illuminated by the main lobe, unlike the edges illuminated by the sidelobes), which degrades positioning performance.

Related Dissemination

S. Dey, et. al. “Joint Localisation and Synchronisation in Downlink Distributed MIMO”, accepted to EUSIPCO 2025.

Figure 5-6: PEB values versus the x-coordinate of the UE position for transmission protocols P1 and P2 with coherent and non-coherent processing.

5.1.4 Contribution #B-4: Joint Localisation, Synchronisation and Mapping via Phase-Coherent Distributed Arrays

Motivations and Challenges

The emergence of ELAAs in beyond-5G and 6G networks has unlocked unprecedented opportunities for joint localisation, synchronisation, and mapping. Among distributed ELAA implementations, radio stripes (RSs) offer a cost-efficient and scalable architecture particularly suited for dense indoor environments such as train stations and stadiums [SBL21]. Their ability to support carrier phase measurements and synchronisation over a distributed network makes them promising for high-accuracy localisation at sub-6 GHz. However, RS-based systems face several challenges: maintaining phase coherence across distributed units is non-trivial, especially under hardware imperfections; accurately modelling multipath propagation from specular and scattering sources is complex; and achieving joint estimation of position, clock, and phase offsets along with environmental features (e.g., scatterer locations) remains computationally intensive. These challenges necessitate innovative signal models and scalable estimation algorithms to fully exploit the RS potential under realistic indoor conditions.

Deployment Scenario

The deployment scenario involves a single-antenna UE communicating with a network of phase- and time-synchronised APs distributed across an indoor environment (See Figure 5-7). Although the APs are synchronised with each other, they remain unsynchronised with the UE, introducing clock and phase offset estimation as additional states besides localisation and mapping. The propagation environment includes both LoS paths and NLoS paths caused by reflections and scattering from walls and objects. In this setup, we aim at jointly estimating UE location, clock and phase offsets, and the positions of SPs, thereby enabling comprehensive situational awareness and environmental mapping.

Proposed Approach and Followed Methodology

A three-step approach is proposed to address the localisation and mapping problem in distributed architectures supported by radio stripes. In the first step, the phase offset of the UE is estimated using the carrier phase information from LoS paths. This is followed by estimating the UE's location and clock offset by combining LoS information with reflections from walls. Finally, the positions of scattering points are determined through a null-space transformation technique, which enhances the resolution of multipath components. By optimally integrating observations

from all distributed arrays, this methodology aims at effectively mitigating the high dimensionality of the estimation problem, while benefiting from high localisation accuracy.

Figure 5-7: Representative scenario of uplink UE localisation supported by a network of 4 distributed radio stripes. There are 2 dominant scatterers, 4 walls, and a single UE.

Results and Discussions

In terms of simulation-based performance evaluations, the proposed approach has been shown to achieve mm-level localisation accuracy at high SNRs when APs are phase-synchronised. As an example, Figure 5-8 illustrates the PEB across spatial locations in a room under different bandwidth regimes. In low-bandwidth regime, severe path overlap between the LoS, specular reflected paths (RPs), and SPs leads to degraded positioning accuracy, especially in corners. Angular information dominates due to insufficient bandwidth to resolve delays. Mid-bandwidth regime shows improvement as overlap with RPs is resolved, yet SP-related overlaps persist, continuing to affect accuracy. In the high-bandwidth, delay resolution improves substantially, allowing all paths to be separated and resulting in smoother and more accurate positioning across the space, with delay information being the primary driver of localisation performance.

Figure 5-8: PEB in the low-bandwidth regime (3MHz, left figure), the mid-bandwidth regime (30MHz, middle figure), and the high-bandwidth regime (300MHz).

Related Dissemination

A. Fascista, et al. "Joint Localisation, Synchronisation and Mapping via Phase-Coherent Distributed Arrays." submitted to IEEE Journal of Selected Topics in Signal Processing.

5.1.5 Contribution #B-5: Near-Field Localisation with Dynamic Metasurface Antennas at THz

Motivation and Challenges

The next generation of wireless networks is anticipated to deliver advanced localisation and sensing capabilities, especially at THz frequencies. At these frequencies, the use of extremely large antenna arrays, such as DMAs, offers significantly improved angular and range resolution. DMAs enable the integration of numerous sub-wavelength-spaced metamaterials, typically grouped into microstrips, each connected to a reception RF chain, within potentially large apertures. Despite these advantages, the optimisation of DMA configurations for effective near-field localisation remains underexplored compared to other beamforming architectures, such as fluid antennas or hybrid and fully connected phase-shifter networks.

Deployment Scenario

A reception-based system featuring a DMA-based panel is employed (as the one showcased in Figure 5-9) for near-field localisation of multiple single-antenna UEs within the DMA's effective coverage area. Operating in the THz frequency band, the system comprises multiple microstrips, each containing an array of phase-tunable metamaterials arranged in a linear configuration.

Proposed Approach and Followed Methodology

The proposed approach focuses on optimising the analog beamforming weights of DMA-enabled Rx for near-field localisation, specifically in the THz frequency band. The methodology involves deriving the CRB for estimating user position parameters, and indirectly optimising it by minimising its lower bound, which serves as the objective for designing the DMA's reception beamforming weights. The design problem is reformulated into a Rayleigh quotient maximization problem with discrete constraints to accommodate the analog weights of the DMA. The optimisation is carried out through a projection and greedy-based schemes, allowing for efficient computation.

Figure 5-9: The considered DMA-equipped RX, including its geometry and the adopted coordinate system, used for near-field localisation.

This design approach is also promising for distributed settings, where optimisation can be performed locally at each DMA node and coordinated through lightweight information exchange. Such decentralised strategies would maintain high localisation accuracy with reduced system overhead in DISAC deployments.

Results and Discussion

Figure 5-10 demonstrates the effectiveness of the proposed designs for near-field localisation using DMAs in the THz frequency band. Specifically, the root mean square error (RMSE) of user position estimation improves with increased transmit power, converging towards the position error bound. The proposed projection-based and greedy-based designs outperform conventional methods, such as maximising received SNR, showcasing superior localisation accuracy. Notably, the projection and greedy approaches yield comparable performance, with the greedy method being more favourable for low-complexity implementations.

Related Dissemination

I. Gavras and G. C. Alexandropoulos, "Near-Field Localisation with Dynamic Metasurface Antennas at THz: A CRB Minimising Approach," submitted to IEEE Wireless Communications Letters.

5.1.6 Contribution #B-6: Mobile User Localisation and Tracking Exploiting Mobile RISs and Fixed Beacons

Motivations and Challenges

AGVs and robots commonly depend on relative positioning for navigation due to the unavailability of GPS indoors. This reliance can lead to safety concerns, particularly as interactions between AGVs and human workers increase, and may potentially lead to accidents [CWH+23]. To mitigate these risks, an original localisation solution based on RISs is proposed and investigated in this work. The approach involves placing fixed beacons within the environment, while AGVs are equipped with RIS units that dynamically reflect signals toward IoT-tagged objects, such as human workers. This method is specifically intended for smart factory environments.

Figure 5-10: Mean RMSE of the positions of the U = 3 UEs versus the transmit power in dBm.

Deployment Scenario

The considered deployment scenario is shown in Figure 5-11 below. We assume that three fixed beacons are placed in the environment, in position $\{x_i, y_i\}_{i=1}^3$. Moreover, an RIS is mounted on top of a mobile AGV, whose position and orientation is represented by $\{x_R, y_R\}$ and θ_R , respectively. Lastly, the target IoT device to be localised is in position $\{x_D, y_D\}$.

Figure 5-11: Deployment scenario for indoor user localisation with mobile RIS-AGV and fixed beacons, where the dependency of the relative angles on time (under AGV mobility) has been deliberately omitted here for the sake of representation simplicity.

Proposed Approach and Followed Methodology

One main working assumption is that there is no direct connection between the beacons and the device to be localised, which is assumed to be positioned in a hard-to-reach area (e.g., a shelf or in NLoS with respect to the beacons). Moreover, the IoT target is assumed to be a simple device, which is not capable of estimating the DoA of a received signal, nor its ToA, but it can only measure received power. Accordingly, the proposed approach consists in two major phases, as follows.

First, the AGV-mounted RIS is localised (Step 1). This part involves estimating both the position and the orientation of the RIS, by exploiting reference signals sent from the three beacons, whose positions in the environment are known.

Second, the IoT device is localised, given the estimated RIS-AGV position (Step 2). This part is also subdivided into two additional sub-tasks. Initially, based on the result of the first step, the RIS scans the environment by exploiting its precise beamforming capabilities to detect the direction to the IoT device (Step 2.1). Then, the AGV moves into a second position with known offset in terms of $\{x_R, y_R\}$ coordinates (Step 2.2), and repeats the previous scanning sub-task (Step 2.1).

The overall IoT device position estimate is finally calculated by combining the results from the two last sub-tasks (i.e., Steps 2.1 and 2.2).

Results and Discussion

As shown in Figure 5-12 below, the performance of the proposed approach is verified in a 30m x 30m indoor environment, wherein the beacons are placed at the border forming an L-shape. It is assumed that the AGV can move by steps of 5 m, where the two consecutive RIS-AGV positions are marked as RIS-1 and RIS-2, respectively. The true and estimated IoT device locations are indicated by a star and a dot, respectively, with different colours indicating different scenarios. In these evaluation scenarios, a mean localisation error of 2.5 m has been empirically demonstrated.

In the future, the plan is to investigate the impact of the beacon deployment, as well as the radius of the AGV consecutive steps.

Figure 5-12: IoT device localisation exploiting AGV-mounted mobile RIS and with an L-shaped beacon deployment.

Related Dissemination

The results of this contribution are under preparation for a paper submission.

5.1.7 Contribution #B-7: Opportunistic User Localisation based on Available RIS Configurations and Environment Knowledge

Motivations and Challenges

In this contribution, we propose a method for tackling the challenge of inferring the user position with high accuracy and without the need to deploy additional infrastructure or relying on power-hungry methods such as GPS, by exploiting the controlled-reflective properties of an RIS. The latter is deployed to assist in the communication between the base station and the user itself. While existing methods (see, e.g., [AKK+21]) require sending specific reference signals for the localisation/sensing application, the proposed method does not interfere with the communication part, as it uses a copy of the received RIS configuration to estimate the location in parallel, thus leaving the ongoing communication unaffected. This method is dubbed as *COLoRIS*, i.e., an *opportunistic ISAC* method with RIS [EDR+25]. Indeed, *COLoRIS* leverages localisation-agnostic RIS configurations to position mobile users via trained learning methods.

While the design presented in this contribution is specific for a single link between a BS and a user via a RIS, it can be extended to consider a distributed setup where multiple RISs collaboratively localise one user, thereby providing multiple points of view on the estimated user position, which can ultimately reduce uncertainty and avoid blockage.

Deployment Scenario

As shown in Figure 5-13, we consider a wireless network with a multi-antenna BS, an N-antenna RIS and a single UE, whose position is unknown. We assume that the RIS is controlled by a RIS controller that instructs the RIS of its configuration, which is optimised for communication, receives feedback from the UE, and communicates with an opportunistic ISAC network module,

which is in charge of running at AI algorithm to estimate the user position given the RIS configuration.

In the case of a distributed setup, such module collects inputs from the available RISs and initially runs the COLoRIS routine per each RIS. In a subsequent step, the outcome of each instance of the AI module is fused together to output a single user position estimate.

Figure 5-13: Schematic representation of COLoRIS.

Proposed Approach and Followed Methodology

An AI architecture is proposed to localise users without interfering with communication operation at the RIS, following a 2-step approach.

First, relevant information is extracted through an AI architecture without interfering with the RIS optimisation process so that the position of the user can be inferred.

Then, for the purpose of making the information usable and combinable with other sources (e.g., for sensor fusion), the uncertainty affecting the previous position estimate is also characterised.

Results and Discussion

The system demonstrates robust performance across simulations and implementation stages. In the former case, as shown in Figure 5-14 - a) below, it was observed an average error of 5.04 m in large-scale (100m x 100m) deployment, an enhanced direction estimation in far-field conditions, and an accurate distance estimation in near-field scenarios. Direction estimation improves in far field, but distance estimation is only accurate in near field. In the latter case, it achieved 0.70 m average localisation error in indoor environments with extremely efficient power consumption at 179 μ J per position inference.

Figure 5-14: COLoRIS performance; a) results for simulation stage and b) for implementation stage.

Related Dissemination

G. Encinas-Lago, et al. "COLoRIS: Localisation-agnostic Smart Surfaces Enabling Opportunistic ISAC in 6G Networks", IEEE Transactions on Mobile Computing, Early Access, March 2025.

5.2 Sensing of Passive Objects

5.2.1 Contribution #B-8: Sensing based on 5G Standard Signals within Distributed Architectures

Motivations and Challenges

Among the reference signals available in 5G networks, the PRS stands out for sensing purposes due to its rich time-frequency resources and flexible configuration. Introduced in 3GPP Release 16 of the 5G specification, PRS aims to enhance the position accuracy of connected UE because of its high resource element (RE) density and superior correlation properties compared to existing reference signals. On the other hand, in 5G NR, the Physical Downlink Shared Channel (PDSCH) serves as the physical downlink channel for user data transmission, with the Demodulation Reference Signal (DMRS) [TS 38.211] serving as the associated reference signal. DMRS, replacing the cell-specific reference signal (CRS) in LTE, aids in channel estimation and PDSCH decoding. In the ISAC framework, where communication and sensing co-occur, we aim to take advantage of PRS and DMRS configuration for sensing.

This approach can be further extended to distributed sensing by leveraging coordinated configurations of PRS and DMRS across multiple distributed transmitters and receivers. By synchronising and sharing sensing-related information between these distributed nodes, it becomes possible to enhance sensing coverage, improve spatial resolution, and enable joint processing for more accurate environmental perception in large-scale or complex deployment scenarios.

Deployment Scenario

A downlink ISAC scenario is assumed, in which a gNodeB (gNB) transmits the signal toward a scanning area containing K point-like targets. One receiver is considered, which not only captures echoes from these targets to estimate their range and velocity, but also receives the communication signals. The targets are also assumed to be in the LoS of both the transmitter and the receiver. An example of scenario can be seen in Figure 5-15. The figure illustrates a deployed setup that adopts a bistatic configuration, characterized by the spatial separation between the transmitter (i.e., the gNB) and the receiver (i.e., the UE), making synchronisation between them crucial. In bistatic setups, maintaining accurate timing and synchronisation between the transmitter and receiver is essential for reliable sensing performance. In this configuration, synchronisation is achieved through the UE, which is already synchronised with the gNB as part of its standard communication process. The data received by the UE for communication purposes is also leveraged for sensing, thereby ensuring that the sensing functionality benefits from the existing synchronisation framework inherent to the communication system.

A distributed sensing configuration could be obtained by utilising multiple UEs and gNBs within the network, where each node contributes sensing information while remaining synchronised through the communication infrastructure. By coordinating the sensing data across these distributed nodes, it becomes possible to achieve a more comprehensive and accurate sensing picture, particularly in complex or large-scale environments.

Proposed Approach and Followed Methodology

In this ISAC scenario, a gNB transmits signals towards a scanning area containing K point-like targets. A receiver captures echoes from these targets, enabling range and velocity estimation. Additionally, the receiver receives communication signals from the gNB. While the targets are assumed to be in LoS with both the transmitter and receiver, the UE and gNB themselves are in a NLoS configuration. This setup poses challenges for accurate target detection, particularly

in terms of range and Doppler estimation, due to the potential for signal distortion and multipath effects. However, the inherent synchronisation capabilities of the communication network, where the UE is tightly synchronised with the gNB as part of standard communication procedures, provide a valuable advantage. This existing synchronisation framework not only supports reliable communication but also enables accurate sensing, helping to mitigate some of the uncertainties introduced by the NLoS condition.

Figure 5-15: Adopted scenario for the simultaneous sensing and communication receiver.

This configuration presents a challenge for accurate target detection due to potential ambiguity in range and Doppler estimation. The ambiguity in target detection primarily arises from the periodicity and sparsity inherent to the PRS signal, as well as in the DMRS signal. When these pilot signals are used independently for sensing, their sparse structure can lead to the appearance of ghost targets, causing false detections and degrading sensing performance. This issue is particularly pronounced when relying on a single pilot type, as the gaps in time and frequency make it difficult to distinguish true targets from ambiguous reflections.

To address this, a novel approach is proposed that utilises the PRS jointly with the DMRS for ambiguity removal. By leveraging the unique characteristics of both signals, each allocated at different time instances for sensing, the effective sparsity pattern becomes more diverse. This joint utilization helps to mitigate ambiguities and reduces the likelihood of ghost targets, thereby enhancing the reliability and accuracy of the sensing process. The proposed method enhances the accuracy of target detection and estimation, enabling reliable ISAC operation in complex environments. This initial configuration will be extended in future work to encompass scenarios where the target is also in NLoS to both the UE and the gNB, further increasing the complexity and requiring more sophisticated techniques for accurate target detection and estimation.

Results and Discussion

In Figure 5-16, it is shown how pilot signals such as PRS and DMRS could be jointly exploited to remove the ghost target (or ambiguity) with a comb 12 configuration.

Figure 5-16 (a) and Figure 5-16 (c) illustrate the ambiguity in range estimation. This ambiguity makes distinguishing between real and ghost targets quite challenging. When the weight for mower allocation for sensing $\sqrt{\gamma_s} = 0.1$ and the power allocated to PRS is low, the combination of PRS and DMRS fails to effectively mitigate the ambiguity, as depicted in Figure 5-16 (b). For instance, when $\sqrt{\gamma_s} = 0.5$, the real targets are distinguishable, allowing accurate identification of the two highest peaks in the sensing output. This enables reliable estimation of the target ranges with improved precision.

In future work, this study will be extended for distributed sensing with NLOS configuration of the target versus the TxS and RxS.

Related Dissemination

K. Khosroshahi, et al. "Localization Accuracy Improvement in Multistatic ISAC with LoS/NLoS Condition using 5G NR Signals." submitted to IEEE WCNC 2025.

Figure 5-16: Ghost target elimination with the presence of two target with $Comb = 12$, $F_c = 25$ GHz and $s_{cs} = 120$ kHz.

5.2.2 Contribution #B-9: Cooperative Sensing of Side Lobes Interference for Blockage Detection and Localisation in Dense mmWave Networks

Motivations and Challenges

In mmWave networks, radio link interruptions can lead to a severe degradation of the UE QoS, hence requiring frequent handover procedures that strongly affect overall network performance. Therefore, the prediction of link blockages through environment sensing is essential to enable more efficient sensing-aided radio resource management (RRM) strategies. To address this problem, most of related state-of-the-art approaches still consider relatively "late" in-band detection mechanisms (e.g., relying on extra guard beams alongside the main communication beam between the BS and the UE [HMP22], or drawing empirical statistics of the received power associated with the direct path, conditioned on free space or obstructions [GYB+19]). Beyond, another in-band detection method initially proposed in [SDD23] makes use of side-lobe information in dense mmWave networks. The temporal fluctuations of the ambient interference power perceived from active transmitters (i.e., other UEs or BSs) in angular sectors around the sensing node are analysed for a certain time window, enabling the reconstruction of the mobile blocker's space-time power profile and hence, the detection of the angular sectors it occupies.

Extending the previous approach into a distributed scenario, the aim here is to benefit from multi-node cooperation to provide more robust 2D position estimates of the blocker (i.e., beyond the only angular sector detection), as multiple sensing nodes can share the results of their own independent detection procedures.

Deployment Scenario

As illustrated in Figure 5-17 - (a), a dense mmWave network is considered, composed of a large number of BSs disseminated in a 2D environment that provide service coverage to multiple UEs. For simplicity, it is assumed that each UE has been preliminarily associated with its closest BS during an initial access phase, where all the UEs perform beam training and beam alignment mechanisms to optimise their beam configurations during the subsequent data service phase.

In this dense network, one mobile passive object is present, moving with a relatively low velocity (e.g., typically pedestrian or wheeled robots), possibly causing the blockage of both interfering and direct communication paths to the receiving sensing nodes (SRxs).

Just like in [SDD23], the cooperative UEs serving as SRxs are supposed to be equipped with sectored antenna systems. They take benefit from DL communications with respect to their serving BSs to detect the presence of the mobile blocker, and finally share their detection information with other sensing nodes in the vicinity (either directly over sidelinks or through the network via their BSs).

Proposed Approach and Followed Methodology

Each sensing UE (i.e., SRx) of the cooperative set first performs independently sector-wise interference power measurements in its observation time window, builds the corresponding “sensing matrix”, before applying a Singular Value Decomposition (SVD) [SDD23] to get the blocker space-time power profile. The latter step enables to determine both the current and past angular sectors occupied by the moving obstacle. The accuracy of this preliminary detection phase depends on the distance to the blocker, the size of the sounding sectors, and the Rx power sensitivity at the sensing devices, but also on other extrinsic factors such as channel fading or non-constant Tx activity patterns of interfering sources. These sources of uncertainty can however be mitigated through multi-node cooperation. Accordingly, after receiving from neighbouring fellows their detected sectors, each sensing UE can locally compute an overlapping region where the blocker is supposed to stand (See Figure 5-17 - (b)).

Figure 5-17: Network model from the perspective of sensing UE u_0 , consisting of 3 BSs interfering on a communication link ($b_0 \rightarrow u_0$), with a mobile blocker (robot) moving around; Example of cooperative scenario to localize a mobile blocker (robot) based on 3 sensing EUs (b).

For a given angular sector, the blocker can take any position along a line crossing the sensing node with a certain slope and certain random uncertainty. The intersection of all the detected sectors can hence be simply determined by solving a least square (LS) optimisation problem, following a similar approach to that proposed in [RS19]. Conceptually, the aim is to minimise the Euclidean distances between the estimated position of the blocker and its closest projections onto the bisectors of all the detected sectors (from cooperative neighbours). After a few mathematical manipulations, the solution of the previous problem is calculated by solving a simple linear equation in close form, which can be computed either at the sensing UE itself (in fully distributed schemes), or at a local FC after gathering raw measurements from the sensing nodes in a sub-area (in hierarchical schemes).

Results and Discussion

The heatmap shown in Figure 5-18 illustrates the impact of the number of cooperative sensing nodes on both the coverage and accuracy of the proposed detection scheme in a 50m x 50m zone, for each cell of the scene (i.e., conditioned on the fact that a blocker moving at the velocity of 1 m/s occupies these cells). The reference sensing UE is supposed to be located at the centre of the scene, while cooperating with its closest 10 to 60 neighbouring nodes. As expected, as the number of cooperative nodes increases, the overall system field-of-view is improved since the area covered by all the sensing UEs widens. However, even with large neighbourhood sets, the accuracy still degrades as the blocker approaches the edge of the network, since it gets farther from the sensing UEs that cooperate. In the main region of interest around the link to be protected against blockages (i.e., around the central node performing the fusion process), a small set of neighbours (say even 10) seems still sufficient to get a fairly good estimation accuracy (on the order of 1 m), hence making it possible to detect and avoid blockages at an early stage with the least communication cost. Other results regarding the sensitivity of the method with respect to both the size and the velocity of the blocker are also provided in [DSD24].

Figure 5-18: Accuracy (in m) and coverage of detected blocker’s 2D position estimation with the proposed distributed method in a dense mmWave network, as a function of the number of cooperative sensing nodes N .

This work has been extended to RIS-aided scenarios (See Sec. 5.2.3) and could be leveraged to feed proactive sensing-based handover mechanisms (See Sec. 6.1).

Future works will consider handling both data association and tracking problems in presence of multiple mobile passive blockers. The sensitivity of the proposed cooperative approach with respect to sources of power under mobility and/or with intermittently emission patterns (especially regarding interfering BSs and UEs) shall also be assessed.

Related Dissemination

H. Dakdouk, et al., “Cooperative Sensing of Side Lobes Interference for Blockage Localisation and Mapping in Dense mmWave Networks”, Joint EuCNC’24 & 6G Summit’24, Antwerp, June 2024.

5.2.3 Contribution #B-10: Detection and Cooperative Localisation of Moving Passive Objects through RIS Beam Scanning of Non-coherent Power Sources

Motivations and Challenges

Just like in Sec. 5.2.2, the aim here is also to position, track, and predict radio blockers in the context of mmWave networks.

Related State-of-the-Art solutions like [HMP22], [SDD23], [GYB+19] have all in common to provide a sensing field of view that is strictly restricted to the immediate vicinity of pre-existing communication links. They can indeed mainly detect close blockers approaching or already starting to obstruct the communication links to be protected, hence having only limited capacity to anticipate link obstructions in the very long term and/or to detect far away objects. Moreover, these solutions require a minimal network deployment of active communicating nodes (including at least one UE and one serving BS), one of which playing the role of sensing node. Some of these existing contributions can only operate in specific environments (e.g., very dense mmWave networks with multiple interfering BSs and Multiple UEs, like in [SDD23] and [DSD24]) or they require specific hardware at the communicating nodes used for sensing (e.g., sectored antenna systems in [SDD23], [DSD24], and multibeam capabilities, incl. guard beams in [HMP22]). Others even external assisting technologies (e.g., sub-6Ghz besides the mmWave system to protect in [ADH20]).

Overall, there is a need to design opportunistic blocker detection/tracking solutions that could i) rely on simple radio metrics to ease non-coherent embedded processing (typically, received power at Rx sensing nodes, with respect to non-coordinated ambient sources), ii) thanks to cooperation and spatial distribution, expand the system field of view far enough from the only communication links to be protected (to enable more proactive and large-scale handover), and iii) leverage already deployed mmWave networks. In the following, such a cooperative sensing solution based on dual-beam reflective RISs is described, relaxing in particular the hardware and protocol constraints at SRxs.

Deployment Scenario

The considered deployment comprises at least one so-called *sensing node* and at least one dual-beam *sensing RIS*. The sensing node could be a dedicated receiving device. However, in the context of a mmWave network, depending on whether UL or DL communications are considered, this sensing node can also be a standard UE or a BS, which receives non-coherent signals reflected from the sensing RIS. A sensing node must be associated with at least one sensing RIS. Like in Sec. 5.2.2, multiple spatially distributed ambient sources (passive or active) are assumed to emit and/or scatter non-coherent signals in the environment being sensed (i.e., around the sensing RIS).

Each dual-beam sensing RIS has at least one programmable “input” beam (i.e., the sensing beam). This input beam is used to enable the sensing functionality by opportunistically scanning

angular regions of space, therefrom, reflecting the signal power integrated from non-coherent sources in those regions using its “output” beam (i.e., the reflecting beam), which points towards the sensing node (See Figure 5-19).

Figure 5-19: Deployment scenario for the RIS-aided detection of moving passive obstacles in a mmWave network context, while relying on reflected signals from non-coherent sources (a); Example of extension to a distributed multi-RIS scenario (b).

The proposed system can support the detection of multiple moving obstacles, as long as the sensing RIS has sufficient sensing resolution and/or multiple distributed sensing RISs can be coordinated. These distributed and cooperative extensions, which benefit from spatial diversity and/or information redundancy, hence enable the positioning of moving targets (i.e., beyond the only angular sector detection), similar to Sec. 5.2.2.

Proposed Approach and Followed Methodology

According to the above deployment, the power of the signals originated from ambient sources aggregated in each tested angular sector (i.e., conditioned on the current RIS input beam steering direction) and reflected towards the sensing node is measured to construct a sensing matrix, like in Sec. 5.2.2. This sensing matrix represents the state of the radio environment in the angular sectors being sensed by the sensing RIS within successive observation time windows. Accordingly, the movement of one or multiple passive target(s) in the angular regions sensed by the RIS blocks the signals emitted and/or scattered by the non-coherent sources, causing fluctuations of the perceived signal strength at the sensing node, which are interpreted to detect the moving targets/objects. This can be achieved by processing the acquired sensing matrix, for instance through the same SVD approach as that in [SDD23] and [DSD24] (See Sec. 5.2.2).

If the sensing node is also a communicating UE, depending on whether the RIS beam scanning process is performed simultaneously or sequentially with respect to the DL data communications, different kinds of sensing matrices can be formed. Typically, the latter can be based on the measured received power directly in case of sequential sensing and communication schemes. Alternatively, they can rely on SINR metrics, requiring dedicated calibration phases when the sensing RIS is off, in case of simultaneous sensing and communication schemes (i.e., evaluating the noise power and the interference power typically collected through side lobes of the sensing node). Beyond, in a distributed multi-RIS scenario, the same information sharing and estimation strategy as that in [DSD24] can be applied to determine the position of the moving blocker.

For each single RIS detection independently, a similarity score is also applied to the SVD-based power source separation, using a structural similarity index measure (SSIM) inspired by image processing [WBS+04]. This score quantifies how closely the raw sensing matrix matches the reconstructed static channel alone (i.e., excluding the presumed mobile blocker’s contributions). It contributes to improve the SVD-based signal separation and serves as an indicator of the reliability of the blocker’s space-time power signature used for the detection of occupied angular sectors. Accordingly, before the positioning step, an outlier rejection test is first applied to eliminate the detected angular sectors associated with extremely high SSIM scores. Then, the presumed angular uncertainty, which is needed to weight each remaining detected sector feeding the positioning algorithm, is also fine-tuned based on the relationship between empirical measurement error statistics and the distribution of SSIM scores (over all the tested sectors).

Results and Discussion

In the following numerical illustrations, a very dense network of 24 BSs and 106 UEs is considered, where the BSs are regularly distributed at the periphery of a 160m x 80m area, while serving their closest UEs. Dual-beam 40x20-element sensing RISs are placed regularly along two parallel lines (each comprising 5 RISs), approximately 20m away from the trajectory of one blocker exhibiting moderate pedestrian mobility and passing by the centre of the scene. Without loss of generality, it is also assumed that the whole network operates in DL at 28 GHz. From the sensing standpoint, all the BSs active in transmission in the area behave as uncoordinated STxs (i.e., ambient sources) with an average transmit power of 33 dBm. Each RIS is oriented to sweep its “input” beam in azimuth in the half-plane containing the mobile blocker (i.e., performing 180° beam scanning) and steers its “output” beam towards the closest UE, which serves as collecting sensing node (i.e, SRx). To assess only the localisation performance of the proposed cooperative sensing approach, these few UEs are supposed to operate only in the sensing mode, assuming for instance time sharing between sensing and communications (See [DISACD41]). Figure 5-20 shows an illustration of the corresponding network deployment.

Figure 5-20: Canonical network deployment considered for the evaluation of the proposed selectively cooperative RIS-based sensing approach (big circles: BSs, small circles: UEs, rectangles: RISs, small red circle and red straight line: blocker and its trajectory).

Figure 5-21 - (a) and Figure 5-21 - (b) show the empirical CDFs of the cooperative positioning error when localising the moving blocker under various SSIM-based pre-processing strategies, using at least 5 or 7 sensing RISs at a time respectively. As expected, in both cases the posi-

tioning performance can be significantly improved after rejecting only the most harmful measurement outliers in comparison to using raw detections. Moreover, weighting the selected angular measurements based on SSIM while considering the worst-case error regime assumption (i.e., applying a “Max” weighting method, rather than a more conservative “Mean” weighting method) contributes to considerably improve accuracy. Beyond the impact of pre-processing, the large-error regime is also more favorable when using at least 7 RISs instead of 5, showing benefits from selective cooperation and spatially distributed sensing points (RISs in our case).

These results can be leveraged to feed proactive sensing-based handover mechanisms (See Sec. 6.1). Besides estimation and algorithmic considerations, protocol design and resource allocation problems related to the proposed RIS-aided sensing approach have also been addressed, as reported in D4.1 [6GDISACD41].

Foreseen extensions to this work will aim at enhancing even further the RIS-wise detection performance through selective cooperation, for instance by considering conditional theoretical performance bounds as a potential selection tool. Furthermore, both the presence of multiple passive obstacles and the sensitivity of the cooperative localisation scheme with respect to the power dynamics caused by mobile and/or intermittent non-coherent sources will be investigated. Additionally, sensing capabilities under different resource allocation scenarios should also be evaluated to design efficient ISAC protocols, as mentioned in D4.1 [6GDISACD41].

Figure 5-21: Empirical CDF of blocker’s estimated position error when cooperating at least 5 (a) or 7 RISs (b) with different SSIM-based pre-processing strategies (i.e., outliers rejection and/or measurements weighting).

Related Dissemination

T.-T. Luc, et al. “Distributed RIS-Based Sensing of Mobile Passive Obstacles in Dense mmWave Networks,” accepted to EUSIPCO’25.

5.2.4 Contribution #B-11: Large-scale/Long-term Targets Tracking based on Cooperative Sensing Nodes

Motivations and Challenges

Sensing of passive targets and connected users is a crucial function of ISAC in 6G networks. Due to the large antenna arrays and large bandwidth, 6G systems can support high accuracy sensing and applications by providing high-resolution estimation of delay and angle parameters [LHL+22], [LCM+22]. When considering moving targets, sensing naturally becomes the problem of tracking. However, a single 6G BS can only track targets within its own FoV, which is usually limited, making long-term, large-scale tracking infeasible without cooperation among BSs. To address this, the concept of DISAC extends ISAC functionality by enabling BSs to collaboratively track targets through shared trajectory information among each other [SAG+24], [TD23]. DISAC can provide better coverage and tracking performance, compared with decentralised environments. However, the development of efficient, low-overhead algorithms for seamless handover and data exchange between BSs remains major research challenge [KCL+19].

Deployment Scenario

The considered scenarios are decentralised systems which enable large-scale deployments. Sensing service requirements specify sensing service area which defines the area of interest for the deployment scenario. Each BS can perform monostatic sensing to track the moving targets in its field of view, and all BSs can share necessary tracking information with each other (See Figure 5-22). The BSs’ orientations and positions are fixed and known, and all BSs know the deployment information and the FoVs of all the other BSs.

Figure 5-22: Example of the considered scenario. Targets move over time, and each BS can only observe those within its own FoV. Each BS independently processes its local observations to track the targets, then shares the tracked trajectories with neighbouring BSs (i.e., with overlapping or adjacent FoV).

Proposed Approach and Followed Methodology

At each BS side, a high-resolution channel parameter estimator is performed to estimate the delays and angles from the received signals. Then each BS perform a trajectory Poisson multi-Bernoulli mixture (TPMBM) filter to track the moving target in its field of view given those estimated delays and angles, and BSs share the necessary trajectory information of a target to the nearby BSs when the target is expected to enter the corresponding FoV.

Results and Discussion

In the simulated scenario, two BSs (BS1 and BS2) are positioned at opposite ends of a 100-meter line, and two targets move with constant velocities toward each other. Figure 5-23 presents the tracking results at BS2 using the TPMBM filter integrated with the target handover mechanism. The ground-truth and estimated trajectories of both targets are shown for comparison. Although clutter present throughout the simulation, the TPMBM tracking filter can accurately track the targets, thus it is stable to the clutter measurements. BS2 can track the Target2 until it leaves its FoV, as a partial trajectory of Target2 can be tracked, and the Target2 will be handed over to BS1. When Target1 enters the FoV of BS2, BS1 hands over the Target1 to BS2, by sending the tracked trajectory information to BS2. Then BS2 continue to target Target1, thus it can track the full trajectory of Target1 in the considered scenario. These results highlight that the proposed handover scheme ensures seamless trajectory continuation across BSs.

Figure 5-23: Tracking results from the TPMBM filter that integrates the target handover method at BS2.

Related Dissemination

Y. Ge, et al. "Target Handover in Distributed Integrated Sensing and Communication," accepted to IEEE ICC 2025.

5.2.5 Contribution #B-12: Joint Detection and Localisation of Multiple Moving Targets in a Distributed Radar System

Motivations and Challenges

Distributed radar systems have attracted increasing attention in both civilian and military domains due to their resilience to jamming, wide field-of-view, and enhanced detection reliability

enabled by spatial diversity. These systems are particularly effective for fundamental radar functions such as target detection and localisation. However, traditional approaches often decouple detection and localisation into separate steps, sacrificing performance due to premature decision-making at local radars and resulting information loss. Recent advances advocate for joint detection and localisation (JDL) directly from raw echoes or log-likelihood ratio (LLR) data at a central FC, especially in scenarios with multiple moving targets [LWG+23]. Yet, JDL for such dynamic environments is highly challenging: it involves estimating unknown target numbers, positions, and velocities simultaneously, and suffers from computational complexity that scales exponentially with the number of targets. These difficulties demand new, scalable algorithms capable of sequentially detecting targets and mitigating inter-target interference without compromising estimation accuracy.

Deployment Scenario

The considered deployment scenario involves a distributed radar system consisting of multiple local radar stations, each capable of transmitting and receiving signals independently. These local stations share a common time reference and operate within the same spectrum. The system monitors multiple point-like moving targets within a two-dimensional Cartesian coordinate system. Each local station transmits orthogonal waveforms and gathers the reflected signals, which are processed to detect and localize the targets. The environment assumes no communication distortion between the local stations and the FC, allowing complete raw data transmission from local stations to the FC for centralised processing and decision-making (See Figure 5-24).

Figure 5-24: Illustration of a distributed radar system with N local stations and P moving targets. There exists a communication system without distortion, enabling the FC to flawlessly gather the complete raw data from each local station.

Proposed Approach and Followed Methodology

A low-complexity iterative algorithm is proposed to solve the JDL problem for multiple moving targets. Initially, a generalised information criterion (GIC)-based detector is derived to jointly detect targets and estimate their unknown parameters, including number, location, and velocity. To mitigate the high computational complexity of joint maximization, the problem is decomposed into several low-dimensional optimisation tasks. An extended successive-interference-cancellation (SIC) algorithm is then employed at the FC to iteratively extract targets one by one, eliminating their influence on subsequent detections. This approach allows simultaneous detection and parameter estimation at each iteration, significantly reducing computational load while maintaining high detection accuracy.

Results and Discussion

Figure 5-25 illustrates the performance of the proposed algorithm compared to two benchmarks -GLRT-CD and O-GLRT- across varying SNR levels. Subplot (a) shows that the proposed method achieves high detection probabilities, closely matching the ideal GLRT-CD and significantly outperforming O-GLRT, especially in low-SNR scenarios. Subplots (b) and (c) demonstrate that the RMSE in location and velocity estimates decreases as SNR increases, with the proposed algorithm again nearly matching the performance of GLRT-CD. Subplot (d) shows a similar trend for velocity direction estimation, where the angular error diminishes at higher SNR. Overall, the proposed algorithm delivers highly accurate detection and parameter estimation for multiple moving targets, maintaining robustness and efficiency even under challenging conditions.

Figure 5-25: Probability of detection and RMSE results of all targets versus SNR. (a) Probability of detection. (b) RMSE in the location estimate. (c) RMSE in the velocity estimate. (d) RMSE in the velocity direction estimate.

Related Dissemination

Y. Lai, et al. " Joint Detection and Localization with an Efficient Censoring Method for Distributed Radars under Communication Constraints." submitted to IEEE Transactions on Aerospace and Electronic Systems.

5.2.6 Contribution #B-13: mmWave Cellular Passive Drone Detection with Re-configurable Intelligent Surfaces

Motivation and Challenges

The increasing prevalence of drones in society has brought about new security concerns, particularly regarding their potential misuse in sensitive areas. Traditional detection methods, such as computer vision, acoustic arrays, and RF fingerprinting, face significant challenges in adverse conditions like fog, rain, or dust. Furthermore, these methods struggle with distinguishing

drones from other objects of similar shapes or sizes and are limited by low detection ranges due to severe signal propagation loss. These shortcomings necessitate the exploration of innovative approaches to enhance drone detection accuracy and reliability in outdoor environments. Leveraging advancements in cellular multiple-input multiple-output infrastructure and RIS offers a promising solution, as RIS can not only improve signal sensing but also serve as virtual nodes to enhance communication and detection capabilities.

However, integrating RIS with cellular MIMO systems for drone detection presents several challenges. Effective deployment of RIS requires addressing trade-offs between factors such as training beam overhead, radar cross-section enhancements, and overall detection performance. Furthermore, optimising the RIS configuration for passive drone detection involves tackling issues like LoS requirements and ensuring seamless operation in dynamic environments. Theoretical validation through simulations is critical to establishing the feasibility of this approach, as the application of RIS for drone detection is still in its nascent stages.

Deployment Scenario

The system model showcased in Figure 5-26, involves a cellular BS equipped with multiple antennas working in conjunction with a passive RIS to detect drones in outdoor environments. The RIS is strategically placed to act as a virtual reflector, enhancing the signal processing capabilities of the system by redirecting and optimising wireless signals. The system leverages the LoS communication path between the RIS and the BS to improve detection accuracy.

While this setup considers a single RIS-BS pair, the concept naturally extends to distributed deployments involving multiple RIS panels positioned across a monitored area. In a DISAC context, these distributed RISs could collaboratively form a passive sensing mesh to enhance detection coverage in complex environments.

Figure 5-26: Drone detection system with one MIMO BS, one RIS, and one UE, all located on the roof of a building.

Proposed Approach and Followed Methodology

The proposed system leverages a RIS, to enhance the detection capabilities of the BS without requiring active radar or extensive modifications to the network. The RIS is designed to redirect and shape the wireless signals, creating focused detection zones that improve sensitivity to drones. The system employs a generalised likelihood ratio test to identify the presence of drones based on changes in the received signal patterns. Such a passive sensing approach is particularly compatible with DISAC systems, where multiple spatially separated RIS-assisted nodes

could run local detection algorithms and share decisions or likelihoods to achieve distributed consensus or fusion-based tracking.

Results and Discussion

Integrating RIS with cellular MIMO systems significantly enhances drone detection accuracy compared to traditional MIMO systems. The use of RIS improves signal focusing and reliability, particularly in outdoor environments with challenging conditions. Key findings show that the number of RIS elements, optimised beam training configurations, and radar cross-section enhancements directly impact detection performance. Additionally, the RIS-augmented system reduces training and computational overhead, offering a cost-effective solution for drone detection. The system proves robust even in partially obstructed line-of-sight conditions, with theoretical and simulation results confirming its feasibility and scalability for real-world deployment in large-scale cellular networks. Most notably Figure 5-27 and Figure 5-28 demonstrate the effectiveness of RIS in enhancing drone detection. First, Figure 5-27 shows that the RIS-augmented system outperforms the RIS-free system by over 5 dB in detection probability, highlighting the benefit of RIS in improving detection accuracy. Figure 5-28 evaluates the impact of different RIS training beam designs, revealing that random and one-bit quantized beams outperform the discrete Fourier transform (DFT) design. This suggests that a flexible, randomized beamforming approach is more effective for drone detection than structured methods like DFT.

Related Dissemination

J. He, et al. "RIS-Augmented Millimeter-Wave MIMO Systems for Passive Drone Detection." IEEE PIMRC 2024.

5.2.7 Contribution #B-14: RF Imaging based on Physics-Informed Neural Networks and New Physical Models

Motivation and Challenges

Performing imaging over a large area based on the reception of RF signals is a fundamentally challenging problem even when multiple receiving nodes are at one's disposal [OOM+18]. The problem arises from the fact that the inverse mapping problem (i.e., the model from the signal observations to the object's positions and surfaces) is posed. Especially when typical wireless signal models are utilised, crude simplifications are made: the same signal measurement may well be generated by different object positions and shapes and the full geometry cannot be captured accurately by simple cascades of reflected paths. To this end, there is a need for physics-compliant, yet computationally tractable models whose parts may be enhanced by data-driven approaches that capture patterns of the objects under study [GHL+23].

Motivated by this idea, the approach here is to utilise state-of-the-art deep learning models to the purpose of combining structures that have proven efficient in the computer vision regime with novel components that address the characteristics of wireless signals. High-quality RF imaging is instrumental for multiple ISAC scenarios, since an overview of environmental surfaces provides important benefits. Namely, it may act complementary to target detection processes to provide information that can be used for environmental and channel sensing. In this perspective, imaging can be regarded as a pre-processing step in sensing-aided communications. Additionally, the learning approach over distributed signals could be extended to incorporate ISAC signals, if relevant data become available.

Deployment Scenario

Consider a distributed setup where an STx illuminates via known RF signals the Area of Investigation (Aoi), that may contain multiple metallic solid objects of arbitrary shapes. Distributed SRxs are assumed to be placed in the boundaries of the area, as shown in Figure 5-29, which collect the reflected and diffracted signals and send it to the central SePF/SeMF.

Figure 5-27: Probability of detection performance with and without using an RIS.

Figure 5-28: Probability of detection performance with different kinds of RIS training beam designs.

Proposed Approach and Followed Methodology

The first part of the methodology is to derive an approximate, yet fast model for the propagation of the wireless signal that captures the surface-to-surface interactions as well as the shapes of the objects. To that end, a simplified version of Maxwell Equations based on the electric field integral equations was derived that can approximate the forward (objects-to-signal) model. A neural network is then trained on multiple data instances to approximate certain components of that model, which can be used to derive the inverse model. Once obtained, the inverse model can be used to perform the imaging process. The proposed DNN architecture (detailed in Figure 5-30) consists of three parts. First, a graph-attention module is used for feature extraction. The imposed graph structure allows for the incorporation of systemic and geometric information (that remains fixed throughout the data set) as node and edge features, while the attention mechanism is tasked to learn correlations between the electric field of each data instance inputs and those system variables. Next, typical five ResNet blocks are applied to the output of the graph-attention module with the intention of capturing information about the location, size, and shape of the objects, resulting in an intermediate image. This is finally processed by a UNet of three downsampling-upsampling layers. The purpose of the U-Net is to efficiently encode information about the shapes of the objects in the image during downsampling to a bottleneck vector, by

increasing the channel and decreasing the image dimensions. The converse procedure of the upsampling layers is designed to decode this information toward assigning each pixel of the image to its corresponding object (or background).

Figure 5-29: Example of the electric field intensity over the area of investigation when three solid metallic objects are randomly positioned. The transmitting node is positioned far away to the right side of the area while receivers are assumed to be located onto the edge of the area.

Figure 5-30: Proposed “GAT-Res-UNet” network architecture for RF imaging consisting of a Graph-Attention module for incorporation of system geometry, a ResNet for feature extraction, and a U-Net for the construction of images.

Results and Discussion

Two diverse data sets have been considered. The first data set creation consisted of placing a square and two circles into 10000 random configurations, while 64 SRxs were placed on a circle

surrounding the objects. The second set depicts 10000 handwritten digits, that are seen as solid metallic objects over the area of influence. The received signals were fed to a neural network that outputs a predicted image representation of the objects. The diameter (or main axis) of each object is slightly larger than the carrier wavelength and a single frequency harmonic tone has been used as the measuring signal. The network is trained by minimising the pixel-wise error between the pixels of the true image and those of the output image. Results for the shapes data set are visually illustrated in Figure 5-31. The proposed GAT-Res-UNet network is able to correctly identify the positions, dimensions, and general shape of the objects, but (sub-wave-length) details of their exact shapes are not discernible. This is attributed to the large number of pixels/sampling points of the appearing objects, which increases the network’s training overhead. Similarly, Figure 5-32 visualizes the reconstructed images of handwritten digits, where reconstruction of individual shapes is much more accurate. In fact, the network is able to uncover cavities without directly observing them and to mimic different writing styles. In all cases, the proposed architecture clearly outperforms the baseline networks. The accompanying numerical evaluation further demonstrates that the pixelwise reconstruction error is smaller for GAT-Res-UNet, which is also more robust in lower SNR and fewer antenna regimes. Future work will focus on integrating physics-based or signal-processing-derived methodologies as components of the neural network to enhance its precision. Nevertheless, the fact that the neural network is able to output an approximate image with high computational speed and in simplified system requirements, offers a big proposition of value.

Figure 5-31: Visual comparison of the proposed GAT-Res-UNet architecture for RF imaging on a data set of circular and square objects.

Related Dissemination

K. Stylianopoulos, et al. "Graph-CNNs for RF imaging: Learning the electric field integral equations," accepted to EUSIPCO 2025.

5.2.8 Contribution #B-15: Digital Twin Aided Sensing

Motivations and Challenges

The use of AI and machine learning models have shown promise in addressing sensing tasks, but their effectiveness relies on access to large, labelled datasets [NGU25]. Collecting such datasets through real-world measurement campaigns is often costly, time-consuming, and highly specific to particular use cases or locations. Additionally, annotating real-world data for training purposes can be labour-intensive and prone to errors. Moreover, expecting a generalist model trained on a broad, non-site-specific dataset to generalise effectively to unseen scenarios

Figure 5-32: Visual comparison of the proposed GAT-Res-UNet architecture for RF imaging on a data set of handwritten digits seen as solid objects.

or locations is currently unrealistic and overly complex. Digital twins, which simulate real-world environments, offer a compelling alternative by enabling the generation of synthetic, labelled datasets at scale. These datasets can be customised for specific scenarios, significantly reducing the dependency on costly and time-consuming real-world data collection efforts. An additional advantage of such approaches is the increasing availability and accessibility of tools to define and simulate realistic environments. Modern 3D modelling tools are widely available, and affordable 3D scanning technologies, such as LiDAR, are becoming more common, even being embedded in consumer devices like smartphones. This makes it significantly easier to create and instantiate realistic 3D models of environments, reducing the effort required to define digital twins and enabling more efficient and scalable dataset generation. Nonetheless, several challenges persist, including ensuring that the radio propagation models within the digital twin are accurate enough to produce reliable training data and validating the performance of machine learning models trained on synthetic data to confirm their effectiveness in real-world deployments.

Deployment Scenario

At this initial stage, the deployment scenario under investigation is intentionally simplified to serve as a foundational step toward more complex and realistic use cases. The scenario involves, in simulation, a square room of 10m x 10m, where the objective is to locate up to three objects or persons positioned at varying locations within the room. The 10m x 10m room might also contain additional static elements such as walls, pillars, and other fixed structures

The setup consists of two fixed Tx/Rx antennas placed at opposite ends of the room, facing each other. The system operates at a frequency of 2.4 GHz.

If successful in this simplified setup, the methodology could be extended to more complex scenarios, such as larger industrial workshops or outdoor urban environments. These extensions could include additional complexities such as Tx/Rx mobility and distributed approaches involving multiple transmitters and receivers.

Proposed Approach and Followed Methodology

The proposed approach leverages a digital twin framework to generate synthetic datasets and train AI and machine learning models for sensing tasks. More concretely it consists in analysing

the Channel Impulse Response (CIR) to infer the positions of the objects. While the current simulations use the "perfect" CIR directly generated by the digital twin environment, the system is designed with the future goal of relying on CIRs estimated using communication-centric pilot symbols as done in a conventional communication system. This approach seeks to leverage the capabilities of communication systems to extract sensing information without requiring additional hardware or modifications (e.g., specific waveform, dedicated pilots for sensing, etc.).

The system is built on NVIDIA's open-source library Sionna [HCA+23], which provides a robust platform for 3D ray-tracing simulations of radio propagation. Sionna generates synthetic CIR data, paired with labelled features such as object positions. Its integration with TensorFlow [PNW19] facilitates seamless prototyping of machine learning models, leveraging Graphics Processing Unit (GPU) acceleration for efficient simulations and training. However, Sionna is not used "out of the box"—additional tools and features have been developed to enhance its capabilities, such as dynamic scene management for evolving scenarios and improved dataset generation workflows.

In parallel, a custom TensorFlow-based machine learning pipeline has been developed to train and evaluate models. This pipeline integrates TensorBoard for real-time monitoring and visualisation of training metrics, enabling efficient debugging and optimisation of model architectures and training algorithms. The pipeline aims to ease experimentation with various machine learning architectures, hyperparameter tuning, and dataset configurations, providing a flexible framework for testing and refining sensing models.

The current methodology focuses on a simplified scenario involving a 10m x 10m square room with two fixed antennas, operating at 2.4 GHz. Synthetic CIR data is generated for up to three objects at varying positions in the room. While the simulations currently rely on "perfect" CIR data directly generated by the digital twin, the goal is to use CIRs estimated from pilot symbols as in a conventional communication system.

The immediate objective is to train models that can map CIR data to object positions, with a focus on developing generalisation capabilities beyond simple overfitting to the dataset. If successful in this simplified setup, the methodology could be extended to more complex scenarios, such as larger industrial workshops or outdoor smart city environments. These extensions may include dynamic elements like Tx/Rx mobility, distributed sensing with multiple transmitters and receivers, and the integration of advanced features such as beamforming.

Results and Discussion

Initial experiments provide insights into the feasibility of using digital twins to train machine learning models for sensing tasks. In the simplest scenario, where a single object is present in the environment, the models are able to fit the training data effectively. This is expected, as the dataset is exhaustive, containing examples of all possible object positions. While this demonstrates that the pipeline and methodology are functional, it does not yet confirm the ability of the models to generalise or perform robustly in more complex scenarios.

As the number of objects in the scene increases, the complexity of the problem grows significantly. The combinatorial explosion of possible object positions makes it impractical to generate exhaustive datasets. In these cases, the models face challenges in learning to generalise beyond the training data.

A key result of this work is the successful development of a complete and functional pipeline, from synthetic data generation using the digital twin to machine learning model training and evaluation. While the current models are not yet robust, having this end-to-end framework in place provides the necessary tools for future studies.

Figure 5-33 showcases three prediction examples from our early results. The leftmost column shows a 3D visualisation of the scene, where Tx/Rx antennas are depicted as coloured spheres, with the actual person shown in blue and the predicted position in red. The second column

displays the measured channel impulse response between the emitter and receiver, which serves as the model's input. The third column presents the ground truth heatmap, representing the expected output used during supervised training. The rightmost column shows the model's predicted position heatmap based on the given channel impulse response. In areas with blind spots, the model displays a uniform probability distribution for position prediction within that blind-spot area, which is expected due to the lack of actionable data. However, in non-blind spots, the model demonstrates significantly higher prediction accuracy.

Figure 5-33: Example of position heatmap predictions within the proposed machine learning pipeline.

Related Dissemination

While no formal publications have been produced at this stage, a currently under review Pull Request has been submitted to the open-source Sionna library, contributing additional tools and features for dynamic scene management and asset placement. Pull request available at: <https://github.com/NVlabs/sionna/pull/536>.

6 Sensing-Aided Communications

Among the many services that DISAC is expected to support based on a unique wireless system, data communication is one of the most prominent. This is especially true when sensing shares the exact same resources as the communication application, which is often the case when ISAC is implemented on existing communication infrastructure. The information collected from DISAC sensing and positioning is valuable for physical layer communication, given the close relation between the propagation channel and these physical and geometric entities. Nevertheless, as radio resources allocated to sensing reduce the available resources for communication, sensing-aided communication does not come for free and there are inherent trade-offs to be considered. This section explores several aspects of sensing-aided communication:

- Sensing-aided dynamic handover management (Sec. 6.1).

- Sensing-aided full-duplex communication (Sec. 6.2).
- Sensing-aided beamforming and beam tracking (Sec. 6.3).

Table 6-1 summarizes the main parameters of the proposed technical proposals.

Table 6-1: Overview of 6G-DISAC contributions on sensing-aided communication.

	Cont. #C-1: Sensing-aided Handover Triggering Policy in Dense mmWave Networks	Cont. #C-2: Simultaneous Near-Field Communications and Guaranteed Sensing with Full Duplex Radios	Cont. #C-3: Near Field Beam Tracking and Sensing Aided Beamforming using Dynamic Metasurface Antennas
Physical Deployment			
Nb, types and mobility regimes of TX nodes	At least 2 static BSs (if DL communications) 1 static UE (if UL communications)	1 (can be extended), Multi-antenna, stationary	1 (can be extended), Single antenna, random movement following Bezier trajectories.
Nb, types and mobility regimes of RX nodes	1 static UE (if DL communications) At least 2 static BSs (if UL communications)	1 (can be extended), Multi-antenna, stationary	1 Multi-antenna BS, static.
Nb, type and mobility regime of Passive Objects	At least 1 moving obstacle	n/a	n/a
Nb, types and mobility regimes of RISs	n/a	n/a	n/a
Environment			
Indoor/outdoor	Agnostic (but typically relevant to industrial indoor)	Outdoor	Outdoor
LoS/NLoS conditions	Both (transient shadowing caused by the moving obstacle)	LoS	Dominant LoS link and NLoS links from scatterers in the environment.
Radio Set-up			
Uplink/Downlink/Full-Duplex	Downlink/Uplink	Full-Duplex	Uplink
Tested frequency (mostly for evaluations when specified)	mmWave (typically in 5G-NR FR2 or FR3)	120 GHz	30 GHz
Bandwidth	n/a	150 KHz	Narrowband
Near-field/Far-field regime	n/a	Near-Field	Near-field
Time synchronisation requirements	Standard 5G-NR requirements for communications	None	None
Phase coherence requirements	Standard 5G-NR requirements for communications	None	None
Localisation and/or Sensing Operations (if any)			
Type of radio measurements at distributed sensing points	n/a (Sensing data used as input, regardless of its source)	Elevation, azimuth angles, distance	Estimation of UE's position.
Entity collecting the radio measurements (for fusion)	n/a (Sensing data used as input, regardless of its source)	n/a	n/a
Data Communications (if any)			

Type and traffic of conveyed information (ex. data format, refresh. rate...)	Application-dependent (typically critical control data if DL or machine/sensor type data if UL in industrial applications)	Modulated data	Modulated data
QoS requirements	Application-dependent	None	None
Transmission range/coverage requirements	A few 10s of meters at most (P2P)	None	None
Throughput requirements	Application-dependent	None	None
Spectral efficiency requirements	None	None	None
Goal-oriented requirements	None	None	None

6.1 Sensing-/Location-aided Dynamic Handover Management

Contribution #C-1: Sensing-aided Handover Triggering Policy in Dense mmWave Networks

Motivations and Challenges

The management of radio obstructions in an anticipated and proactive way is of primary importance into mmWave networks. Considering the cost of performing handover (HO) (incl. the time to make the decision and the duration to initiate the handover process itself), one open challenge consists in triggering HO events only if necessary, so as to maximize the network sum-rate, while limiting the average HO frequency, and hence ultimately, limiting the overhead cost with respect to data communications. Unlike standard HO solutions simply based on instantaneous DL SINR measurements with respect to distinct BSs or at most, on current UE positions, the possibility to jointly rely on predicted positions, directions, and velocities of both UEs and mobile blockers at large scales in the DISAC context is expected to enable more efficient HO mechanisms.

Leveraging sensing approaches adapted to dense mmWave wireless networks, such as that proposed in [SDD23], in Sec. 5.2.2 [DSD24], or in Sec. 5.2.3, it is proposed here to evaluate and compare basic sensing-aided HO triggering policies to highlight the benefits from cooperation and distributed approaches.

Deployment Scenario

Assuming the same kind of mmWave network deployment as that in [SDD23], we consider a reference UE u_0 communicating in DL with its serving base station b_0 (i.e., after initial association), with at least an alternative BS b_1 in range, with respect to whom a HO procedure could be triggered. Besides, one mobile obstacle is moving in the direction of the BS-UE link to protect. Without loss of generality, the reference BS is assumed to be the sensing node, thus providing angular information (i.e., sector) [SDD23] or positional (i.e., 2D Cartesian coordinates) [DSD24] information regarding the presence of the mobile blocker, if detected (See Figure 6-1).

In a typical industrial environment, the connected UE could for instance be associated with a controlled mobile device (e.g., a handheld tool) or a static equipment, while the passive blocker could be a non-connected forklift truck, an AGV, etc.

Proposed Approach and Followed Methodology

We consider two main sensing-aided HO triggering strategies, as follows.

The first HO triggering decision does not require cooperation. It is based on the definition of a BS-centric *risky sector*. A protection *angular observation window* θ_0 is set around the reference link $u_0 \rightarrow b_0$ to be protected from obstructions, centered around the sensing BS. Then, the angular position (i.e., the angular sector $\psi_B(t)$ of the mobile blocker) is estimated with respect to the serving BS, typically applying techniques like in [SDD23]. For a predefined time window τ , the angular “direction” of the blocker according to the local BS reference is estimated using previous logs $\psi_B(-\tau + t : t)$. Finally, a HO procedure is decided if the current angular position lies in the protection window, that is $\psi_B(t) \in [-\theta_0, \theta_0]$, and the mobile blocker is detected to be heading “towards” $u_0 \rightarrow b_0$ (according to BS reference). Obviously, this first strategy can benefit from further refinement, particularly by incorporating the range information. Indeed, a blocker that lies within the risky angular sector but located beyond the UE (radially) may not cause any link obstruction. Conversely, a closer blocker slightly outside the angular sector might pose a stronger risk. Considering both angle and range (e.g., through polar coordinates or predictive modelling of blocker trajectories) is hence expected to improve the robustness of the HO decision process, which is the basis of the second strategy following below.

Figure 6-1: Deployment scenario considered for the evaluation of sensing-aided HO decisions based on the definition of a risky angular sector (a) or 2D region (b), with one reference DL to protect from a mobile blocker between a sensing BS and its served UE, and another spare BS in range from the UE (for possible HO triggering).

The second HO triggering decision relies on cooperation, as well as on the definition of a BS-centric *risky region* (rather than a *risky sector*). A protection *angular observation window* θ_0 and a protection distance d_0 are defined around the typical link $u_0 \rightarrow b_0$ to be protected from obstructions, both centered around the sensing BS. Then, the relative 2D position (i.e., the angle $\psi'_B(t)$ and the range $d_B(t)$) of the mobile blocker is estimated with respect to the serving BS, typically applying techniques like in [DSD24]. For a predefined time window τ , the angular “direction” of the blocker according to the local BS reference is estimated using previous logs $\psi'_B(-\tau + t : t)$. Finally, a HO procedure is decided if the current angular position lies in the protection window, that is $\psi'_B(t) \in [-\theta_0, \theta_0]$, its current range is lower than the protection distance, that is $d_B(t) \leq d_0$, and the blockage is heading “towards” $u_0 \rightarrow b_0$ (still according to BS reference).

The first HO strategy above simply needs the blocker’s coarse angle and angular direction as primary “sensing” input data (e.g., from 1 sensing node, which is typically collocated with the serving BS here). Accordingly, it enjoys lower complexity and lower signaling overhead but it is expected to suffer from more frequent false alarms as the blocker may cross the sector without

blocking the link. The second HO strategy benefits from the detected blocker’s 2D position (converted into both an angle and a distance, relatively to the serving BS) and heading, as main sensing input data (e.g., through distributed positioning with multiple sensing nodes [DSD24]).

Results and Discussion

To assess the impact of sensing on the performance of the HO strategies above, we consider a scenario with multiple BSs and UEs randomly distributed on a disk of radius $R = 100$ m according to homogeneous Poisson Point Processes (PPPs) with densities equal to $8 \times 10^{-4} \text{ m}^{-2}$ and $2 \times 10^{-3} \text{ m}^{-2}$ respectively. Each UE is initially associated to its closest BS, while a mobile blocker is moving at moderate speed from 1 to 3 $\text{m} \cdot \text{s}^{-1}$, intermittently obstructing radio links.

Two main performance indicators are evaluated, namely the *prediction accuracy* on the one hand, which is defined as the ratio between the number of correct decisions over the number of made decisions, and the so-called *F1-score* on the other hand, which provides a balanced measure of performance by combining precision and recall (i.e, sensitivity), where the former quantifies the accuracy of positive predictions (i.e., the ratio between the number of true positives and the number of detected blockages), while the latter quantifies the ability to predict all blockages (i.e., the ratio between the number of true positives and the number of true blockages). Figure 6-2 illustrates the evaluation of these two indicators as a function of the blocker size, when HO decisions are made based on non-cooperative and cooperative sensing information (i.e., considering *risky sectors* and *risky 2D regions* respectively, for the protection of communication links). In Figure 6-2 – (a), it is thus seen that a larger blocker’s size results in better detectability first. However, beyond a critical size (in comparison with the angular sector resolution), the blocker is detected in multiple sensing sectors at the same time, thus causing larger angular uncertainty and false alarms accordingly. Conversely, Figure 6-2 - (b) shows how cooperative sensing enables both better detectability and accuracy, while limiting false alarms.

Figure 6-2: Evaluation of sensing-based HO decisions making (expressed in terms of probability, along the y-axis) in a dense mmWave network as a function of the blocker size, without (a) or with (b) cooperation, according to sensing algorithms from [SDD23] and [DSD24] respectively.

Future works will consider the use of obstruction predictions up to arbitrary longer time horizons, along with their related uncertainty, to anticipate even better the HO decisions. On this occasion, end-to-end performance evaluations will also be conducted to highlight the actual impact on data communications, aiming at optimising the HO frequency and overall throughput (i.e., beyond triggering events themselves).

Related Dissemination

The results of this contribution are under preparation for a paper submission.

6.2 Sensing-/Location-aided Full-Duplex Communications

Contribution #C-2: Simultaneous Near-Field Communications and Guaranteed Sensing with Full Duplex Radios

Motivations and Challenges

ISAC is poised to play a crucial role in future 6G networks, especially in the THz frequency range, where ultra-high data rates and precise sensing capabilities are essential. Current ISAC approaches often treat communication and sensing separately, leading to suboptimal performance. This contribution aims to bridge that gap by leveraging full-duplex (FD) eXtremely Large (XL) MIMO transceivers with DMAs to enable simultaneous near-field THz communications and sensing. The key challenge is to mitigate self-interference (SI) in full-duplex operation while optimising both sum-rate for communication and accuracy for target localisation. By formulating a novel joint optimisation framework, we seek to maximize the sum-communication rate while ensuring precise 3D target positioning.

Deployment Scenario

The deployment scenario as shown in Figure 6-3 considers a FD XL-MIMO node operating at THz frequencies, equipped with DMAs for both transmission and reception. The FD node is designed for simultaneous communications and sensing in the near-field environment, where it serves multiple user equipment (UEs) while also detecting and localizing multiple targets via backscattered signals. The UEs and targets are assumed to be in close proximity, within the Fresnel region, enabling high-resolution spatial sensing. The node transmits data to a subset of UEs while simultaneously estimating the 3D positions (range, azimuth, and elevation angle) of nearby targets. The DMA-based transmit and receive panels dynamically adjust beamforming for optimal signal transmission and reception, while adjusting analog beamforming for self-interference cancellation.

Figure 6-3: The considered FD massive MIMO system for simultaneous data transmission and mono-static sensing. The FD massive MIMO node jointly optimises its hybrid analog and digital Tx BF, analog Rx combining, and digital SI cancellation for the intended ISAC operation.

Proposed Approach and Followed Methodology

The methodology follows a two-step optimisation framework: first, it separately optimises the system for communication (maximising downlink sum-rate) and sensing (minimising PEB for accurate target localisation); then, it combines these designs to achieve an ISAC trade-off. The

approach involves precoder and combiner optimisation, SI mitigation, and beamforming adaptation to enhance both data transmission and spatial sensing. A CRB analysis is introduced to improve localisation accuracy, while an efficient sub-optimal alternating optimisation technique is used to handle the non-convex problem, balancing computational efficiency and ISAC performance.

Results and Discussion

The simulation results validate the effectiveness of the proposed FD XL MIMO ISAC system, demonstrating a strong trade-off between communication sum-rate and sensing accuracy. The key findings, illustrated in Figure 6-4, show that as transmit power increases, the target localisation accuracy improves, with the RMSE closely approaching the PEB, confirming efficient SI

Figure 6-4: Sensing (a) and communication (b) performance for $K=3$ targets, $U=2$ of which being UEs, versus the transmit power with the proposed FD-enabled XL-MIMO ISAC scheme for the case where $N_{RF}=4$ TX/RX microstrips, each with $N_E=4$ metamaterials.

cancellation. Meanwhile, the downlink sum-rate improves significantly with higher power, showcasing the system's ability to support high data rates while maintaining accurate target localisation. Comparisons with a benchmark ISAC scheme from prior work show that the proposed approach provides greater flexibility in optimising communication and sensing trade-offs, outperforming previous methods in both localisation precision and achievable data rates.

Related Dissemination

I. Gavras and G. C. Alexandropoulos, "Simultaneous near-field THz communications and sensing with full duplex metasurface transceivers," IEEE SPAWC 2024.

6.3 Sensing-/Location-aided Beamforming and Beam Tracking

Contribution #C-3: Near Field Beam Tracking and Sensing Aided Beamforming using Dynamic Metasurface Antennas

Motivation and Challenges

To meet the ultra-low latency and Tbps data rates envisioned in 6G, high-frequency bands are essential due to their vast bandwidth. However, severe path losses at these frequencies necessitate large antenna apertures and highly directive beams, naturally leading to near-field regimes where wavefront curvature can no longer be ignored. One question that arises is how frequent channel knowledge (and with what accuracy) is needed, in order to follow a moving target with highly directive beams without losing focus, i.e., losing transmitting gain? To that end, in this work we aim to answer the latter question and propose a beam tracking framework capitalising on the proposed analysis and develop a codebook-based channel estimation scheme.

The employed methodology allows for dynamic use of sensing resources by performing target searching at progressively smaller spatial regions and time intervals. As a result, it can enhance the overall efficiency of (D)ISAC operations.

Deployment Scenario

We consider a DMA-enabled BS transceiver, wishing to communicate in the DL with a single antenna UE which randomly moves in a plane vertical to the former, with a constant height difference as shown in Figure 6-5. The DMA comprises phase-tunable metamaterial elements, which are grouped into microstrips: each microstrip includes metamaterials, and is connected to a single RF chain.

Proposed Approach and Followed Methodology

It is assumed that the BS only knows the UE's position at each time instant and thus applies beam-focusing on that direction. Considering the limitations of the hybrid design of DMAs, one first idea is to obtain the optimal beamformer and the achievable gain at the focused position. Then an analytical function is derived, which expresses the beamforming losses due to potential errors in the UE's position, that is, the mismatch between the focusing position and the actual UE's position.

Using this model, spatial limits are determined, along range and azimuth, within which the gain remains above a specified fraction of the optimum. These limits are given either with respect to range or azimuth spatial coordinates (an example is shown in Figure 6-6). It can be seen that the range intervals are asymmetric: when the UE moves toward the DMA, the focus depth is shorter due to stronger near-field effects compared to movement away.

Next, the worst-case direction of UE movement is analysed, deriving the direction along which the beamforming gain deteriorates the fastest. From this, a closed-form expression is obtained for the minimum distance required to reduce the gain below a target level. Combined with the UE's velocity, this gives the beam coherence time T_C , i.e., the minimum time needed for the UE

to experience this loss, which will serve as the reconfigurable time interval between pilot signaling from the UE. Then the reconfigurable sampling resolution is defined for UE position estimation, framing localisation as a beamforming gain objective. That is, position estimates should be accurate enough to maintain the gain above a desired threshold (as a fraction of the optimal gain). Based on this, a dynamic non-uniform grid is created, which samples a disc centred around a given point with reconfigurable resolution, so that the maximum gain loss due to the discretisation does not exceed the specified limit (see Figure 6-6).

Figure 6-5: The considered system model comprising a static BS equipped with a DMA of an extremely large number of metamaterials, lying in the xz -plane and a mobile single-antenna UE moving inside the xy -plane.

Building on the above, a beam tracking framework is introduced, based on a proactive QoS-aware communication protocol. Given the derived beam coherence time, the BS can adaptively request pilot signals to ensure the beamforming gain remains above a desired threshold. This threshold can be tuned according to the UE's QoS requirements, allowing for reconfigurable update intervals. As a result, dense pilot signalling is triggered when the UE is near the BS, where the gain is highly sensitive to position errors, while sparser updates suffice when the UE is farther away. At each interval, the last estimated position serves as the centre of a polar sampling disc, with its radius scaled by an estimate of the UE's velocity norm. This strategy ensures robust performance without relying on per-slot channel estimation.

Results and Discussion

We demonstrate the performance of our proposed tracking framework via simulations, with random Bezier trajectories, since they are known to realistically depict trajectories of moving objects and are widely used for smooth path generation. We consider perfect prior knowledge of the initial position of the UE before beginning the tracking algorithm.

From Figure 6-7, the stability in beamforming gain achieved for random trajectories throughout time further validates the preceding analysis. Furthermore, by employing this reconfigurable estimation interval T_c the percentage of gain achieved is always greater than the specified

threshold within the 95th percentile of the trajectory data points. Finally, as anticipated, the re-configurable time intervals decrease when increasing the percentage threshold that we impose, since denser estimations are needed over time to satisfy a stricter constraint.

Figure 6-6: Dynamic non-uniform grid for UE localisation. The proposed non-uniform sampling process for a circular area of interest with central point at the polar coordinates $r = 70$ m and $\Phi = \pi / 4$, resolution $\delta\% = 80$ % and radius $c = 30$ m. It is also observed that Δr increases with increasing r .

Figure 6-7: Left vertical axis: average percentage of optimum gain achieved and 95th percentile error bar, over time with 500 μ s time step. Right vertical axis: average estimation time interval. Both are plotted versus the different QoS constraints.

Related Dissemination

P. Gavrilidis and G. C. Alexandropoulos, "Near-Field Beam Tracking with Extremely Large Dynamic Metasurface Antennas," IEEE Transactions on Wireless Communications.

7 Conclusion

In this deliverable, we have presented initial developments and results achieved in the frame of 6G-DISAC WP3, which specifically aim at addressing the radio PHY of future distributed ISAC systems. These contributions comprise 5 methods regarding the optimisation of PHY parameters, waveform shaping, and network deployment, as a support to both communication and sensing functionalities, but also 15 algorithmic solutions enabling the detection, localisation, and tracking of both connected UEs and passive objects such as scattering points or moving obstacles (or optimising the related system parameters for these purposes), and finally, 3 sensing-aided communication schemes leveraging the acquired sensing data.

While a large number of these contributions are by design intended for distributed network settings and multistatic scenarios, a few other proposals are more generic, agnostic with respect to both the network architecture and processing segmentation, and/or more focused on specific low-level PHY aspects (i.e., remaining at link level). However, the latter would still remain applicable in distributed and/or multistatic contexts too.

The main achievements and findings reported in this deliverable can be summarised as follows:

- A new waveform has been designed, providing robust trade-offs between energy consumption and spectral efficiency and offering programmable control via Walsh order selection at inference time. This solution provides finer support to semantic symbol mapping with high diversity and deterministic orthogonality (over conventional fixed-grid OFDM), making it particularly relevant in the context of sensing data communications.
- A machine learning-based approach has been proposed to optimise RIS profiles in the context of localisation and sensing, using mixed Gaussian distributions to model the UE state uncertainty. The corresponding neural network is trained to output both the optimal RIS profile and an updated state representation for each UE, bringing a robust solution for RIS optimisation in dynamic and/or obstructed scenarios.
- A comprehensive beam modelling and calibration method has been put forward, which effectively incorporates realistic hardware imperfections and measurement uncertainties, while achieving robust and high-accuracy RIS-aided localisation.
- A signalling scheme has been developed for secure ISAC systems utilising a dual-functional BS, which minimises the Bayesian CRB and leverages constructive interference to direct signals towards intended users while simultaneously reducing their decodability for potential eavesdroppers. This solution is shown to outperform conventional block-level precoding techniques (in terms of both lower symbol error rates at legitimate UEs and better immunity against eavesdropper attacks).
- A method integrating a multidimensional orthogonal matching pursuit algorithm has been proposed for joint channel estimation and localization/sensing in RIS-aided systems, enabling better estimation accuracy (typically, in sparse mmWave multipath channels). This solution relies on a dictionary learning stage to calibrate hardware impairments at the user array.
- Several low-complexity CFO and AoD estimators have been put forward in the context of multi-RIS accurate UE localisation and synchronisation, depending on whether the direct LoS exists or not between the BS and the UE. In addition, a detector has been designed to identify the presence of the LoS path and cast the estimation variant accordingly. The proposed approach is shown to demonstrate rapid convergence to theoretical bounds even under dense multipath.

- In the context of DL D-MIMO system, several algorithms have also been introduced to deal with the joint localisation and synchronisation problem framed as a maximum likelihood estimation problem, while aiming to estimate both the UE's 2D position and its phase offset.
- A three-step approach has been proposed to address the simultaneous localisation and mapping problem in distributed architectures supported by radio stripes, determining the phase offset of the UE using the carrier phase information from LoS paths first, then the UE's location and clock offset by combining LoS information with reflections from walls, and finally, the positions of scattering points through a null-space transformation technique providing fine multipath resolution.
- An optimisation solution has been proposed to determine the best analog beamforming weights at a Rx endowed with a dynamic metasurface array for near-field localisation, by relying on theoretical performance bounds, which is particularly suited to the THz frequency band.
- An original multi-step algorithmic framework has also been developed to address the indoor localisation of ultra low-complexity mobile IoT nodes with received power, based on both a mobile AGV-mounted RIS and fixed beacons.
- A dedicated AI RIS-enabled architecture has been proposed to determine the UE position and its uncertainty, but without interfering with the communication-oriented operations carried out in parallel at the surface.
- A novel approach has been proposed for multistatic sensing based on 5G NR signals, which utilises the PRS jointly with the DMRS for ambiguity removal, thus exhibiting fine accuracy thanks to the properties of both kinds of signals.
- In the context of dense mmWave networks, two cooperative sensing schemes have been described, relying on sectored antenna systems at sensing nodes or dual-beam reflective RISs, which both aim at monitoring the shadowing-based variations of the Rx power received from uncoordinated ambient sources, so as to opportunistically detect and localise a moving obstacle based.
- A target handover solution has been proposed, where each BS implements a trajectory Poisson multi-Bernoulli mixture filter to track the moving target in its field of view, given locally estimated delays and angles, while the different BSs share information to anticipate on the moment when the target is expected to enter their respective FoVs.
- A RIS-enabled system has been presented, which enhances the detection capabilities of a BS without requiring active radar or extensive modifications to the network. Accordingly, a RIS redirects and shapes the wireless signals to create focused detection zones and a generalised likelihood ratio test is applied to identify the presence of passive drones based on changes in the received signal patterns.
- A new data-driven imaging approach has been described, which first derives a simplified EM model accounting for the propagation of the wireless signal that captures both the surface-to-surface interactions as well as the shapes of the illuminated objects. A deep neural network is then trained to approximate certain key components of that model, which can be used to derive the inverse model at low complexity and ultimately, enables to perform imaging.
- A digital twin-based sensing methodology relying on deterministic ray-tracing simulations has also been provided, where synthetic channel impulse response data is first generated for up to three objects at varying positions in the room. This data is then used to train models that can map CIRs to these passive objects' positions, with a focus on generalisation capabilities.

- In the context of mmWave networks, several handover policies have also been evaluated, aiming at preventing from the obstruction of a BS-UE DL communication link caused by a passive mobile obstacle, given various kinds of sensing information as inputs (i.e., angular sector and/or relative distance and/or relative position with respect to a serving BS). The success of these handover decisions is evaluated, depending on the characteristics of the sensed moving obstacle (typically, velocity and size) and hence, on the underlying detection performances.
- In a Full Duplex massive MIMO context, a two-step optimisation framework has been designed, including precoder and combiner optimisation, SI mitigation, and beamforming adaptation. This method first separately optimises the DL communication sum-rate, then minimises the PEB for accurate target localisation, and finally combines the two approaches to achieve an ISAC trade-off.
- A location-based beam tracking framework has been proposed, including a proactive QoS-constrained communication protocol, where the BS evaluates the minimum time needed so that the beamforming gain drops by a certain percentage and asks for pilot signals subject to the UE's QoS constraints in a reconfigurable manner (e.g., triggering denser pilot signalling when the UE is close to the BS and the beamforming gain is more sensitive to position errors). This strategy is shown to offer more stable communications without the need for channel estimation at every time slot.

From the previous list, one can note the relatively large number of contributions regarding localisation and mapping algorithms from Sec. 5 (i.e., in comparison with the two other families of contributions in Sec. 4 and 6). This can be partly explained by the fact that related or side research questions have already been addressed, at least in part, for the last past years in the more general context of UEs localisation, while the two other domains remain comparatively less mature and more marginally explored so far. Accordingly, the localisation and mapping contributions provided in the new context on (D)ISAC could build on top of these recent research outcomes at an early stage in the 6G-DISAC project. It is however foreseen that the work on waveform design, sensing-aided communications, and communication-sensing operating trade-offs, will ramp up in the coming months to reach a climax before the end of the WP activities, while strengthening the interaction and cross-fertilisation between the respective tasks. In particular, while most of the sensing-aided communication approaches put forward so far in Sec. 6 still assume quite standard sensing information (as input) or are relatively agnostic with respect to the underlying sensing method it-self, it is hence expected that the recent advances reported in Sec. 5 as regards to localisation and sensing will be beneficial to the design of even more advanced and synergetic sensing-aided communication approaches in the upcoming period of activity in WP3. A quite similar remark holds also for waveform design for instance, as some of described contributions seem general enough to comply with multiple sensing methods.

Beyond intra-WP interactions, the contributions in this deliverable D3.1 have also a close connection to the work carried out in WP4. In particular, the described algorithmic approaches are intended to make use of proposed protocols from WP4. Depending on their system and objective details (e.g., sensing of passive objects, UE localisation, incorporation of RIS, semantic and ISAC waveform design, or federation and cooperative learning, etc.), different protocol variants have been defined on purpose in [6GDISAC-D41]. Resource allocation and orchestration schemes reported in the latter deliverable have also been designed so as to accommodate the distributed deployment of sensing-based algorithms from D3.1.

Finally, beyond continuing and extending these initial theoretical works on algorithmic design and simulation-based evaluations, WP3 is also committed to provide support to the experimental validations envisaged in WP5 by the end of the project. Accordingly, by the time this deliverable is written, a joint cross-WP initiative has been taken to start identifying and adapting some of the algorithmic proposals reported herein, as possible candidates for real-life proof-of-concept demonstrations under more realistic hardware capabilities and constraints. The results

of this selection and adaptation process will be accounted in the next deliverable D3.2. In addition to this new WP3 document, the interactions with WP5 will also be part of the material reported in deliverable D5.1 [6GDISAC-D51].

8 References

- [3GPP10] "Physical Channels and Modulation, Release 16, V16.2.0," 3GPP, Rep. 3GPP TS 36.211, 2010.
- [3GPP20] "Study on Channel Model for Frequencies from 0.5 to 100 GHz, V16.1.0," 3GPP, Rep. 3GPP TR 38.901, 2020.
- [6GDISAC-D22] Deliverable D2.2 "Preliminary Version of the Distributed ISAC Architecture", from HORIZON-JU-SNS-2023/6G-DISAC, December 2024.
- [6GDISAC-D41] Deliverable D4.1 "Initial Specifications for Protocols and Orchestration Solutions", from HORIZON-JU-SNS-2023/6G-DISAC, June 2025.
- [6GDISAC-D51] Deliverable D5.1 "Key Components and Integration", from HORIZON-JU-SNS-2023/6G-DISAC, June 2025.
- [ABM+22] M. Arnold, et al. "MaxRay: A Raytracing-Based Integrated Sensing and Communication Framework", Proc. IEEE International Symposium on Joint Communications & Sensing 2022 (IEE JC&S'22), Seefeld, March 2022.
- [ADH20] Z. Ali, et al. "Early Warning of mmWave Signal Blockage and AoA Transition Using sub-6 GHz Observations," in IEEE Communications Letters, vol. 24, no. 1, pp. 207-211, Jan. 2020.
- [AKK+21] Z. Abu-Shaban, K. Keykhosravi, M. F. Keskin, G. C. Alexandropoulos, G. Seco-Granados, and H. Wymeersch, "Near-Field Localisation with a Reconfigurable Intelligent Surface Acting as Lens," Proc. IEEE International Conference on Communications 2021 (IEEE ICC'21), Montreal, June 2021.
- [AMZ20] N. A. Abbasi, A. F. Molisch, and J. C. Zhang, "Measurement of Directionally Resolved Radar Cross Section of Human Body for 140 and 220 GHz Bands," Proc. IEEE Wireless Communications and Networking Conference 2020 Workshops (IEEE WCNC'20 Workshops), Seoul, April 2020.
- [ATL+20] F. Alsaleemz, J. S. Thompson, D. I. Laurenson, S. K. Podilchak, and C. A. Alistarh, "Small-Size Blockage Measurements and Modelling for mmWave Communications Systems," Proc. IEEE International Symposium on Personal Indoor Mobile Radio Communications 2020 (IEEE PIMRC'20), London, Aug.-Sept. 2020.
- [ATR23] A. Abrardo, A. Toccafondi, and M. Di Renzo, "Design of Reconfigurable Intelligent Surfaces by Using S-Parameter Multiport Network Theory—Optimization and Full-Wave Validation," in IEEE Transactions on Wireless Communications, vol. 23, no. 11, pp. 17084-17102, Nov. 2024.
- [AVM+23] A. Behravan et al., "Positioning and Sensing in 6G: Gaps, Challenges, and Opportunities," IEEE Vehicular Technology Magazine, vol. 18, no. 1, pp. 40–48, 2023.
- [BAL11] C. A. Balanis, Advanced Engineering Electromagnetics 2nd Edition. Hoboken, NJ, USA: John Wiley & Sons, Ltd, 2011.

- [BT21] A. B. Baral and M. Torlak. "Joint Doppler Frequency and Direction of Arrival Estimation for TDM MIMO Automotive Radars." *IEEE Journal of Selected Topics in Signal Processing*, vol. 15, no. 4, pp. 980-995, June 2021.
- [BWM+22] E. Björnson, H. Wymeersch, B. Matthiesen, P. Popovski, L. Sanguinetti, and E. De Carvalho, "Reconfigurable Intelligent Surfaces: A Signal Processing Perspective with Wireless Applications," *IEEE Signal Processing Magazine*, vol. 39, no. 2, pp. 135–158, 2022.
- [CAA+25] E. Calvanese Strinati, G. C. Alexandropoulos, N. Amani, M. Crozzoli, G. Madhusudan, S. Mekki, F. Rivet, et al. "Toward Distributed and Intelligent Integrated Sensing and Communications for 6g Networks," *IEEE Wireless Communications*, vol. 32, no. 1, pp. 60–67, 2025.
- [CKA+23] H. Chen, M. F. Keskin, S. R. Aghdam, H. Kim, S. Lindberg, A. Wolfgang, T. E. Abrudan, T. Eriksson, and H. Wymeersch, "Modelling and Analysis of OFDM-Based 5G/6G Localisation under Hardware Impairments," *IEEE Transactions on Wireless Communications*, vol. 23, no. 7, pp. 7319–7333, 2023.
- [CKA+24] H. Chen, H. Kim, M. Ammous, G. Seco-Granados, G. C. Alexandropoulos, S. Valaee, and H. Wymeersch. "RISs and Sidelink Communications in Smart Cities: The Key to Seamless Localisation and Sensing," *IEEE Communications Magazine*, vol. 61, no. 8, pp. 140-146, Aug. 2023.
- [COST2100] L. Liu, C. Oestges, J. Poutanen, et al., "The COST 2100 MIMO Channel Model," *IEEE Wireless Communications*, vol. 19, no. 6, pp. 92–99, Dec. 2012.
- [CR85] B. J. Cown and C. E. Ryan. "Near-Field Scattering Measurements for Determining Complex Target RCS," *IEEE Transactions on Antennas and Propagation*, vol. 37, no. 5, pp. 576-585, May 1989.
- [CSD+24] E. Calvanese-Strinati, et al "Goal-Oriented and Semantic Communication in 6G AI-Native Networks: The 6G-Goals Approach," *Proc. Joint European Conference on Networks and Communications & 6G Summit 2024 (EuCNC/6G Summit'24)*, Antwerp, June 2024.
- [CTT+16] X. Chen, L. Tian, P. Tang, J. Zhang, "Modelling of Human Body Shadowing Based on 28 GHz Indoor Measurement Results," *Proc. IEEE Vehicular Technology Conference – Fall 2016 (IEEE VTC-Fall'16)*, Montreal, Sept. 2016.
- [CWH+23] H. R. Chi, C. K. Wu, N.-F. Huang, K.-F. Tsang, and A. Radwan, "A Survey of Network Automation for Industrial Internet-of-Things Toward Industry 5.0," *IEEE Transactions on Industrial Informatics*, vol. 19, no. 2, pp. 2065-2077, Feb. 2023.
- [CZK+24] H. Chen, P. Zheng, M. F. Keskin, T. Al-Naffouri, and H. Wymeersch. "Multi-RIS-Enabled 3D Sidelink Positioning," *IEEE Transactions on Wireless Communications*, vol. 23, no. 8, pp. 8700-8716, Aug. 2024.
- [DLX+24] Z. Du, F. Liu, Y. Xiong, T. X. Han, Y. C. Eldar, and S. Jin, "Reshaping the ISAC Tradeoff under OFDM Signalling: A Probabilistic Constellation Shaping Approach," *IEEE Transactions on Signal Processing*, vol. 72, pp. 4782-4797, Sept. 2024.
- [DSD24] H. Dakdouk, M. Sana, and B. Denis, "Cooperative Sensing of Side Lobes Interference for Blockage Localisation and Mapping in Dense mmWave

- Networks," Proc. Joint European Conference on Networks and Communications 2024 & 6G Summit 2024 (EuCNC/6G Summit'24), Antwerp, June 2024.
- [EDR+25] G. Encinas-Lago, F. Devoti, M. Rossanese, V. Sciancalepore, M. Di Renzo, X. Costa-Pérez, "COLoRIS: Localisation-Agnostic Smart Surfaces Enabling Opportunistic ISAC in 6G Networks", IEEE Transactions on Mobile Computing, Early Access, March 2025.
- [EGG+21] A. Elzanaty, A. Guerra, F. Guidi, and M.-S. Alouini, "Reconfigurable Intelligent Surfaces for Localisation: Position and Orientation Error Bounds," IEEE Transactions on Signal Processing, vol. 69, pp. 5386-5402, Aug. 2021.
- [EII21] S. W. Ellingson, "Path Loss in Reconfigurable Intelligent Surface-Enabled Channels," Proc. IEEE International Symposium on Personal, Indoor and Mobile Radio Communications 2021 (IEEE PIMRC'21), Helsinki, Sept. 2021
- [FDK+25] A. Fascista, et al., "Joint Localisation, Synchronisation and Mapping via Phase-Coherent Distributed Arrays," IEEE Journal of Selected Topics in Signal Processing, vol. 19, no. 2, pp. 412-429, March 2025.
- [FKC+22] A. Fascista, M. F. Keskin, A. Coluccia, H. Wymeersch, and G. Seco-Granados, "RIS-Aided Joint Localisation and Synchronisation with a Single-Antenna Receiver: Beamforming Design and Low-Complexity Estimation," IEEE Journal of Selected Topics in Signal Processing, vol. 16, no. 5, pp. 1141-1156, Aug. 2022.
- [FMV+20] L. A. Fierro, E. C. Maggi, A. A. Vazquez, D. Schkolnik, "Empirical Results for Human-Induced Shadowing Events for Indoor 60 GHz Wireless Links," IEEE Access, vol. 8, pp. 44522-44533, March 2020.
- [FSA+23] R. Faqiri, C. Saigre-Tardif, G. C. Alexandropoulos, N. Shlezinger, M. F. Imani, and P. del Hougne, 'PhysFad: Physics-Based End-to-End Channel Modeling of RIS-Parametrized Environments With Adjustable Fading', IEEE Transactions on Wireless Communications, vol. 22, no. 1, pp. 580–595, 2023.
- [GDR21] G. Gradoni and M. Di Renzo, "End-to-End Mutual Coupling Aware Communication Model for Reconfigurable Intelligent Surfaces: An Electromagnetic-Compliant Approach Based on Mutual Impedances," in IEEE Wireless Communications Letters, vol. 10, no. 5, pp. 938-942, May 2021.
- [GGD+17] A. Guerra, et al., "A Millimeter-Wave Indoor Backscattering Channel Model for Environment Mapping," IEEE Transactions on Antennas and Propagation, vol. 65, no. 9, pp. 4935–40, 2017.
- [GHL+23] R. Guo, et al., "Physics-Embedded Machine Learning for Electromagnetic Data Imaging: Examining Three Ttypes of Data-Driven Imaging Methods," IEEE Signal Processing Magazine, vol. 40, no. 2, pp. 18-31, March 2023.
- [GMC+24] G. Gougeon, F. Munoz, Y. Corre, and R. D'Errico, "Ray-Tracing Calibration from Channel Sounding Measurements in a Millimeter-Wave Industrial Scenario," Proc. European Conference on Antennas and Propagation 2024 (EuCAP'24), Glasgow, 2024.
- [GQA+22] D. Gündüz, Z. Qin, I. E. Aguerri, H. S. Dhillon, Z. Yang, A. Yener, K. K. Wong, and C.-B. Chae, "Beyond Transmitting Bits: Context, Semantics,

- and Task-Oriented Communications," IEEE Journal on Selected Areas in Communications, vol. 41, no. 1, pp. 5–41, 2022.
- [GYB+19] T. Gu, et al. "Beamsniff: Enabling Seamless Communication under Mobility and Blockage in 60 GHz Networks," Proc. IFIP Networking Conference 2019, Warsaw, May 2019.
- [GZC24] R. Ghazalian, P. Zheng, H. Chen, C. Ozturk, M. F. Keskin, V. Sciancalepore, S. Gezici, T. Y. Al-Naffouri, and H. Wymeersch, "Calibration in RIS-aided Integrated Sensing, Localisation and Communication Systems," arXiv:2409.16931, Sept. 2024.
- [HCA+23] J. Hoydis, S. Cammerer, F. Ait Aoudia, A. Vem, N. Binder, G. Marcus, A. Keller, "Sionna: An Open-Source Library for Next-Generation Physical Layer Research," arXiv:2203.11854, March 2023.
- [HDC24] N. Hello, P. Di Lorenzo, and E. Calvanese-Strinati, "Semantic Communication Enhanced by Knowledge Graph Representation Learning," Proc. IEEE International Workshop on Signal Processing Advances in Wireless Communications 2024 (IEEE SPAWC'24), Lucca, Sept. 2024.
- [HEXAXXIID43] Deliverable D4.3 "Early results of 6G Radio Key Enablers" from HORIZON-JU-SNS-2023/Hexa-X-II, April 2024.
- [HHC+25] N. Hello, M. A. Hamoura, F. Costanzo, F. Rivet, and E. Calvanese Strinati, "Semantic Waveforms for AI-Native 6G Networks," submitted to IEEE International Workshop on Signal Processing and Artificial Intelligence for Wireless Communications 2025 (IEEE SPAWC'25), Surrey, July 2025.
- [HMC+24] N. Hello, M. Merluzzi, E. C. Strinati, and L. Sanguinetti, "Optimising RIS impairments through Semantic Communication," Proc. IEEE Global Communications Conference 2024 (IEEE GLOBECOM'24), Cape Town, Dec. 2024.
- [HMP22] R. Hersyandika, Y. Miao, and S. Pollin, "Guard Beam: Protecting mmWave Communication through In-Band Early Blockage Prediction," Proc. IEEE Global Communications Conference 2022 (IEEE GLOBECOM'22), Rio de Janeiro, Dec. 2022.
- [ITUR17] "Guidelines for Evaluation of Radio Interface Technologies for IMT-2020", Report ITU-R M.2412-0, Oct. 2017.
- [JRB+14] S. Jaeckel, L. Raschkowski, K. Börner, and L. Thiele, "QuaDRiGa: A 3-D Multi-Cell Channel Model with Time Evolution for Enabling Virtual Field Trials," IEEE Transactions on Antennas and Propagation, vol. 62, no. 6, pp. 3242-3256, June 2014.
- [KCK+23] H. Kim, H. Chen, M. F. Keskin, Y. Ge, K. Keykhosravi, G. C. Alexandropoulos, S. Kim, and H. Wymeersch, "RIS-enabled and Access-Point-Free Simultaneous Radio Localization and Mapping," IEEE Transactions on Wireless Communications, vol. 23, no. 4, pp. 3344-3360, 2023.
- [KCL+19] J. Kim, D. H. Cho, W. C. Lee, S. S. Park, and H. L. Choi, "Optimal Target Assignment with Seamless Handovers for Networked Radars," Sensors, is. 19, Oct. 2019.
- [KDA+23] K. Keykhosravi, B. Denis, G. C. Alexandropoulos, Z. S. He, A. Albanese, V. Sciancalepore, and Henk Wymeersch, "Leveraging RIS-Enabled Smart

- Signal Propagation for Solving Infeasible Localisation Problems: Scenarios, Key Research Directions, and Open Challenges," IEEE Vehicular Technology Magazine, vol. 18, no. 2, pp. 20-28, Feb. 2023.
- [KJM+22] M. F. Keskin, F. Jiang, F. Munier, G. Seco-Granados, and H. Wymeersch, "Optimal Spatial Signal Design for mmWave Positioning under Imperfect Synchronisation," IEEE Transactions on Vehicular Technology, vol. 71, no. 5, pp. 5558-5563, May 2022.
- [KKS+21] K. Keykhosravi, M. F. Keskin, G. Seco-Granados, and Henk Wymeersch, "SISO RIS-Enabled Joint 3D Downlink Localisation and Synchronisation," Proc. IEEE International Conference on Communications 2021 (IEEE ICC'21), Montreal, June 2021.
- [KMH21] P. Kumari, et al., "JCR70: A Low-Complexity Millimeter-Wave Proof-of-Concept Platform for a Fully-Digital SIMO Joint Communication-Radar," IEEE Open Journal on Vehicular Technology, vol. 2, pp. 218–34, 2021.
- [LAH19] J. Li, B. Ai, R. He et al., "On 3D Cluster-Based Channel Modelling for Large-Scale Array Communications," IEEE Transactions on Wireless Communications, vol. 18, no. 10, pp. 4902–4914, Oct. 2019.
- [LBB+21] C. D. Lima, D. Belot, R. Berkvens, et al., "Convergent Communication, Sensing and Localization in 6G Systems: An overview of Technologies, Opportunities and Challenges." IEEE Access, vol. 9, pp. 26902-26925, 2021.
- [LCM+22] F. Liu, Y. Cui, C. Masouros, J. Xu, T. X. Han, Y. C. Eldar, and S. Buzzi, "Integrated Sensing and Communications: Toward Dual-Functional Wireless Networks for 6G and Beyond," IEEE Journal on Selected Areas in Communications, vol. 40, no. 6, pp. 1728-1767, June 2022.
- [LHL+22] A. Liu, Z. Huang, M. Li, Y. Wan, W. Li, T. X. Han, C. Liu, et al., "A Survey on Fundamental Limits of Integrated Sensing and Communication," IEEE Communications Surveys & Tutorials 24, vol. 24, no. 2, pp. 994-1034, Feb. 2022.
- [LLL+24] P. Li, M. Li, R. Liu, Q. Liu, and A. L. Swindlehurst, "MIMO-OFDM ISAC Waveform Design for Range-Doppler Sidelobe Suppression," IEEE Transactions on Wireless Communications, vol. 24, no. 2, pp. 1001-1015, Nov. 2024.
- [LML+18] F. Liu, C. Masouros, A. Li, H. Sun, and L. Hanzo, "MU-MIMO Communications with MIMO Radar: From Co-existence to Joint Transmission," IEEE Transactions on Wireless Communications, vol. 17, no. 4, pp. 2755-2770, April 2018.
- [LW18] C. F. Lopez and C.-X. Wang, "Novel 3-D Non-Stationary Wideband Models for Massive MIMO Channels," IEEE Transactions on Wireless Communications, vol. 17, no. 5, pp. 2893–2905, May 2018.
- [LWG+23] Y. Lai, L. Venturino, E. Grossi, and W. Yi, "Joint Detection and Localisation in Distributed MIMO Radars Employing Waveforms with Imperfect Auto- and Cross-correlation," IEEE Transactions on Vehicular Technology, vol. 72, no. 12, pp. 16524–16537, Sep. 2023.
- [LZZ23] Y. Liu, et al., "A Shared Cluster-based Stochastic Channel Model for Integrated Sensing and Communication Systems," IEEE Transactions on Vehicular Technology, vol. 73, no. 5, pp. 6032-6044, Nov. 2023.

- [MDD+23] T. Malherbe, R. D'Errico, C. Delaveaud, and P. Pouliguen, "An Approximate Model of Near Field RCS based on Physical Optics," Proc. IEEE International Symposium on Antennas and Propagation and USNC-URSI Radio Science Meeting 2023 (IEEE AP-S/URSI'23), Portland, pp. 901-902, July 2023.
- [MdEO20] A. Mudonhi, R. D'Errico, and C. Oestges, "Indoor mmWave Channel Characterisation with Large Virtual Antenna Arrays," Proc. European Conference on Antennas and Propagation 2020 (EuCAP'20), Copenhagen, March 2020.
- [MdEO22] A. Mudonhi, R. D'Errico, and C. Oestges, "Analysis of Multipath Components Distributions Over a Large Array in Indoor mmWave Channels," IEEE Transactions on Antennas and Propagation, vol. 70, no. 9, pp. 8330-8336, Sept. 2022.
- [METIS15] Deliverable D1.4 (v3) "METIS Channel Model" of H2020/METIS 2020, Jul. 2015.
- [MH13] J. Medbo and F. Harrysson, "Channel Modelling for the Stationary UE Scenario," Proc. European Conference on Antennas and Propagation (EuCAP'13), pp. 2811–2815, Gothenburg, Apr. 2013.
- [MLL+24] J. Ma, Q. Li, R. Liu, A. Pandharipande, and X. Ge, "Enhanced Semantic Information Transfer on RIS-Assisted Communication Systems," IEEE Wireless Communications Letters, vol. 13, no. 8, pp. 2225-2229, Aug. 2024.
- [MMM+24] P. Mursia, T. Mazloum, F. Munoz, et al., "Empirical Validation of the Impedance-Based RIS Channel Model in an Indoor Scattering Environment," Proc. European Conference on Antennas and Propagation 2024 (EuCAP'24), Glasgow, March 2024.
- [mmMAGIC16] Deliverable D2.1 "Measurement Campaigns and Initial Channel Models for Preferred Suitable Frequency Ranges" of H2020-ICT-671650/mmMAGIC, March 2016.
- [MMS+24] T. Mazloum, et al., "Indoor Channel Characterisation using Transmitting and Reflecting RIS at mmWaves", IEEE Transaction on Antennas and Propagation, vol. 73, no. 4, pp. 2026-2037, Nov. 2024.
- [MPM+21] M. A. Uusitalo, et al., "6G Vision, Value, Use Cases and Technologies from European 6G Flagship Project Hexa-X," IEEE Access, vol. 9, pp. 160004–160020, Nov. 2021.
- [MPS+23] P. Mursia, S. Phang, V. Sciancalepore, G. Gradoni, and M. D. Renzo, 'SA-RIS: Scattering Aware Reconfigurable Intelligent Surface Model and Optimization for Complex Propagation Channels', IEEE Wireless Communications Letters, vol. 12, no. 11, pp. 1921–1925, 2023.
- [NGU25] Q. D. M. Nguyen, W. D. Lukito, X. Liu, and C. Liu, "Deep Learning-Empowered RF Sensing in Outdoor Environments: Recent Advances, Challenges, and Future Directions", Electronics, vol. 14, is. 1, 2025
- [NMM+19] N. Vukmirovic, et al., "Direct Wideband Coherent Localisation by Distributed Antenna Arrays," Sensors, vol. 19, no. 20, p. 4582, 2019.
- [NMP21] N. Vukmirovic, et al., "Performance Limits of Direct Wideband Coherent 3D Localisation in Distributed Massive MIMO Systems," Sensors, vol. 21, no. 10, p. 3401, 2021.

- [NYUSIM] S. Ju, et al., "A Millimeter-Wave Channel Simulator NYUSIM with Spatial Consistency and Human Blockage," Proc. IEEE Global Communications Conference 2019 (IEEE GLOBECOM'19), Waikoloa, Dec. 2019
- [OBL19] Ö. Özdogan, E. Björnson, E. G. Larsson, "Intelligent Reflecting Surfaces: Physics, Propagation, and Pathloss Modelling," IEEE Wireless Communication Letters, vol. 9, no. 5, pp. 581–585, May 2020.
- [OOM+18] D. O'Loughlin, et al., "Microwave Breast Imaging: Clinical Advances and Remaining Challenges," IEEE Transactions on Biomedical Engineering, vol. 65, no. 11, pp. 2580–2590, Nov. 2018.
- [PNW19] B. Pang, E. Nijkamp, and Y. N. Wu, "Deep Learning With TensorFlow: A Review," Journal of Educational and Behavioral Statistics, vol. 45, is. 2, pp. 227-248, Sept. 2019.
- [PRL+18] J. A. del Peral-Rosado, R. Raulefs, J. A. LÃspez-Salcedo, and G. Seco-Granados, "Survey of Cellular Mobile Radio Localisation Methods: From 1G to 5G," IEEE Communication Surveys and Tutorials, vol. 20, no. 2, pp. 1124– 1148, 2018.
- [RDM+24] J. C. Ruiz-Sicilia, M. Di Renzo, P. Mursia, A. Kaushik, and V. Sciancalepore, "Spatial Multiplexing in Near-Field Line-of-Sight MIMO Communications: Paraxial and Non-Paraxial Deployments," IEEE Transactions on Green Communications and Networking, vol. 9, no. 1, pp. 338-353, June 2024.
- [RMG+24] M. Rossanese, P. Mursia, A. Garcia-Saavedra, V. Sciancalepore, A. Asadi and X. Costa-Perez, "Open Experimental Measurements of Sub-6GHz Reconfigurable Intelligent Surfaces," IEEE Internet Computing, vol. 28, no. 2, pp. 19-28, March-April 2024.
- [RMG+24b] M. Rossanese, P. Mursia, A. Garcia-Saavedra, V. Sciancalepore, A. Asadi, X. Costa-Perez, "Design and Validation of Scalable Reconfigurable Intelligent Surfaces", Computer Networks, vol. 241, 2024.
- [RS19] M. Rupp and S. Schwarz, "An LS Localisation Method for Massive MIMO Transmission Systems," Proc. IEEE International Conference on Acoustics, Speech and Signal Processing 2019 (IEEE ICASSP'19), pp. 4375–4379, Brighton, May 2019.
- [SAG+24] E.C. Strinati, G.C. Alexandropoulos, M. Giyyarpuram, P. Sehier, S. Mekki, V. Sciancalepore, M. Stark, M. Sana, B. Denis, M. Crozzoli, and N. Amani, "Distributed Intelligent Integrated Sensing and Communications: The 6G-DISAC Approach," Proc. Joint European Conference on Networks and Communications & 6G Summit 2024 (EuCNC/6G Summit'24), pp. 392-397, Antwerp, June 2024.
- [SBL21] Z. H. Shaik, et al., "MMSE-Optimal Sequential Processing for Cell-Free Massive MIMO with Radio Stripes," IEEE Transactions on Communication, vol. 69, no. 11, pp. 7775–7789, Nov. 2021.
- [SCM22] S. Shen, B. Clerckx, and R. Murch, 'Modeling and Architecture Design of Reconfigurable Intelligent Surfaces Using Scattering Parameter Network Analysis', IEEE Transactions on Wireless Communications, vol. 21, no. 2, pp. 1229–1243, 2022.

- [SDD23] M. Sana, H. Dakdouk, B. Denis, "Sensing of Side Lobes Interference for Blockages Prediction in Dense mmWave Networks", Proc. IEEE International Symposium on Personal, Indoor and Mobile Radio Communications 2023 (IEEE PIMRC'23), Toronto, Sept. 2023.
- [SGA25] K. Stylianopoulos, P. Gavriilidis, and G. C. Alexandropoulos, "Graph-CNNs for RF imaging: Learning the electric field integral equations," submitted to European Signal Processing Conference 2025 (EuSIPCO'25).
- [SGD+18] A. Shahmansoori, G. E. Garcia, G. Destino, G. Seco-Granados, and H. Wymeersch, "Position and Orientation Estimation Through Millimeter-Wave MIMO in 5G Systems," IEEE Transactions on Wireless Communications, vol. 17, no. 3, pp. 1822–1835, March 2018.
- [SKM+13] E. Schubert, M. Kunert, W. Menzel, J. Fortuny-Guasch, and J.-M. Chareau, "Human RCS Measurements and Dummy Requirements for the Assessment of Radar Based Active Pedestrian Safety Systems," Proc. International Radar Symposium 2013 (IRS'13), vol. 2, pp. 752–757, Dresden, June 2013.
- [SLF+23] E. P. Simon, P. Laly, J. Farah, E. Tanghe, W. Joseph, and D. P. Gaillot, "Measurement of the V2I Channel in Cell-free Vehicular Networks with the Distributed MaMIMOSA Channel Sounder," Proc. European Conference on Antennas and Propagation 2023 (EuCAP'23), Florence, 2023.
- [SM11] J. Salmi and A. F. Molisch, "Propagation Parameter Estimation, Modelling and Measurements for Ultrawideband MIMO Radar," IEEE Transactions on Antennas and Propagation, vol. 59, no. 11, pp. 4257–67, Nov. 2011.
- [SMJ+25] K. Stylianopoulos, G. Madhusudan, G. Jornod, S. Mekki, F. Costanzo, H. Chen, P. Mursia, M. Crozzoli, E. C. Strinati, G. C. Alexandropoulos, and H. Wymeersch, "Distributed Intelligent Sensing and Communications for 6G: Architecture and Use Cases," to appear in Proc. Joint European Conference on Networks and Communications & 6G Summit 2025 (EuCNC & 6G Summit'25), Poznan, June 2025.
- [SMM24] S. Ye, M. Xiao, M. W. Kwan, Z. Ma, Y. Huang, G. Karagiannidis, and P. Fan, "Extremely Large Aperture Array (ELAA) Communications: Foundations, Research Advances and Challenges," IEEE Open Journal of the Communications Society, vol. 5, pp. 7075-7120, Oct. 2024.
- [SZM+09] S. Singh, F. Ziliotto, U. Madhow, E. M. Belding, and M. Rodwell, "Blockage and Directivity in 60 GHz Wireless Personal Area Networks: From Cross-Layer Model to Multihop MAC Design," IEEE Journal on Selected Areas in Communications, vol. 28, no. 8, pp. 1400-1413, Oct. 2009.
- [TD23] R. Thomä and T. Dallmann, "Distributed ISAC Systems—Multisensor Radio Access and Coordination," Proc. European Radar Conference 2023 (EuRAD'23), pp. 351-354, Berlin, Sept. 2023.
- [TSM+21] H. Tataria, M. Shafi, A. F. Molisch, M. Dohler, H. Sjöland, and F. Tufvesson, "6G Wireless Systems: Vision, Requirements, Challenges, Insights, and Opportunities," Proceedings of the IEEE, vol. 109, is. 7, pp. 1166–1199, March 2021.
- [TT97] J. M. Taylor and A. J. Terzuoli, "On the Concept of Near Field Radar Cross Section," Proc. IEEE Antennas and Propagation Society International Symposium 1997, vol.2, pp. 1172-1175, Montreal, July 1997.

- [W+24] Z. Weng, et al., "Semantic MIMO Systems for Speech-to-Text Transmission," *IEEE Transactions on Wireless Communications*, vol. 23, no. 12, pp. 18697-18710, Dec. 2024.
- [WBS+04] Z. Wang, et al. "Image Quality Assessment: from Error Visibility to Structural Similarity," *IEEE Transactions on Image Processing*, vol. 13, no. 4, pp. 600-612, April 2004
- [WC18] Z. Wei and X. Chen, "Deep-Learning Schemes for Full-Wave Nonlinear inverse Scattering Problems," *IEEE Transactions on Geoscience Remote Sensing*, vol. 57, no. 4, pp. 1849–1860, 2019.
- [WLW+18] F. Wen, P. Liu, H. Wei, Y. Zhang, R. C. Qiu, "Joint Azimuth, Elevation, and Delay Estimation for 3-D Indoor Localisation," *IEEE Transactions on Vehicular Technology*, vol. 67, no. 5, pp. 4248-4261, May 2018.
- [WZZ+22] J. Wang, et al., "Empirical Analysis of Sensing Channel Characteristics and Environment Effects at 28 GHz," *Proc. IEEE Global Communication Conference 2022 (IEEE GLOBECOM'22) Workshops*, pp. 1323–28, Rio de Janeiro, Dec. 2022.
- [YA20] A. Yazar and H. Arslan, "A Waveform Parameter Assignment Framework for 6G with the Role of Machine Learning," *IEEE Open Journal of Vehicular Technology*, vol. 1, pp. 156–172, May 2020.
- [YBK21] M. Yang, C. Bian, and H.-S. Kim, "Deep Joint Source Channel Coding for Wireless Image Transmission with OFDM," *Proc. IEEE International Conference on Communications 2021 (IEEE ICC'21)*, Montreal, June 2021.
- [YQZ+22] L. Yan, Z. Qin, R. Zhang, Y. Li, and G. Y. Li, "Resource Allocation for Text Semantic Communications," *IEEE Wireless Communications Letters*, vol. 11, no. 7, pp. 1394–1398, July 2022.
- [YZJ23] Z. Yuan, J. Zhang, Y. Ji, et al., "Spatial Non-Stationary Near-Field Channel Modelling and Validation for Massive MIMO Systems," *IEEE Transactions on Antennas and Propagation*, vol. 71, no. 1, pp. 921–933, Jan. 2023.
- [YZW+22] Y. Yang, Y. Zheng, C.-X. Wang, et al., "Channel Capacities of Nonstationary 6G Massive MIMO Channels with Mutual Coupling Verified by Channel Measurements," in *Proc. IEEE International Symposium on Personal Indoor and Mobile Radio Communications*, Kyoto, Sept. 2022.
- [ZCC+24] Y. Zhang, T. Choi, Z. Cheng, J. Gomez-Ponce, I. Kanno, M. Ito, and A. F. Molisch, "Cell-Free Massive MIMO Channels in an Urban Environment-Measurements and Channel Statistics", *IEEE Transactions on Wireless Communications*, Early Access, 2024.
- [ZGF+15] Z. Zhou, X. Gao, J. Fang, et al., "Spherical Wave Channel and Analysis for Large Linear Array in LoS Conditions," in *Proc. IEEE Global Communication Conference 2015 (IEEE GLOBECOM'15) Workshops*, San Diego, Dec. 2015.
- [ZHA+23] Z. Zhang, et al., "A General Channel Model for Integrated Sensing and Communication Scenarios," *IEEE Communication Magazine*, vol. 61, no. 5, pp. 68–74, May 2023.
- [ZJY23] Z. Zhang, T. Jiang, and W. Yu. "Localisation with Reconfigurable Intelligent Surface: An Active Sensing Approach," *IEEE Transactions on Wireless Communications*, vol 23, no. 7, pp. 7698-7711, Dec. 2023.

- [ZOY14] K. Zheng, S. Ou, X. Yin, "Massive MIMO channel models: A survey," International Journal on Antennas and Propagation, vol. 2014, no. 11, June 2014.
- [ZWY+23] Y. Zheng, C.-X. Wang, R. Yang, et al., "Ultra-Massive MIMO Channel Measurements at 5.3 GHz and a General 6G Channel Model," IEEE Transaction on Vehicular Technology, vol. 72, no. 1, pp. 20–34, Jan. 2023.

9 Appendices

Table 9-1: Mapping table between main D3.1 and D4.1 technical contributions.

D3.1		D4.1 [6GDISAC-D41]	
Technical item nb / Section nb	Topic	Technical item nb / Section nb	Topic
#A-1 / Sec. 4.1	Waveform for semantic mapping and control	#P-7 / Sec. 3.2	Protocol for sensing using semantic waveforms
#A-2 / Sec. 4.2.1	Machine-learning-based RIS control for robust localisation	#P-3 / Sec. 3.1	Protocol for orchestration of RIS devices
#A-3 / Sec. 4.2.2	Beam model for hardware-aware calibration for ISAC	#P-2 / Sec. 3.1	Protocol for sensing of connected targets
#A-4 / Sec. 4.3.1	ISAC signalling for secure dual-function BS	#P-1 / Sec. 3.1	Protocol for sensing of non-connected targets
#A-5 / Sec. 4.3.2	Joint channel and location	#P-2 / Sec. 3.1	Protocol for sensing of connected targets
#B-1 / Sec. 5.1.1	Joint RIS channel and UE position estimation	#P-3 / Sec. 3.1	Protocol for orchestration of RIS devices
#B-2 / Sec. 5.1.2	LoS-aware sync and angle estimation with multiple RISs	#P-3 / Sec. 3.1	Protocol for orchestration of RIS devices
#B-3 / Sec. 5.1.3	Joint localisation and synchronisation	#P-2 / Sec. 3.1	Protocol for sensing of connected targets
#B-4 / Sec. 5.1.4	Joint localisation, synchronisation, and mapping with multiple RISs	#P-3 / Sec. 3.1	Protocol for orchestration of RIS devices
#B-5 / Sec. 5.1.5	Near-field ELAA localisation	#P-4 / Sec. 3.1	Dynamic beam searching
#B-6 / Sec. 5.1.6	UE tracking with mobile-mounted RIS	#P-3 / Sec. 3.1	Protocol for orchestration of RIS devices
#B-7 / Sec. 5.1.7	Opportunistic localisation based on RIS reflections	#P-2 / Sec. 3.1	Protocol for sensing of connected targets
#B-8 / Sec. 5.2.1	Ambiguity removal on sensing signals	#P-2 / Sec. 3.1	Protocol for sensing of connected targets
#B-9 / Sec. 5.2.2	Blockage detection and localisation on dense networks	#P-2 / Sec. 3.1	Protocol for sensing of connected targets
#B-10 / Sec. 5.2.3	Detection of moving objects using RIS	#P-5 / Sec. 3.1	Protocol for RIS-empowered sensing

#B-11 / Sec. 5.2.4	Target handover for sensing with increased FoV	#P-1 / Sec. 3.1	Protocol for sensing of non-connected targets
#B-12 / Sec. 5.2.5	Joint detection and localisation of multiple moving Targets	#P-1 / Sec. 3.1	Protocol for sensing of non-connected targets
#B-13 / Sec. 5.2.6	Passive object detection using RIS	#P-1 / Sec. 3.1	Protocol for sensing of non-connected targets
#B-14 / Sec. 5.2.7	Distributed imaging of surfaces	#P-1 / Sec. 3.1	Protocol for sensing of non-connected targets
#B-15 / Sec. 5.2.8	Object sensing through digital twins	#P-1 / Sec. 3.1	Protocol for sensing of non-connected targets
#C-1 / Sec. 6.1	Target handover mechanism	#P-6 / Sec. 3.2	Protocol for exchange of data representations
#C-2 / Sec. 6.2	FD joint sensing and communication	#P-1 / Sec. 3.1	Protocol for sensing of non-connected targets
#C-3 / Sec. 6.3	Location-based beam tracking	#P-4 / Sec. 3.1	Protocol for dynamic beam searching